

MANSOURA UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
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APPLYING REMOTE SENSING AND MORPHOLOGICAL MODELING IN CONTROLLING COASTAL ZONE PROBLEMS

BY

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Acknowledging that the novelty of the subject of the research study and the research title have never been used in its final full form or previously published in any papers, thesis, books, research, or any scientific publications, and in line with the scientific integrity recognized in the writing of scientific papers and thesis.

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ABSTRACT

The Nile Delta, one of the most prosperous and highly inhabited regions in Egypt, faces significant environmental challenges due to non-human and human-induced factors. Over the past few decades, the delta has experienced profound variations in its shoreline, driven by sediment supply disruptions, sea-level rise, and human activities, such as building dams. The Aswan High Dam, in particular, has played a pivotal role in reducing the natural flow of sediment to the delta, which historically replenished coastal areas and counteracted erosion. As a result, several areas of the delta, particularly along the Damietta and Rosetta branches, have seen accelerated coastal retreat, threatening nearby populations, amenities and agriculture.

The Nile Delta's shifting coastline is exacerbated by climate change, which raises ocean sea levels and amplifies storms. Vulnerability analyses are crucial to the delta's long-term sustainability because of the region's elevated risk of coastal erosion and floods due to a combination of reasons. Assessing variables like Geomorphology, Elevation, Coastal slope, Bathymetry, Shoreline chang, Significant wave height, Tidal range, Sea level change, Land subsidence, Wave Orientation, Atificial Alternatives, land use, and distance to urban regions, as vulnerability variables aids in identifying the most at-risk regions. The Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) was calculated by synthesizing the rankings of each parameter via two separate methodologies: the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Gornitz's methodology. Gornitz's approach combines factors and simply standardizes their weight and significance in order to assess the vulnerability of coastal regions to sea-level rising (SLR). The Analytic Hirarchy Process (AHP) model, on the other hand, provides a more thorough and organized method that is helpful when making decisions. It combines professional judgment with the conversion of qualitative data into quantitative weights, enabling the ranking of factors according to their impact. All things considered, AHP offers a more precise evaluation of coastal risk, assisting planners in identifying regions in need of quick care. The findings derived from the AHP model indicate that, on average, 128 km (approximately 40%) of the coastline is situated within a very high to

Abstract

high vulnerability zone, particularly in areas such as Abo-Khashba Bay (75%), Abu-Qir Bay and Rosetta Headland (48%), and the western sector of Alexandria (25%), necessitating increased scrutiny. These evaluations are crucial for guiding coastal management tactics, land-use planning, and disaster readiness.

Numerical modeling, such as the coastal modeling system (CMS), makes it feasible to comprehend the dynamics of sediment transport, shoreline evolution, and the effects of coastal protection structures, particularly for sites of critical importance like Damietta Harbor. Models provide insights into how future changes can affect the harbor and the nearby beaches by simulating various scenarios for development plans adopted by Egyptian government. This thesis examined eight choices, such as deepening the navigation channel, building a new western breakwater, and extending the eastern and western breakwaters. The findings indicated the amounts of sediment in each scenario's navigation channel within Damietta Harbor and how they affected the beaches nearby. According to the calculations, scenario 8 fared better than the others and deposited 72.1% less silt to the entry region annually than the benchmark case.

These models also help in the design of effective initiatives, such as dredging programs or breakwaters, to lessen sedimentation problems and halt erosion. Stakeholders may create better educated coastal management policies and ensure the long-term resilience of the Nile Delta against the growing threats of climate change and man-made activities by integrating numerical modeling with risk assessments.

CONTENTS

Subject	Pages
Acknowledgments	<i>i</i>
Abstract.....	<i>ii</i>
Contents.....	<i>iii</i>
List of Figures	<i>vi</i>
List of Tables	<i>ix</i>
List of Equations	<i>x</i>
List of abbreviation.....	<i>Xi</i>
Chapter 1 Introduction	<i>1</i>
1.1 Introduction.....	<i>1</i>
1.2 Shoreline Definition.....	<i>2</i>
1.3 Climate Change.....	<i>2</i>
1.3.1 Sea level rise (SLR).....	<i>3</i>
1.3.2 The potential impact of sea level rise SLR.....	<i>4</i>
1.4 Nile Delta.....	<i>5</i>
1.5 Shoreline Changes and Coastal Vulnerability Index.....	<i>6</i>
1.6 Numerical Modelling	<i>9</i>
1.7 Scope of The Present Study	<i>14</i>
1.8 Layout of The Thesis	<i>15</i>
References.....	<i>16</i>
Chapter 2 Assessment of human interventions presence and their impact on shoreline changes along Nile delta, Egypt.....	<i>20</i>
Abstract	<i>20</i>
2.1 Introduction	<i>21</i>
2.2 Study area	<i>23</i>
2.3 Methodology.....	<i>24</i>
2.3.1 Data collection and shoreline extraction	<i>24</i>
2.3.2 Shoreline changes.....	<i>26</i>
2.3.3 Shoreline prediction by using LRR.....	<i>26</i>
2.4 Results and discussion.....	<i>28</i>
2.4.1 Analysis of shoreline changes for different zones.....	<i>29</i>
2.4.2 Future shoreline changes in 2030, 2050 and in 2100.....	<i>43</i>
2.5 Conclusion.....	<i>45</i>
References.....	<i>47</i>
Chapter 3 Evaluation of coastal risks to Sea level rise: Case Study of Nile Delta Coast.....	<i>50</i>
Abstract	<i>50</i>

3.1 Introduction.....	51
3.2 Study area	53
3.3 Methodology.....	55
3.3.1 Definition parameters and data sources.....	55
3.3.2 Mapping Parameters and Data.....	56
3.3.2.1 Remote Sensing parameters and data.....	56
3.3.2.2 Other parameters and data.....	57
3.3.3 CVI calculation method	59
3.3.3.1 Gornitz's method.....	59
3.3.3.2 Analytical hierarchy process 'AHP method'.....	62
3.4 Results	63
3.4.1 Geomorphology	63
3.4.2 Elevation.....	64
3.4.3 Coastal slope	64
3.4.4 Bathymetry.....	65
3.4.5 Shoreline change	66
3.4.6 Significant wave height.....	67
3.4.7 Tidal range	68
3.4.8 Sea level change	68
3.4.9 Land subsidence	68
3.4.10 Artificial protection structures.....	68
3.4.11 Wave direction	69
3.4.12 Distance to urban.....	71
3.4.13 Land Use Land Cover LULC.....	71
3.4.14 Calculation of CVI	74
3.5 Discussion	78
3.6 Conclusion.....	81
References	82
Chapter 4 Impact evaluation of development plans in the Egyptian harbors on morphological changes using numerical simulation (case study: Damietta harbor, northeastern coast of Egypt).....	89
Abstract	89
4.1 Introduction.....	90
4.2 Study area	92
4.3 Materials and methods.....	94
4.3.1 Remote sensing study.....	94
4.3.1.1 Dataset and Processing.....	94
4.3.1.2 Shoreline extraction and analysis.....	95
4.3.2 Morpho-dynamics study.....	95
4.3.2.1 Field Observation Data.....	95
4.3.2.2 Hydrodynamic Model Description.....	97
4.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	103
4.4.1 Shoreline analysis results	103

4.4.2 Numerical simulation results	106
4.4.2.1 The influence of designed scenarios on DH's navigation channel	106
4.4.2.2 The influence of designed scenarios on adjacent beaches.....	110
4.4.2.3 The influence of deepening navigation channel on sedimentation problem,.....	111
4.4.2.4 The influence of planned coastal structures at the eastern side of harbor,.....	113
4.5 Conclusion.....	115
References	116
Chapter 5 Conclusions and Recommendations.....	121
5.1 Summary and conclusion.....	121
5.2 Recommendations	124
Appendix I for the first research	125
Appendix II for the second research.....	127
Appendix III for the Third research.....	134

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure No.</i>	<i>Caption</i>	<i>Page</i>
Figure 1.1	Coastal areas hazards	2
Figure 1.2	Different scenarios in Damietta harbor proposed by Khalifa, 2017	10
Figure 1.3	Dimension of sediment trap in Damietta harbor proposed by Khalifa, 2017.....	11
Figure 1.4	Explained a) Breakwaters parameters, b) littoral transport and wave dominant, c) Description α_3 , α_4 (Ytiksek, 1995).....	12
Figure 1.5	Bypassing sand system proposed by Nassar et al., 2019	13
Figure 1.6	Proposed scenarios by Masria et al. 2021.	14
Figure 2.1	Location of the research area	25
Figure 2.2	Shorelines extraction from 1985 to 2022	27
Figure 2.3	Flowchart of the overall technique conducted in this research	28
Figure 2.4	Alexandria coast (zone 1).....	31
Figure 2.5	Rates of Erosion and accretion LRR along the Nile delta coast in a)1985-2000, b) 2000-2010, C) 2010-2022	39
Figure 2.6	Shoreline changes “LRR” for long term period 1985-2022 at different locations	40
Figure 2.7	Summary of protection structures along Nile delta coast	41
Figure 2.8	Recent development along the study area	42
Figure 2.9	Shoreline changes between 2016-2022 at the recently executed structures	43
Figure 2.10	NSM distance between digitalized and predicted shoreline in 2022 at each transect.	44
Figure 2.11	Future shoreline changes from 1985 -2100: a) Rosetta promontory, b) Burullus headland, C) Damietta promontory	45
Figure 3.1	Location of study area	55
Figure 3.2	Methodological framework for vulnerability assessment	61
Figure 3.3	Inundation areas under scenarios SLR of 0.5m, 1.0m	64
Figure 3.4	Mapping of A) coastal elevation and B) coastal slope.....	66
Figure 3.5	Decision matrix for shoreline changes along Nile Delta.....	67
Figure 3.6	Artificial structures along Nile Delta coast at A) Rosetta promontory Burullus Headland, C) Damietta promontory, and D) El-Gamil inlet	69
Figure 3.7	Wave rose diagram for the locations: A) Rosetta Headland, B) Burullus Headland, C) Damietta Headland.....	70
Figure 3.8	LULC classification for Nile Delta region	72
Figure 3.9	a) Mapping vulnerability of Geomorphology, Elevation, Coastal slope, Bathymetry, Shoreline change, b) Mapping vulnerability of Hs, Tidal range, SLR, land subsidence, Artificial protection, c) Mapping vulnerability of Wave direction, Distance to urban, LULC.....	73
Figure 3.10	Percentage of the vulnerability of each parameter on the Nile Delta	74

Figure 3.11	coast Coastal vulnerability mapping by using Gornitz's model along Nile Delta coast: A) Alexandria coast, B) Rosetta, C) Burullus, D) Damietta, E) Port Said coast.	76
Figure 3.12	Coastal vulnerability mapping by using AHP model along the Nile Delta coast: A) Alexandria coast, B) Rosetta, C) Burullus, D) Damietta, E) Port Said coast.	77
Figure 3.13	Correlation test between Gornitz's and AHP model.	78
Figure 3.14	Distribution of CVI scores (%) for Egypt's Nile Delta coast for a) Gornitz's model, b) AHP model.	81
Figure 4.1	Study area location.	94
Figure 4.2	Shoreline extraction and human interventions along Damietta coast: a) DH in 2016 and 2023, b) Y-gs east of DH in 2016 and 2023, c) DBW along Ras-Elbar resort, d) Jetties at Damietta promontory, e) Wave rose at DH entrance.	97
Figure 4.3	Bathymetry and Meteorological data.	97
Figure 4.4	Model grids with boundary condition for DH, (a) CMS-Flow grid; (b) CMS-Wave grid; A) Hard bottom cells at the DH entrance in CMS-Flow; B) Rubble mound cells at the DH entrance in CMS-Wave....	99
Figure 4.5	Explained a) Profiles location east DH, b) Bathymetry map 2016, c) Morphology change after simulation for 2017 using VanRijn formula.	100
Figure 4.6	Estimated values of NRMSE and R2 between the measured and calculated depth in 2017 for (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; and (c) Profile 3 for different manning coefficient n (sediment formula VanRijn, time step = 450 s, scaling factor = 2.0 and adaptation length = 20 m).. ..	101
Figure 4.7	Estimated values of NRMSE and R2 between the measured and calculated depth in 2017 for (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; and (c) Profile 3 for different sediment formula (Manning coefficient n = 0.01, time step = 450 s, Scaling factor = 2.0 and adaptation length = 20 m). ...	102
Figure 4.8	Proposed scenarios in CMS modeling.	103
Figure 4.9	Shoreline changes showing accretion and erosion patterns along DH coast: a) Shoreline changes between 2020- 2023, b) Shoreline changes between 2005- 2016, c) EPR rates along Damietta coast in the period of 2020-2023, d) Overall accretion and erosion areas from 1985- 2023.	105
Figure 4.10	Explained a) Profile locations, and Morphology changes after one-year simulation for b) Benchmark case, c) Scenario 1, d) Scenario 2, e) Scenario 3, f) Scenario 4, g) Scenario 5, h) Scenario 6, j) Scenario 7, k) Scenario 8.	108
Figure 4.11	Bed elevation inside DH inlet for three cross sections (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; (c) Profile 3, and one longitudinal section (d) Profile 4. .	109
Figure 4.12	A comparison of sediment volumes (m ³ /y) in the navigation channel based on Benchmark and the designed scenarios.	110
Figure 4.13	Explained a) Profile location, Morphology changes for b) Current	112

	state 15 m deepening, c) 16 m deepening, d) 17 m deepening, e) 18 m deepening, f) Future-plan of 19 m deepening, g) Wave height distribution.	
Figure 4.14	Explained A) Sediment volume accumulation for each navigation depth m ³ /y, b), c), d), e), f) Bed elevation in port entrance for five cross-section profiles of different navigation depth.....	113
Figure 4.15	Proposed scenarios at the eastern side of port.....	114
Figure 4.16	Morphology changes for a) 4 Y gs only east of harbor at 15 m deepening, b) 4 Y gs only at 19 m deepening, c) 4 Y gs + DBW at 15 m deepening, d) 4 Y gs + DBW at 19 m deepening, e) Wave distribution at planned coastal structures	115

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page
Table 1.1	Projected SLR (cm) relative to 1990 sea level (Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021).	4
Table 2.1	Specifics about the satellite images utilized in this study	29
Table 2.2	Ranking of erosion and accretion rates LRR	
Table 2.3	Shoreline change rates LRR in different periods.	
Table 3-1	Details of the sources and time scale of data sets considered	55
Table 3.2	Vulnerability rank assigned to the different CVI parameters investigated.....	62
Table 3.3	The fundamental scale of Saaty, 1977.	63
Table 3.4	Random index for n of parameters.	63
Table 3.5	Summary of accuracy and error of land use classification.....	72
Table 3.6	Comparison matrix and criteria weight.....	77
Table 3.7	Consistency index calculations.	77
Table 4.1	Information about the satellite images utilized in this research.	95
Table 4.2	Results from the present study along the Damietta coast compared with the pervious works.	104
Table 4.3	Results from current study for sediment volume in the navigation channel of DH for different scenarios compared to Benchmark case.	110

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

DSAS: Digital Shoreline Analysis system
GIS: Geographic Information System
RS: Remote Sensing System
LRR: Linear Regression Rate
EPR: End point Rate
NSM: Net Shoreline Movement
SCE: Shoreline Change Envelope
MSS: Multispectral Scanner
TM: Thematic Mapper
ETM: Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus
OLI: Operational Land Imager
NDWI: Normalized Difference Water Index
CVI: coastal vulnerability index
AHP: Analytical Hierarchy Process
GHG Green-House Gases
IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
SLR: Sea Level Rise
CC: Climate Change
LULC: Land Use Land Cover
STRM: Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
DH: Damietta Harbor
EBW: Eastern Breakwater
WBW: Western Breakwater

NWBW: New Western Breakwater

DBW: Detached Breakwater

Y-gs: Y-groins

CMS: Coastal Modelling System

LIST OF EQUATIONS

<i>Plate No.</i>	<i>Caption</i>	<i>Page</i>
Equation 2.1	future shoreline position equation.....	26
Equation 3.1	Wave Energy equation	58
Equation 3.2	Tidal range.....	58
Equation 3.3	Gornitz equation	60
Equation 3.4	Consistency index.....	63
Equation 3.5	Consistency ration	63
Equation 3.6	CVI equation by embedding wight of parameters.....	63
Equation 4.1	NDWI equation	95
Equation 4.2	Bed load transport rate in m ² /sec.....	98
Equation 4.3	Current-related suspended load transport in m ² /sec	99

Chapter (1)

INTRODUCTION

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Coastal areas are acknowledged to be volatile places that are important for sustainable approaches of coastal management. Due to both human activity and natural processes, these locations confront a number of environmental, social, and economic issues (**Fig 1.1**). Coastal erosion, or the process by which rock or sediment is gradually eroded off the shore by wind, waves, currents, and tides, is one of the frequent issues that coastal cities contend with. Its consequences include land loss, damage to infrastructure and property. Among the factors causing coastal erosion include storm surges, natural wave action, rising sea levels, and human activities like building seawalls and groins. Another issue affecting coastal zones is "sea-level rising", which is known as a continuous global increase in the ocean's average level brought on by polar ice melting and climate change. Its effects include increased land loss, disruption of aquatic ecosystems, and incursion of seawater into freshwater aquifers. Global warming, ocean thermal expansion, and thawing glaciers and polar ice sheets are some of its causes. Storm surges and violent weather patterns pose serious dangers, catastrophic coastal inundation, deterioration of beachline, damage to facilities, and a jump in human mortality. "Storm surges" refer to the momentary raises in sea level that occur during storms as a result of high winds velocities and low air pressure. Some of its reasons include hurricanes, cyclones, and typhoons that are exacerbated by climate change. The term "pollution" refers to the contaminating impacts of chemicals, plastics, oil spills, and agricultural runoff on coastal ecosystems and rivers. It harmed marine life, compromised human health, and degraded water quality. When natural sediment transport systems are disrupted by man made's meddling, dredging and sediment disparity frequently follow. It is hampered by the building of ports, dams, and dredging projects that block the flow of sediment. The amount of freshwater accessible for agriculture, drinking, and ecosystems was diminished by the invasion of saltwater. In addition, overdevelopment along the coast has degraded natural ecological systems, heightened the proneness of coastal regions to erosion and flooding, and restricted public enjoyment to beaches due to the growth of the population, tourism, and real estate sectors in these areas. Most of the world's industrial and commercial activities, concentrated in coastal regions. Nearly 60 percent of the global population resides along the coastline

(Quang et al.,2021). The pressures of urbanization and population growth on coastal areas have also led to conflicts over land use, and resource management. By safeguarding and rehabilitating coastal ecosystems, establishing sustainable protective systems, and mitigating pollutants, we may enhance the adaptability and resilience of coastal communities and ecosystems for the foreseeable future.

Fig. 1.1 Coastal areas hazards

1.2 Shoreline definition

Coastline is one of the 27 distinctive characteristics of the earth's surface that the International Geographic Data Committee (IGDC) has acknowledged. According to [El-Zeiny et al. \(2016\)](#), it is the border dividing a body of water from the nearby land. Because of its dynamic character, it is simple to define yet challenging to document. Understanding different coastal dynamics requires accurate coastline delineation as well as long-, seasonal-, and short-term shoreline observation.

1.3 Climate change

It can no longer be denied that climate change is one of the major worldwide phenomena affecting the standard of living, the economy, and prosperity in the modern era ([Raey and Askary, 2020](#)). However, monitoring these climatic shifts might be achieved using a range of analysis of observational information collections, such as the raising ocean sea level and the yearly and seasonal air temperatures. Any rise in air temperature carries the risk

of hastening sea level rise and escalating flooding events and storm surges. Due to human interventions, greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations in the atmosphere have significantly increased worldwide. This has made it possible for visible rays from the sun to reach the earth's surface, but it has prevented longwave radiation—infrared light—emitted from the earth's warmed surface from escaping into space. The observed rise in the average global temperature is being caused by this disparity in radiation absorbance (IPCC, 2007, Raey and Askary, 2020). Global surface temperature averages by 2100 are most likely to rise by 4°C in the worst-case scenario of increasing GHG emissions (IPCC, 2021).

In addition, it is projected that additional environmental problems brought on by climate change, such as coastal erosion, will pose more danger to the people, infrastructure, coastlines, wetland areas and ecosystems along the shore. According to Torresan et al. (2010), there is growing stress on unexpected, interconnected subsystems, which is causing conflicts over usage, a scarcity of coastal resources, and the destruction of natural ecosystems.

1.3.1 Sea level rise (SLR)

One of the most exorbitant and worrisome consequences of climate change on the long-term viability of coastal cities is sea level rise (SLR) (Abou Samra et al., 2021). In fact, the pace of grow in mean sea level worldwide was 1.2 ± 0.2 mm/y between 1900 and 1990, and 3.0 ± 0.7 mm/y between 1993 and 2010 (Yi et al., 2015). SLR expectations under the low GHG emission scenario (SSP1-2.6) could go up above 3 m by 2300, although it is unlikely to surpass 0.62 m by 2100. SLR might expand to 2 m by 2150 (0.98–1.88 m) in the high GHG emission scenario (SSP5-8.5) and 7 m by 2300 (Zhang et al., 2023). Realizing that over a billion people inhabit in coastal low-elevation places or places that are fewer than ten meters above sea level, increasing sea levels are expected to result in a large-scale population relocation (IPCC, 2021).

1.3.2 Sea level rise's possible implications

Major environmental issues connected with SLR and impacting the vital coastal assets, especially in relatively lowlands and heavily populated cities, include destroyed coastlines, storms, and sediment import-induced basin filling, variations in storm and storm surge severity and frequency, overtopping of coastal barriers that eliminates their

effectiveness, and saltwater seeping into ground water aquifers (Elsharkawy et al., 2009; El deberky, 2011; Ahammed and Pandey, 2022). Dasgupta et al. (2009) emphasized how SLR will affect eighty-four developing coastal nations. Many research projects, especially in the Nile Delta, have been conducted to assess the influence of SLR on coastal regions such as:

According to Elsharkawy et al. (2009) estimations of the effect of SLR on Egypt's coastal zones, a number of smaller locations, such as those north of Lake Bradawl and near Matruh, as well as portions of the governorates of Damietta, Suez, Alexandria, Beheira, Port Said, and Damietta, Alexandria, are considered to be extremely susceptible. The consequences of SLR are threatening around 20% of the delta's land. Iskander (2013) examined data on sea level change along Egypt's coast between 1977 and 2010, noting that rates of rise, which took land subsidence into account, varied from 1.6 to 5.3 mm. Hasan et al. (2015) applied the "SRTM" and the "ASTER-GDEM-V2", two publicly accessible Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), to explore the potential effects of Sea Level Rise (SLR) on Egypt's Nile Delta. According to "SRTM DEM data", a 1 m SLR will destroy more than 6 million homes, harm over 3900 km² of agricultural crops, 205 km² of wetlands, and 146 km² of urban zones. According to data from "ASTER-GDEM-V2", a 1 m SLR will induce the forced relocation of around 887 thousand people and the inundating of roughly 580 Km². As a result, it was believed that the "ASTER-GDEM-V2" dataset produced the best future years forecasts.

Refaat and Eldeberky (2016) evaluated the cross-section profiles and DEM models to gauge the effects on Egypt's Nile delta of a possible 1-m SLR. According to their estimates, 7% of the Nile Delta might inundated. Abou-Mahmoud (2021) used scenario 1 m when tracking the imminent risk of "SLR" in Alexandria, Egypt's coastal districts. The east and center of Alexandria would be under water in the event of floods, but impediments both natural and man-made would keep the water from spreading too far. But the sharp topographical gradient and coastal dune formations in northwestern Alexandria have mostly shielded the area. The Gamasa-Ras El Bar coast in Egypt was the subject of a study conducted in Elshinnawy and Almaliki (2021). Their findings showed that a 73-cm SLR, which was predicted based on historical data (Table 1.1), inundated about 2.16 percent of the study area, primarily the Izbet El Borg locality.

Table 1.1 Projected SLR (cm) relative to 1990 sea level (Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021).

IPCC Scenario	Projected SLR (cm)			
	2025	2050	2075	2100
B1	10.75	19.5	32.5	54
A1T	10.75	26	48.75	61.75
B2	14	35.75	52	58.5
A1B	14	32.5	55.5	65.5
A2	10.75	26	58	70.25
A1F1	14	32.5	59.5	73

1.4 Nile Delta

Where the Mediterranean Sea and the Nile River converge in northern Egypt is the vibrant Nile Delta. Throughout time, the Nile Delta coastline has undergone tremendous alterations due to natural and non-natural interventions. In certain parts of the Nile Delta, natural processes may also be the reason of coastal retreat. The building of dams and other water management projects along the Nile River, such the High dam in Aswan, has modified the natural trends of water and sediment movement and may have an influence on coastal equilibrium. The 100–115 million m³/y of sediments dumped into the Mediterranean were picked up by the Rosetta and Damietta promontories, together with the beaches of the surrounding embayment, in the years preceding the installing of the Aswan high dam (El-Asmar et al., 2014). Net coastal progress resulted from these sands' constant replenishment of the beach despite long-shore currents. However, the majority of the flowing sediments were not able to reach the Mediterranean due to the 1964 building of the Aswan High Dam (El-Asmar et al., 2014).

Land reclamation, shoreline modifications, and the development of coastal buildings are the results of the rapid urbanization and expansion of coastal cities in the Nile Delta. These activities may be responsible for both the erosion and the accretion of the shoreline, depending on how they are planned and how they impact the flow of sediment. Furthermore, because the Nile Delta is a Lowland coastal district, SLR and CC may make it more susceptible to floods and eroded of the shoreline.

Monitoring shoreline changes has typically involved a variety of approaching, including field surveys, coastline tracing from topographic maps, and various analyses of aerial pictures. In recent years, the utilize of satellite imagery-based remote sensing techniques

for coastal tracking has grown in popularity due to its effectiveness, low resource needs, and quick coverage of wide regions. Even with its vast collection of publicly available images that facilitates the production of long-term research, the main drawback of the Landsat project is its 30 m spatial resolution.

This study provides a clear explanation for the rates and patterns of shoreline variance as well as the Nile Delta's overall coastal vulnerability.

1-5 Shoreline variance and Coastal vulnerability index

The coastal vulnerability index and the determination of shoreline changes are essential instruments for understanding the dynamic character of coastal regions and evaluating their vulnerability. Regarding changes in coastal accretion and erosion, relevant data on coastline locations was obtained using satellite photographs taken between 1985 and 2022. In order to determine the rates and trends of erosion and accretion, the historical coastline locations are then examined. This might involve assessing both new and old coastal infrastructure, identifying regions of significant erosion or accretion, and monitoring the rate of change in the shoreline. Additionally, coastline predictions for 2030, 2050, and 2100 are provided for the Nile Delta.

The employment of remote sensing as a method for monitoring coastal changes in the Nile Delta has been utilized since [Klemas and Abdel-Kader \(1982\)](#). Previous scholars on shoreline changes reviewed in Nile Delta region such as [Abou Samra and Ali \(2021\)](#) applied Geographical Information System (GIS) and Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) tools to assess changes along the Nile Delta, Egypt between 1984 to 2018. [Dewidar and Bayoumi \(2021\)](#) used 31 Landsat images and DSAS tool to track the fluctuation of abrasion and accumulation patterns along the Nile Delta zone over 46 years, then predict future shoreline alterations. [Abd-Elhamid et al. \(2023\)](#) investigated alterations along Nile Delta's shoreline between 1974 to 2022 using GIS and DSAS tools. The results showed that the erosion pace varied between 30–60 and 10–25 m/yr at Rosetta and Damietta, respectively, but at Manzala, it varied between 8–15 m/yr. [Youssef et al. \(2024\)](#) analyzed Landsat images from 1985 to 2023 to track shoreline variability at Damietta- Port Said coast. The findings explained that the Damietta promontory witnessed the highest average EBR of -34.92 m/yr, follow the Manzala Lake and the El-Tina Plain, with average erosion between -5.28 to -17.32 m/yr.

Data on topography, bathymetry, coastline features, coastal infrastructure, and socioeconomic factors were gathered for the Coastal Vulnerability Assessment. It can be listed and described the coastal risks that include erosion, flooding, and sea level rise. We considered factors like geomorphology, coastal elevation, coastal slope, bathymetry, shoreline change, significant wave height, mean tide range, sea level change, artificial structures, land subsidence, and wave direction, as well as two socioeconomic parameters, distance to urban, land use land cover LULC, when analyzing the vulnerability of the Nile Delta coastal zone. Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Gornitz's model, a Coastal Vulnerability Index, and vulnerability maps, were created to spatially depict the vulnerability levels of Nile Delta' coastal areas. This helps prioritize areas for adaptation and mitigation measures.

Previous studies on coastal vulnerability index reviewed around world such as [Kunte et al. \(2014\)](#) used two socioeconomic related parameters: population and tourist density data, in addition to seven physical and geologic risk related variables: mean tidal range, significant wave height, coastal elevation, rate of sea-level shift, and geomorphology to figure out the vulnerability of the coast for the Indian state of Goa. Depending on the overall level of vulnerability—low, medium, and high—the coastal vulnerability index (CVI) was measured as the product of the ranking variables' square root divided by the overall number of variables. The shoreline vulnerability of the Nigerian coast was defined by [Oloyede et al. \(2021\)](#) calculations of the CVI utilizing Gornitz's and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) , as well as physical and geomorphological factors and socioeconomic data. A combined CVI of 3.29 to 4.70 was calculated using Gornitz's method, and the findings from both methods indicated that 59–65% of Nigeria's coastline is moderately to very vulnerable to SLR.

Using Gornitz's CVI model and the AHP approach, [Hossain et al. \(2022\)](#) evaluated the vulnerability of the Purba Medinipur-Balasore coastline stretch in India. Ten geological and physical characteristics were taken into consideration. It was determined that 13.56% and 11.29%, respectively, of the coastline is extremely sensitive to these hazards based on Gornitz's CVI and AHP models. The most susceptible coastal regions that need for rapid coastal adaptation interventions or modification of adaptation procedures were identified by [Charuka et al. \(2023\)](#) after they used the AHP technique to estimate and map the CVI for the Ghanaian coasts.

The coastal vulnerability index was assessed by [Turriza et al. \(2024\)](#), utilizing 13 factors pertaining to the socioeconomic and physical characteristics of the Campeche state coastlines.

1.6 Numerical modelling

Additionally, this thesis examines the flow field and deposition following the development of Damietta Harbor using a numerical simulation. Numerical Coastal Modeling: A coastal modeling system CMS that can replicate physical processes relevant to shoreline erosion and accretion needs to be chosen. Examples of these processes are waves, tides, sediment transport, and coastal geomorphology. CMS is used to model the sedimentation of Damietta Harbor following development as well as the response of the surrounding beaches. The CMS was set up by defining the boundary conditions, initial conditions, computational domain, and bathymetry. It integrates relevant physical process and sediment transport models. The CMS was calibrated by adjusting model parameters to match observed data, and it was validated by comparing the simulated results with independent data sets. Various scenarios were analyzed to assess their impact on sedimentation in inlets and coastal erosion.

Numerous scholars on Damietta Harbor in Egypt have looked at coastline alterations, concerns with erosion, and siltation by putting forth a number of scenarios, such as three models -- Multicomponent numerical modelling -- was applied by [GAD et al. \(2013\)](#) to eliminate sedimentation problem in Damietta Harbor. This analysis put out four possible scenarios: an angled breakwater is added to the enlarged eastern jetty of solution 1, a submerged dike is added, a 700-meter extension of the eastern breakwater, and a 900-meter extension of the western jetty. [El-Asmar et al. \(2016\)](#) monitored the alterations along the coastal strip at Damietta Harbor-Ras El-Bar using Landsat images for the periods from 1973 to 2015. The results revealed that beach segment between the detached breakwaters and the eastern jetty of the Damietta Harbor experienced erosion with shoreline retreat of -7.43 m/yr, -10.90 m/yr, and -3.11m/yr for during the periods of 1984-1998, 1998-2003, and 2003-2015 respectively.

Concerned about the sedimentation issue in the port of Damietta, where over a million m³ are deposited year, [Khalifa \(2017\)](#) employed numerical simulations Delft 3D to determine the best feasible ways to circumvent the problem of deposition in the shipping channel. They summarized their results in that the most cost-effective scenarios to

increase the trapping efficiency to 84% with annual channel deposition of 127,000 m³ compared with the current state (800,000 m³) involves combining the sediment trap with dimensions of 500* 200* 5 m parallel to the navigation channel in addition to enlarging the western jetty by 100 m (provided in **Fig. 1.2, 1.3**). Also, [Khalifa et al. \(2017\)](#) noticed in satellite images the government's construction of 4 Y-gs east of Damietta Port, thus they used the LITPACK program to do a one-dimensional numerical simulation to forecast coastal alterations. Additionally, they included a variety of pre-planned situations and investigated the results of combining soft and hard protection, including: The optimal way to stabilize the harbor down drift shoreline was determined by the results to be 200,000 m³/year nourishment volumes plus 150,000 m³ through the building time of four Y-gs with 160 m length and 400 m spacing. The nourished area was entirely relieved, and new beaches are beginning to be developed for Ras El-Bar resorts at a rate of 50 m each year.

Using imagery from satellites and geospatial techniques, [Esmail et al. \(2018\)](#) evaluated the response of the shoreline to protective structures throughout the Damietta coastal stretch between 1990 and 2015. Between 1990 and 1999, the breakwaters at Damietta Port had an effect on the behavior of the shorelines. The western portion of the port experiences accretion at a rate of 14.0 m/yr, while the eastern part experiences erosion at a rate of 10.0 m/yr. Even though the erosion rate dropped to 5.0 m/year in 2015, the accretion continued to advance at the same rates.

Using a 2D model CMS, [Masria et al. \(2022\)](#) look at six scenarios to lessen the problem of sedimentation and erosion on the eastern side. There were six scenarios put forth: two 500-meter-long groins at the harbor entrance's eastern side that are perpendicular to the shoreline; a 500-meter extension for the western jetty; combining the initial and subsequent scenarios; two groins on the harbor's western side and two more groins (500 m in length) on the eastern side; the two groins described in state two, together with a sediment trap next to the inlet's western side—all excavated below the initial bed level. The last scenario is the change of breadth of the sediment trap from 200 to 400 m, much like in the fifth scenario. The outcomes displayed that the suggested scenario 4 might attenuate roughly 37.4% of the accumulated sediments after a year of simulation. In the second state, which might be used to lower the accumulated deposits, a mitigation of roughly 20.5% was possible.

Fig. 1.2 Different scenarios in Damietta harbor proposed by Khalifa, 2017: (A) extension of western jetty by 100m, (B) extension of the western jetty by 200m, (C) extension of the western jetty by 300m, (D) Submerged extension of BreakWater (SDW) with -2m crest level, (E) SBW with -4m crest level, (F) 500 m straight Current Deflector Wall (CDW), (G) 500 m CDW with break and (H) 300 m straight CDW.

Fig. 1.3 Dimension of sediment trap in Damietta harbor proposed by Khalifa, 2017.

Also, Numerous studies have addressed the issue of sedimentation in Egyptian ports around the Nile Delta and other ports worldwide, including: Ytiksek (1995) examined the shoaling processes of fisheries harbors using a physical model to investigate the impacts of main and secondary characteristics (such as length, position, and so forth) on fishery harbor shoaling. Shoaling decreases when both L_2 and α_2 grow; nevertheless, L_2 's

influence is greater than α_2 's. These two issues—shoaling and fluctuation—should be at their lowest when α_4 is almost equal to 90° . Increasing L_3 values is neither cost-effective nor appropriate for reducing shoaling. The secondary breakwater ought to be situated such that the dominant wave line from the tip of main breakwater passes on or close to the secondary breakwater [$x_3 = X_A$] (see **Fig. 1.4**).

Sharaan et al. (2018) used CMS modelling to simulate different scenarios on morphological changes of Burullus fishing port. The stability of the harbor entry is enhanced by cutting the middle jetty upper edge by 90 m, as per the modelling results. Alternately, reducing the middle jetty's length by 60 m and substituting an inclined extension for the perpendicular one will lessen the rate of accretion and erosion surrounding the harbor, thus enhancing the coastal area's long-term stability.

Fig. 1.4 Explained a) littoral transport and wave dominant, b) Breakwaters parameters, c) Description α_3, α_4 (Ytiksek, 1995).

In addition to the LITPACK numerical model, which is mostly used to anticipate the shoreline responses, Nassar et al. (2019) introduced CMS-Flow and CMS-Wave to explain the morpho-dynamics condition inside the Bardawil Lagoons artificial western entry. The scenarios that have been suggested: eight groins in scenario 1; eight detached BW in scenario 2; four detached with four groins in scenario 3; bypassing sand

nourishment in scenario 4; building of eight groins with an interim one-time nourishment in scenario 5a; and inclusion of 100,000 m³ of nourishment annually in scenario 5b. The results showed that Scenario 1 has no effect but scenario 2 lessened erosion but still exists. In scenario 3, the long groins help to break up the eastward-flowing littoral drifts, which causes a recession on the downdrift side and severe accretion on the updrift side. This lowers erosion by 1.79 percent. According to **Fig. 1.5**, option four is intended to pour 150,960 m³ of silt annually to the eastern coast for disposal at several locations along the coastline. This is a very good substitute that decreases silt buildup to the western portion of inlet (1) by 54.43% and eroding to the northeast by 62.23%. If a 250,000 m³ one-time feeding had been employed in the spaces between groins during their creation, the optimal decrease of the anticipated area of loss would have been near 91.85%.

Fig. 1.5 Bypassing sand system proposed by Nassar et al., 2019.

Using the CMS model, Masria et al. (2021) investigated the efficacy of newly suggested scenarios of protection against siltation for Burullus fishing harbor as shown in **Fig. 1.6**. According to simulations, SC3 (extension of the left jetty plus five 200-meter-long right groins and two 200-m-long left groins) achieved better outcomes than the present configuration and helped to generate sea depths of more than 2.5 m for the majority of the changed cross-sections.

Fig. 1.6 Proposed scenarios by Masria et al. 2021: SC1 represents 90.0 m-long extension of the main breakwater, SC2 represents SC1 + 5 groins 200 long in the eastern side of port, SC3 represents SC2 + 2 left groins (200 m in length), SC4 represents SC2 + sediment trap (120 × 500 × 3 m).

1.7 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- 1- Assess the regressive change of the coastline during a 37-year period in the Nile Delta.
2. Test the effectiveness and protective function of different kinds of current countermeasures.
3. Use the CVI models to determine which locations are most dangerous and assess how SLR is affecting the Nile Delta shoreline.
4. Use Gornitz's approach and the AHP methodology to visualize the vulnerability system to "SLR" and rank based on 13 characteristics, including geological, physical, and socioeconomic components.
5. Update the trend of shoreline modifications for the Damietta coast from 1977 to 2023 by utilizing Remote sensing methods and the DSAS software.
6. Propose scenarios and assess them using the CMS model in order to simulate a form of reality that the Egyptian government would seek.
7. Investigate the impact of these scenarios on the neighboring beaches, including the facilities that are now in place or about to be constructed in the area east of the Damietta Harbor.

1.8 SCHEME OF THE WORK

The thesis is organized into five chapters, which are provided as follows:

Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

Provides a basic overview of the investigation, including a brief summary and the study's scope.

Chapter 2: Paper 1 titled by "Assessment of human interventions presence and their impact on shoreline changes along Nile delta, Egypt. "

It presents an analysis of shoreline variation along Nile Delta' region using DSAS tool.

Chapter 3: Paper 2 titled "Evaluation of coastal risks to Sea level rise: Case Study of Nile Delta Coast".

It presents overall assessment of vulnerability along Nile Delta' shoreline using two techniques (Gornitz's method and AHP method).

Chapter 4: Paper 3 titled by "Impact evaluation of development plans in the Egyptian harbors on morphological changes using numerical simulation (case study: Damietta harbor, northeastern coast of Egypt) "

- It presents estimates of sedimentation volumes in Damietta harbor following development plans by Egyptian authorities.

Chapter 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

displays a synopsis of the findings, suggestions for more study, and conclusions.

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Chapter (2)

Assessment of human interventions presence and their impact on shoreline changes along Nile Delta, Egypt

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Abstract. Coastal erosion is a natural process, that contributed to shaping the Nile Delta shoreline in Egypt over history. The objective of this research is to investigate shoreline changes, accretion and erosion, and to detect particularly vulnerable locations that require immediate attention. Another goal is to assess the efficiency of coastal installations that have been recently implemented along the study area and to determine whether they have performed their role to the fullest or need additional modifications. A number of Landsat images (TM, ETM+, and OLI) was utilized over 37 years to track the shoreline changes and was analyzed using remote sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS). Digital shoreline analysis system (DSAS) was integrated with LRR model for assessing historical changes for shorelines from the year 1985- 2022 and forecasting future shoreline positions in (2030, 2050, and 2100). The Delta region was divided into eight zones, but only five zones have lately seen the construction of coastal projects. From the results, it was found that the areas around Rosetta promontory, Burullus headland, and Damietta promontory experienced a significant and rapid retreat and with large rates over the study period with average values of -15.7, -3.25, -16.8 m/y, respectively. However, both the coast of Alexandria, and Gamasa embayment were subjected to accretion as a prevailing case with average rates of 2.85, and 4.03 m/y, respectively. A number of groins was installed in the east of the Rosetta promontory (zone 3) in 2016 to decrease the erosion process, however, it didn't pay off and could not solve the problem. In contrast, the groins system, which was implemented at the East Kitchener Drain (zone 5)

in the same year, lowered erosion rates from 17.6 m/y from 2000 to 2010 to 7 m/y from 2010 to 2022. In 2019, Y-groins built in Zone 7, east of Damietta Port, succeeded in slowing rates of erosion. Finally, inlet jetties at El-Gamil (zone 8), were constructed in 2016, resulting in the coastline advancing at 14.7 m/y on average in the period of 2010-2022. The findings of this study confirmed that hard structures are dangerous because they exacerbate the problem of shoreline erosion by disseminating it to the neighboring beaches and acting as an impediment to the movement of longshore sediments. According to the expected future shoreline patterns, it is necessary for authorities to implement both short-term and long-term protective measures to stop the erosion of several areas of the beaches.

Keywords Shoreline changes -Nile Delta -Landsat image -DSAS software- LRR model

2.1 Introduction

Natural processes and human interventions as well as coastal development itself, have all contributed to continuous changes in coastal zones (Niya et al., 2013; Thielor and Hammar-Klose, 1999). The Nile Delta, like other deltas around the world, is susceptible to rapid changes in its shorelines, including erosion problems (Rosette, Burullus, Damietta headland, Ras El-bar), siltation problems in estuaries and lake outlets, pollution problems, salt water intrusion, subsidence of land, and rising sea levels SLR due to global climate change, all of which are brought worse by human interventions, such as the interruption in sediment supply since the completion of the Aswan High Dam, (Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021; Masria et al., 2014). In the years prior to the building of the Aswan high dam, the Rosetta and Damietta promontories, and even the beaches of the intervening embayment, all received the 100–115 million m³/y of sediments that were released into the Mediterranean (El-Asmar et al., 2014). These sands provided ongoing replenishing to the coast in the face of long-shore currents, resulting in net coastal progression. However, the Mediterranean no longer received most of the sediment discharge as a result of the building of the Aswan High Dam in 1964, (El-Asmar et al., 2014). The Nile Delta coastline, which stretches from Alexandria City in the west to Port Said in the east, is lined with numerous coastal structures including groins, jetties at inlets, detached breakwaters, and seawalls. These were primarily intended to slow down

the erosion process in the delta zone, but because they completely or partially block sand passage, they caused up-drift accretion and severely eroded down-drift sides, (El Sayed and Khalifa, 2017). According to (El-Asmar et al., 2014), sand dunes existed in Abo-Qir Bay and Burullus headland, are considered the first natural barrier against erosion processes. The pace of erosion of the coastal region would worsen due to the anticipated changes in climate and sea level rise. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimations, which predict a 59 cm sea level rise and 2.5 mm/y land subsidence by 2100, one-fifth of the Nile Delta region will be severely susceptible to floods (IPCC, 2007; Ali and El-Magd, 2016). (El-Hattab, 2015) reported after vulnerability assessment that About 29.64% of the Nile Delta shoreline is having a very high vulnerability.

Geographic information systems (GIS) and remotely sensing (RS) have recently proven to be quite helpful in grasping the entire processes associated with coastal erosion, accretion, and consequences of protection structures, and based on that, necessary mitigation measures are proposed (El-Masry, 2022). Several authors have estimated shoreline alterations trend along the Nile Delta coast: (Balbaa et al., 2020; Dewidar and Frihy, 2010; Elsayed et al., 2005; Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021; Frihy et al., 1988; Frihy and Lawrence, 2004; Ghoneim et al., 2015; Sanhory et al., 2022; Torab and Azab., 2007). (Deabes, 2017) applied ArcGIS model builder to estimate shoreline change rates, particularly after building coastal structures along the Nile Delta coast. His results deduced that the erosion patterns between 1970- 2010 were centralized around delta promontories Rosetta, Damietta, and along Burullus headland with average rates of -60 m/y, -6 m/y, and -6 m/y respectively. The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS), a statistics tool, has demonstrated its approximate efficacy in studying coastal changes through much research on the Nile Delta coast, in addition to many locations around the world. (Niya et al., 2013) calculated the shoreline changes from 1990 to 2005 on Iran's coast. (Kaliraj et al., 2015) estimated accretion and erosion rates along the coast of Kanyakumari, South India. (Basheer Ahammed and Pandey, 2019) monitored shoreline changes along the Eastern Coast of India between 1973 to 2015. (Gümüs et al., 2021) investigated coastline change rates in Lake Beyşehir, Turkey from 1984 to 2018. (Quang et al., 2021) analyzed shoreline morphology along Quang Nam coastline, Vietnam.

Using remote sensing and the DSAS program, the current study sought to evaluate the shoreline's regressive displacement along the coastal region of the Nile Delta over a 37-year period to compare and verify the efficacy and protection role of various types of existing countermeasures.

2.2 Study area

The Nile Delta shoreline is situated in the south-eastern Mediterranean, north of Egypt, and stretches from Alexandria city in the west at 29° 23' 32.17" E and 30° 53' 23.68" N to Port Said in the east at 32° 34' 7.86" E and 31° 4' 27.55" N, **Figure 2.1**. It composes of beaches, coastal dunes, deserts, and lakes, ([Dewidar and Bayoumi, 2021](#)). The Nile Delta coast is recognized for its four major coastal lakes. These lakes are Mariut and Idku lake in west, Burullus lake in middle and Al-Manzalah Lake in east which represent approximately 25% of the wetland area covered by extensive fishing farms, ([Iskander, 2013](#)). Since the construction of the Aswan High Dam in 1964, the Nile Delta has seen a significant deficit in the quantity of accumulated sand, and therefore, excessive erosion rates have been observed ([Masria et al., 2014](#)). There are several coastal structures, including (jetties, breakwater, groins, seawall) erected in an attempt to slow the erosion processes in the study region. According to ([Frihy et al., 1988](#)), the most prevalent wind direction during the year is from NNW or NW. It is typically dominated by waves and currents where tides are almost tideless and semidiurnal with tidal range of 25- 30 cm. The prevailing current direction in most Burullus and Damietta region records is from west to east, except at spring season, when the current changes its direction due to wave direction and bottom terrain ([Frihy et al., 1996](#)). ([Iskander, 2013](#)) analyzed wave records at Abu-Qir Bay station between 1985 and 1990 and discovered that significant Wave height or Hs was 1.91 m with average peak wave period of 6.0 sec coming from the northwest. Between 1997 and 2010, waves in front of Damietta harbor had Hs of 1.02 m with an average peak wave period of 6.3 sec. Because of its low elevation, the Nile Delta is particularly vulnerable to sea level rise (SLR) and climate change. Digital elevation models (DEMs) have been analyzed by ([Hereher, 2010](#)), and the results show that 18.1% of the delta is below mean sea level, 12.7% has an elevation between 0 and 1 m, and

13.1% has an elevation between 1 and 2 m. Around 30 million people reside in this region, making it extremely populated (Abou Samra and Ali, 2021).

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 Data collection and shoreline extraction

The Nile Delta's shoreline positions were analyzed from satellite images captured over a 37-year period. In the current research, a set of digital images (Landsat TM, ETM+, and OLI) was collected at a spatial resolution of 30 m acquired via USGS Global Visualization website (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) between 1985 and 2022 intervals, **Table 2.1**. These data were projected to the Universal Transverse Mercator UTM, World Geodetic System WGS 84, zone 36. Also, they were radiometrically calibrated which combines sensor calibration, as well as atmospheric correction. To cover total study area in a single scene image, various Landsat images for all selected dates have been mosaicked by using ENVI v.5.3 software (**Appendix I, Fig A-1**). The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) technique was employed to extract shorelines and exported as a shapefile to ArcGIS v.10.7 software then converted from feature to polyline. The jagged edges (blocky shape) of all shorelines of the selected dates were smoothed, **Figure 2.2**, and merged as a single polyline in one length.

Figure 2.1 Location of the research area: a) Alexandria and Abo-Qir coast (zones 1, 2), b) Rosetta coast (zone 3), c) Burullus coast (zone 5), d) Damietta and Port Said coast (zones 7 and 8).

Table 2.1 Specifics about the satellite images utilized in this study:

Satellite data	Acquisition Date	Spatial Resolution (m)
Landsat5 TM	03/06/1985	30
	10/06/1985	
	29/03/1985	
Landsat5 TM	01/07/1995	30
	22/06/1995	
	21/07/1995	
Landsat5 TM	14/07/2000	30
	22/08/2000	
	29/08/2000	
Landsat7 ETM	18/06/2005	30
	03/05/2005	
	13/04/2005	

Landsat7 ETM	31/05/2010	30
	06/05/2010	
	27/04/2010	
Landsat8 OLI	08/06/2016	30
	18/05/2016	
	24/07/2016	
Landsat8 OLI	27/07/2022	30
	17/07/2022	
	04/04/2022	

2.3.2 Shoreline changes

To analysis shoreline changes, the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS), an ArcGIS extension, was utilized. Based on previous studies, such as (Abd-Elhamid et al., 2023), DSAS is considered an efficient and precise tool for identifying changes in the coastline. For each set of shorelines, a coastal length of about 324 km was covered by 4050 transects with an 80 m spacing. DSAS computed shoreline changes at each transect by using four different methods. To calculate the overall distance of the coastline displacement throughout the whole study period, Net Shoreline Movement NSM model is applied. Shoreline Change Envelope SCE model calculates the distance between the closest and farthest shoreline to the baseline. End Point Pates EPR and Linear Regression Rates LRR estimate shoreline change rates. The spatial changes in the study area's coastline were measured by using the LRR model for the three intermediate periods (1985- 2000, 2000- 2010, 2010- 2022), and for the overall long-term period from 1985 to 2022. **Figure 2.3** summarizes the total method of work followed in this research.

2.3.3 Shoreline prediction by using LRR

To validate LRR model in the prediction process, the predicted shoreline 2022 was generated using **Eq. (2.1)**, but with LRR calculated for historic changes between 1985 and 2016. Normalized root-mean square error, or NRMSE, was determined by using the values of the positional difference between the predicted shoreline for 2022 and the digitalized shoreline from the 2022 satellite image at each transect. Next, by determining the error distance of the NSM, the LRR model was used to predict future shorelines in 2030, 2050, and 2100.

$$P_F = LRR * (T_F - T_R) + P_R \quad \text{Eq. (2. 1)}$$

Where; P_F : future shoreline position, T_F : future date, T_R : recent date, P_R : recent shoreline position.

Figure 2.2 Shorelines extraction from 1985 to 2022: A) zone 1 represents Alexandria coast, B) Zone 2 represents Abo-Qir coast, C) zone 3 represents Rosetta promontory, D) Abo khashaba coast (zone 4), E) Burullus headland (zone 5), F) Gamase coast (zone 6), G) Damietta promontory (zone 7) and H) Port Said coast (zone 8).

Figure 2.3 Flowchart of the overall technique conducted in this research.

2.4. Results and discussion

The Nile Delta shoreline was divided into eight zones, all of which have relatively similar geomorphological changes patterns: (1) Al Hammam city to Abo-Qir port as explained in **Figure 2.4**, (2) Abu-Qir embayment, (3) Rosetta Promontory, (4) Abo-khashba embayment, (5) Burullus Headland, (6) Gamasa embayment, (7) Damietta Promontory, (8) Port Said coast. In this study, LRR was selected to represent shoreline changes in four periods: 1985- 2000, 2000- 2010, 2010- 2022, and 1985- 2022. As shown in **Table 2.2**, (Thieler and Hammar-Klose, 1999) divided accretion and erosion rates LRR into five categories: very high, high accretion, and moderate, high, very high erosion, with > 2.0

m/y, 1.0-2.0 m/y, 1.0 - -1.0 m/y, -1.0 - -2.0 m/y, and < -2.0 m/y change rate, respectively. The findings indicated that the erosion beaches existed along the Nile promontories, and an accretion pattern was present inside the embayment between the promontories. The coastal changes for all zones are presented in **Figures 2.5, 2.6** and the differences between LRR and EPR rates explained in (**Appendix I, Fig. A-2**). Also, **Figure 2.7** summarizes all structures implemented along the Nile Delta coast. The average rates of accretion and erosion along the research region are listed in **Table 2.3** for each zone.

Table 2.2 Ranking of erosion and accretion rates LRR

Rank	LRR rates (m/y)	Classification
1	> 2.0	Very high accretion
2	1.0 - 2.0	high accretion
3	1.0- -1.0	Moderate erosion
4	-1.0 - -2.0	high erosion
5	< -2.0	Very high erosion

2.4.1 Analysis of shoreline changes for different zones:

Zone 1 covers approximately 25 % of the coastline. It is the most western section extended from ELhammam city to Abo Qir port, constitutes of 1000 transects that span 80 kilometers of coastline. The results depicted that LRR had a positive value for all examined periods except the period of 2000- 2010 which had dominated erosion for around 842 transects with average value of -1.5 m/y and maximum value of -10.47 m/y (see Appendix **Fig A.3**). Erosion occurred along zone 1 over the (1985- 2000) and (2010- 2022) periods albeit on a small number of transects (287 and 221, respectively). The average accretion rates of three periods (1985- 2000, 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022) ranged from 1.23 m/year occurring in the 1985-2000 period to 3.73 m/year in the 2010- 2022 period. This zone suffered from moderate to high erosion rates, with average values ranging from -0.62 m/y happened in the 1985- 2000 period to -1.5 m/y in the 2000- 2010 period. In 2010- 2022, the mean erosion rate was -1.03 m/y. This region was shown to be likewise characterized as a very high accretion zone during the Long-term period of the research, with an average NSM value of 105.45 m and LRR rate of 2.85 m/y.

The protection structures executed in this zone contributed dramatically to controlling erosion processes. Some of Structures identified in this region: breakwaters for four ports (El-Dekhila, Abo Qir, Alexandria, Sidi-Kerair port) to provide safe shipping maneuvering, Nobaria Drain jetties to prevent siltation inside inlet, Al agami- emerged detached breakwaters to dissipate wave energy and helping in advance shoreline, submerged breakwater installed in 2006-2008 to eroded beach along El-Mandara area, groins constructed at El-Chatby, El-Asafra, El-Mandara, (El-Masry, 2022; Frihy et al., 2010; Frihy and El-Sayed, 2013). Nourishment activities were also accomplished periodically by adding desert sand to compensate sand losses at some affected beaches, (Darwish et al., 2017). **Figure 2.8(a)** shows the changes that occurred in the breakwater of Abu Qir port in year of 2021, which will certainly have an impact on the morphology of the shoreline. The results were also comparable to those calculated by (Abd-Elhamid et al., 2022; Elbagory et al., 2019; Soliman et al., 2014) for the same shoreline of the study region. El-Masry (2022) evaluated the effect of coastal structures on Agami–Sidi Kerair coast throughout period (1995–2020). According to the author's observations, the majority of the studied region underwent accretion, which is consistent with the findings of the current study. Darwish et al. (2017) examined shoreline changes along zone 1 from 1972 to 2015. The researcher divided this zone into two segments separating them by El Dekheila port. The analysis for the first segment revealed accretion rates with an average value of 1.4 m/y from 1984 to 2001 and 1.2 m/y between 2000 and 2015. When compared to the current study, the final findings demonstrated a high degree of convergence, with average accretion rates reaching 1.35 m/y, 1.45 m/y, and 1.29 m/y in intermediate periods 1985- 2000, 2000-2010, and 2010- 2022 respectively. Similarly, the second segment stretched from El-Dekheila to Abo Qir port, recorded an average accretion rate of 3.3 m/y between 2001 and 2015, while 4.2m/y during the 2000-2010 period and 5.3 m/y during the 2010-2022 period in the current study.

Zone 2 comprises about 6.94 % of the study area's coastline in the most western section, stretching from Abo Qir port to western part of Rosetta promontory. It began in the first period (1985- 2000) with accretion trend on more than 243 transects and erosion recorded on just 17 transects. Average and max accretion rates were approximately 3.33 m/y, 25.18 m/y respectively. The shoreline movement has seen an increase in erosion rates in

the two following intermediate periods 2000-2010, and 2010- 2022 where average values were -2.03 m/y, -2.48 m/y, respectively (see Appendix **Fig A.4**). A long-term estimation of coastline changes along zone 2 was also performed from 1985 to 2022. The overall number of transects that demonstrated accretion is 177, representing about 70% of the shoreline of the research region and covering a total length of 14.16 km. This is because the whole length of the coastline in this region is covered by a variety of natural and man-made protective systems. For example: Mohammed Ali seawall was constructed in 1830 in western side of Abo-Qir Bay and was maintained in 1981 and 2011 to protect low elevation land of El-Tahr city (1.5- 2.5 m below MSL) from inundation, (Ismail et al., 2012). Coastal dunes are considered as natural protection systems and represent about 60% of the length of the bay's middle portion. Jetties were structured during the year of 1986 to protect Idku inlet from shoaling. In addition, breakwaters of Idku port, located in the east portion of Abo-Qir Bay, were built to provide calm area in harbor. Several of the previous studies investigated and examined shoreline changes at the same zone, (Darwish et al., 2017; Smith and Abdel-Kader, 1988). Emam and Soliman (2020) quantified shoreline changes in the same region using Landsat images (1987–2017). The observations showed very high accretion rates on about 78% of transects.

Figure 2.4 Alexandria coast (zone 1)

Along Rosetta promontory, 330 transects were applied to cover 26.4 Km of shoreline length (Zone 3). It experienced significant changes in shoreline displacement between the different intermediate periods. In the 1985- 2000 period analysis, erosion was the dominant factor where average erosion rates reached -36.2 m/y with a max value of -99.18 m/y (see Appendix **Fig A.5**). There were a few parts that accreted with an average value of 7.94 m/y centralized in the eastern side of promontory. In the 2000- 2010 period, erosion continued to occur but with lower values due to the implementation of many coastal structures on both sides of the Rosetta estuary. Where it was revealed that the average shoreline retreat rate of this section was -10.21 m/y while the average advance rate was 4.55 m/y. It also found that the maximum erosion rate was about -30.7 m/y between 2010 and 2022. Erosion in this zone occurred by the action of waves and longshore currents, which carried sand away from the Rosetta tip of promontory, as well as sand supplementation from the Nile River has been halted due to the building of Aswan high dam. Eroded sand travelled east along the beach of Abu-Khashaba Bay and west along Abu Qir Bay's shoreline. More Structures were implemented in this region to mitigate erosion pattern, for example: Five Km seawall constructed between 1988 to 1991 at the western and eastern side of Rosetta promontory to stop erosion pattern at this promontory ([Abou Samra and Ali, 2021](#)). Additional structures were established at the down drift of eastern seawall in 2003. These included on five groins ranging in length from 400 to 500 m seaward, spaced 800 to 900 m apart. Subsequently, in 2005, another nine short groins (80- 150 m long) with 500-600 m spacing were erected at the downdrift of the western seawall, ([Dewidar and Frihy, 2007](#)).

The results indicated that the building of nine groins mitigated erosion processes significantly where rates of shoreline retreat decreased from -36.27 m/y in 1985- 2000 to -16.3 m/y and -2.81 m/y in two intermediated period 2000- 2010 and 2010-2022. In 2016, fish farms GFF were constructed and extended about 25 thousand feddan. GFF influenced the balance of the coastline. So, a new groin system was installed as shown in **Figure 2.8(b)**. Between the inlet and outlet of GFF, there were 8 groins spacing about 100 m, which were completed in 2018. The observations found that this region experienced dominated erosion reduced from -29.3 m/y in 2000- 2010 to -18.3 m/y in 2010- 2022. Another 8 groins at eastern side of outlet were also constructed by Egyptian

shore protection authority. The erosion problem still persists with an average value of -12.3 m/y during 2010- 2022 period, as shown in **Figure 2.9(a)**. (Sanhory et al., 2022), also investigated how recently built groins along GFF fish farm influenced shoreline alterations between 1984 and 2020. The results showed that installing an 8-groin system between the GFF's inlet and outlet reduced erosion rates from -36.22 m/y to -17 m/y. Furthermore, 8 groins at the eastward outlet of the GFF reduced erosion, but it still occurred, and there is a strong resemblance to the present research. For long term period from 1985- 2022, average shoreline movement NSM showed erosion value of -579.3 m and accretion value of 189.57 m. (Ghoneim et al., 2015) also reached the same conclusion that the shoreline of Rosetta promontory witnessed significant erosion, but rates reduced as a result of the protection installations that were implemented in this area. (Abou Samra and Ali, 2021) observed that the average erosion rates were -13.64 m/y from 1984 to 2018 period at the same region.

Zone 4's shoreline consists of 500 transects with an overall length of 40 km of shoreline. This zone witnessed a dominant and continuous erosion throughout the study periods. In the 1985- 2000 period, the erosion pattern significantly spread, with average rates reaching -2.97 m/y and peaking at -8.37 m/y (see Appendix **Fig A.6**). There were very few numbers of transects showing accretion with an average value of 4.24 m/y. The total number of transects between 2000- 2010 period that show erosion is 393, representing 78.6 % of the shoreline. In contrast, a minor accretion was recorded with a maximum rate of 14.87 m/y. From 2010 to 2022, erosion continued with higher rates where an average value reached -3.31 m/y and a maximum value was -9.35 m/y. The total number of transects showing accretion was only 64 transects representing 12.8 % of the shoreline. The long-term shoreline movement from 1985 to 2022 showed dominant erosion at 419 transects with an average value of -2.6 m/y. The reason for all these high erosion rates in this zone was the absence of protection structures. These findings were consistent with those of (Dewidar and Bayoumi, 2021), who stated that this area has completely suffered from erosion problems.

Zone 5 is the middle section extended along Baltim–Burullus headland, constitutes of 533 transects that span 42.5 kilometers of coastline. The result of shoreline changes rates

showed that an average erosion from 1985 to 2000 was about -4.52 m/y. The studied region possessed more erosion than accretion over this period, with 58% of the area eroded. In the 2000- 2010 period, a number of transects that show accretion was 301 transects with average accretion rates of 7.04 m/y (see Appendix **Fig A.7**). The average erosion was about -6.6 m/y, and a maximum value was -32.73 m. The shoreline changes rates of the period from 2010 to 2022 showed that average accretion and erosion rates were about 5.09 m/y and -5.67 m/y, respectively.

Burullus Headland is a changing location prone to a variety of natural and artificial variables that exacerbate the erosion process, necessitating the development of numerous efficient forms of coastal structures along the coast. Protection works along the Burullus coast began in 1947 with the erection of a 6 km seawall to safeguard the Burullus Lake inlet downdrift. A basalt rock wall was installed on the east side of Baltim village to protect it in 1975. The western jetty of Burullus Lake inlet, on the other hand, was erected between 1971 and 1972, while the eastern jetty was completed between 1982 and 1983. On the western side of this zone, despite the construction of three detached breakwaters, the erosion in this area was increasing, and this proves that these breakwaters were not sufficient to stop the erosion due to their number in relation to the length of the area to be protected. The deposition only occurred in the shadow area of these breakwaters. The rates of erosion were -6.08 m/y between 1985-2000 and continued to reach -6.83 m/y between 2000- 2010 and decreased to -3.15 m/y between 2010- 2022. Seventeen detached breakwaters have been installed in sea depths ranging from 3 to 4 meters along the Baltim coastal resort. Pre-construction stage of 17 detached breakwaters, this area experienced erosion processes from a period of 1985- 2000, where the average shoreline retreat was about -6 m/y. However, this erosion converted into local accretion as a result of forming tombolo and salient in the 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022 periods with average shoreline advance of about 13.5 m/y and 8.95 m/y, respectively.

The downdrift part of these detached breakwaters witnessed erosion due to the lack of sediment amount. Therefore, 9 groins were established in the eastern half of this zone in 2004 to safeguard the eroded shoreline west of the Kitchener drain, ([Elkafrawy et al., 2021](#)). Even after the construction of these groins, the result revealed continued erosion

with rates of -8.3 m/y and -5.86 m/y in 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022, respectively. In 2016, a group of groins was installed at the eastern side of Kitchener drain, as shown in **Figures 2.8(c), and 2.9(b)**, to control eroded beaches. And therefore, the results showed erosion rates reached -17.6 m/y on average in the 2000- 2010 period, then decreased to -7 m/y in the 2010- 2022 period. All of these results were consistent with the observations made by (Elkafrawy et al., 2021). (Emam and Soliman, 2020) reported that the overall trend of shoreline change rate from 1987 to 2017 in Burullus region was -2.95 m/y (EPR).

Zone 6's shoreline representing Gamasa embayment, consists of 440 transects totaling 35.2 km in length. This area was referred to as a very high accretion zone with average rates of 4.03 m/y between the 1985- 2022 period. The average accretion rates of the three periods (1985- 2000, 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022) ranged from 3.98 m/year in the 1985- 2000 period to 6.76 m/year in the 2010- 2022 period (see Appendix **Fig A.8**). Also, the average value of accretion rates in the 2000- 2010 period was 4.6 m/y. This zone also suffered from high to very high erosion rates, with average values ranging from -1.94 m/year happened in the 2000- 2010 period to -3.45 m/year in the 2010- 2022 period. The maximum erosion rates of three periods varied between -8.46 m/year in the 1985- 2000 period to -10.63 m/year in the 2010- 2022 period. This zone is considered a sediment sink receiving sediments from all eroded beaches along Burullus shoreline, (Dewidar and Bayoumi, 2021). Jetties at the Gamasa drain outlet and a group of groins on the eastern side of this drain are two recently added coastal structures in 2019 to the zone.

440 transects were utilized to study shoreline change rates along Damietta promontory (**Zone 7**), representing 10.8 % of the shoreline of the research region. Between 1985 and 2022 period, the findings indicated that this segment retreated at a rate of -16.76 m/y on average with a max value of -45.4 m/y (see Appendix **Fig A.9**). The mean accretion rate was 17.8 m/y. (Abou Samra and Ali, 2021) revealed that the average shoreline accretion and erosion rates were about 29.36 m/y and -20.61 m/y for the total period of 1984- 2018. (Abd-Elhamid et al., 2023) declared that the Damietta promontory experienced average rates of erosion ranging from -10 to -25 m/y between 1974 and 2022. At the beginning of this zone, there is Damietta Port, consisting of a western breakwater with a length of

1500 meters, and another eastern breakwater with a length of 800 meters that was extended in the year 2021. The results stated that the building of the two breakwaters enhanced accretion on the port's western side by 10.7 m/y and 3.4 m/y at intermediated periods 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022, respectively, and caused local erosion at downdrift of the port's eastern breakwater with average -5.64 m/y and -4.12 m/y between 2000- 2010 and between 2010- 2022 respectively. A comparable rate of erosion between -9.9 and -13.5 m/y east of the Damietta port was quoted by (El-Asmar et al., 2014) from 1984 to 2011. Four Y groins were constructed in 2019 as shown in **Figure 2.8(d)** to decrease this erosion. Rates of shoreline retreat decreased from -17.4 m/y between 1985- 2000 to -2.31 m/y in the 2010- 2022 period, **Figure 2.9(c)**. From 2000 to 2010 period, the mean rate of erosion was -5.13 m/y. It should be mentioned that Damietta port's eastern breakwater extension will prevent a significant quantity of sand from reaching this beach, and this is what will cause a problem, and affect these groins' functionality.

Because of Ras-Elbar resort, 8 detached breakwaters 200 m long with 200 m spacing were installed to control in the eroded beach. Dominated erosion in the period of 1985- 2000 was -2.38 m/y and converted into accretion with average rates of 3.8 m/y, 1.72 m/y in 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022, respectively. (Esmail et al., 2019) indicated that the shoreline advanced behind detached breakwaters with rates of 6.25 m/y and 4.25 m/y through the 1999- 2003 and 2003- 2015 periods. Our measured maximum rates of erosion at Damietta promontory were -39.7 m/y in 1985- 2000 then decreased to -6.77 m/y and -2.98 m/y in 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022. Two jetties were constructed at Damietta inlet to prevent siltation. Also, two seawalls were installed on the eastern and western sides of the inlet to stop erosion, however, erosion has begun at the eastern jetty with average rates of -27 m/y between 1985- 2000 then significantly decreased to -0.81 m/y and -0.224 m/y in 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022 respectively. The accretion pattern replaced the erosion pattern with the average of 0.4 m/y and 1.26 m/y during the period 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022, respectively. More monitoring of Damietta spit reflects the presence of reciprocal changes between erosion and accretion. The western part of spit, this area suffered from erosion with average rates of -25 m/y during the period of 1985- 2000. The erosion shifted distance and recorded average rates of -11.86 m/y in the 2000- 2010 period, then converted into an accretion pattern with average rates of 56 m/y from

2010 to 2022. In the middle part of spit, accretion was dominated in 1985- 2000 with rates of 61 m/y on average and, but erosion and accretion patterns were observed in the 2000- 2010 period with average rates of -18 m/y and 34.55 m/y respectively. From 2010 to 2022, the erosion pattern was dominated by values of -26.2 m/y on average. Accretion rates were observed with an average of 17.9m/y. On the eastern side of Damietta spit, the shoreline accreted with average values of 17.7 m/y during the period of 1985- 2022. These results concurred with those of (Aly et al., 2012) who mentioned that the eastern part of sand spit increased in width during the study period.

Zone 8 extends from the eastern side of Damietta spit to the end of port said city which represents about 44 km, covers 13.5 % of the shoreline. From 1985 to 2022, the shoreline advanced at a rate of 7.2 m/y on average. The average rate of coastline erosion was -13.2 m/y. The results of the shoreline trend analysis were congruent with those of (Abou Samra and Ali, 2021). This region displayed various variations in coastline displacement between the different intermediate periods, including accretion and erosion (see Appendix **Fig A.10**). Shoreline retreat with average rates was -8.1 m/y, -6.92 m/y, and -5.1 m/y for intermediate periods 1985- 2000, 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022 respectively. In the 1985- 2000 period, this section was prone to the influence of accretion with an average rate of 5.23 m/y. Accretion also occurred in the 2000- 2010, and 2010- 2022 periods with average rates of 6.52m/y, 7.78 m/y.

After Damietta spit, this area experienced dominant erosion through three intermediate periods with average rates of -11.57 m/y, -7.48 m/y, and -4.25 m/y respectively. The reason for that is the presence of Damietta spit trapped the eastward sediments, therefore the area behind it suffered from a strong erosion, and also because the presence of jetties at the entrance to the fish farms trapped the long-shore sediments transport, (Sarhan et al., 2022).

Between 1985 and 2000, the region extending to the entrance of the Suez Canal had erosion and accretion with average values of roughly -6.36 m/y and 4.18 m/y, respectively. Accretion rates in the 2000- 2010 and 2010- 2022 periods were 6.77 m/y and 3.53 m/y, respectively. Significant erosion rates were also observed in this region and

were about -5.82 m/y, and -7.39 m/y in the intermittent intervals 2000- 2010 and 2010-2022, respectively. As consequently, many protective structures have been established to lessen the erosion that already exists. One such measure is a group of groins installed in 2016, **Figure 2.8(e)** at the western side of El-Gamil's first inlet of El-Manzala Lake which increased accretion rates from 7.9 m/y in 2000- 2010 to 11.05 m/y in 2010- 2022. This was consistent with the findings of (Sarhan et al., 2022), who estimated accretion rates due to the implementation of these groins to be 7 m/y between 2002 to 2020. The shoreline was significantly built thanks to the several detached breakwaters installed on the western side of El-Gamil's second entrance, with accretion rates of 11.65 m/y and 6.44 m/y from 2000 to 2010 and 2010 to 2022, respectively. Jetties at El-Gamil inlets were completed recently as shown in **Figure 2.8(e)**. The results for the jetties' western side at El-Gamil second inlet showed a transition from erosion with an average value of -2.32 m/y in the period of 1985- 2000 to an accretion pattern with an average value of 14.7 m/y in the period of 2010- 2022, **Figure 2.9(d)**. Rates of erosion decreased from -1.63 m/y in 2000- 2010 to -0.64 m/y in 2010- 2022 as a result of the existence of 14 groins with 175 m spacing at the western side of Suez-canal. (Dewidar and Frihy, 2010) observed erosion rates downdrift of Damietta spit in long-term period 1972- 2007 between -5.1 m/y to -10.16 m/y. Additionally, they mentioned that an accretion pattern occurred at the western of Suez-canal with an average value of 8 m/y. After the Suez-canal entrance, an erosion pattern was observed with average values of -10.82 m/y, -18.2 m/y, and -29.3 m/y at intermediate periods, respectively.

Table 2.3 Shoreline change rates LRR in different periods.

	Short-term periods						Long-term period	
	1985-2000		2000-2010		2010-2022		1985-2022	
	Mean Erosion (m/y)	Mean Accretion (m/y)						
Zone 1	-0.62	1.23	-1.5	3.35	-1.03	3.73	-0.4	2.85
Zone 2	-0.46	3.33	-2.03	5.35	-2.48	4.14	-0.78	5.01
Zone 3	-36.2	7.94	-10.2	4.55	-7.55	2.33	-15.7	5.12
Zone 4	-2.97	4.24	-2.48	4.55	-3.31	3.6	-2.56	4.82
Zone 5	-4.52	4.68	-6.57	7.04	-5.67	5.09	-3.25	4.25
Zone 6	-2.27	3.98	-1.94	4.7	-3.45	6.76	-1.2	4.03
Zone 7	-22.8	27.13	-17.1	25.06	-21.7	24.27	-16.8	17.81
Zone 8	-8.1	5.23	-6.92	6.52	-5.1	7.78	-13.2	7.2

Figure 2.5 Rates of Erosion and accretion LRR along the Nile delta coast in a)1985-2000, b) 2000-2010, C) 2010-2022

Figure 2.6 Shoreline changes “LRR” for long term period 1985-2022 at different locations: a) Alexandria and Abo-Qir coast, b) Rosetta promontory, c) Abo khashabe coast, c) Burullus headland, e) Gamase embayment, f) Damietta promontory, g) Port Said coast.

Figure 2.7 Summary of protection structures along Nile delta coast: a) Rosetta promontory, b) Burullus headland, c) Damietta promontory, d) Port Said coast around El-Gamil inlets.

Figure 2.8 Recent development along the study area.

Figure 2.9 Shoreline changes between 2016-2022 at the recently executed structures: a) At the groins system east of Rosetta promontory, b) At the groins system east of Kitchner drain, c) At the y- groins east of Damietta harbor, d) At the detached breakwater west of the second El Gamil inlet.

2.4.2 Future shoreline changes in 2030, 2050 and in 2100

To verify the LRR model, the positional difference between the predicted and extracted shorelines in 2022 was compared using NSM at each transect, **Figure 2.10**. The findings of this comparison resulted in a small NRMSE value of 0.0195, demonstrating that the LRR model is a good predictor of future locations of the study region's coastline. **Figure 2.11** depicts the analysis and identification of future shoreline alterations predicted for 2030, 2050, and 2100 at specified locations. The results revealed that zone 1 will advance 128.14 m on average in 2030, then increase to 200.3 m in 2050, and 402.8 m in 2100 years. Furthermore, it will erode by -503.5 m, -550.15 m, and 714.4 m in 2030, 2050, and 2100, respectively. This necessitates the construction of protective structures to mitigate coastline erosion and protect this region. The predicted shoreline positions at zone 2 show accretion changing from 508.15 m in the year 2030 to 1266.48 m for the year 2100, respectively. While it shows erosion on average of -85.26 m, -156.1 m, and -355.6 m for the years 2030, 2050, and 2100 respectively. Shoreline position at zone 3, **Figure 2.11(a)**, will advance with about 219.73 m, 412.22 m, and 862.16 m, but it will erode with about -204.59 m, -360.71 m, and -794.139 m for the years 2030, 2050, and 2100 respectively.

The coastline position at zone 4 was estimated to retreat about -66.12 m, -119.5 m, and -286.4 m and to advance by approximately 69.5 m, 104.42 m, and 180.26 m for years 2030, 2050, and 2100 respectively. It was also noticeable that zone 5, **Figure 2.11(b)**, will continue in erosion, and the coastline will retreat with calculated NSM values of -

183.88m, -213.55m, and -316.89 m for years 2030, 2050, and 2100 respectively. Zone 6 is anticipated to advance with an average shoreline distance of 134.35 m by 2030, 157.7 m by 2050, and 223.97 m by 2100. The shoreline of Zone 7 will erode by average distances of -446.73 m in 2030, -715.98 m in 2050, and -1520.36 m in 2100. As shown in **Figure 2.11(c)**, zone 7 will experience severe erosion, with large sections of the beach disappearing completely by 2100. Zone 8 will need urgent protection structures because it will suffer from severe erosion rates. It will lose land by -702 m in 2030, by about -1038.83 m in 2050, and -1930.17 m in 2100.

Figure 2.10 NSM distance between digitalized and predicted shoreline in 2022 at each transect.

Figure 2.11 Future shoreline changes from 1985 -2100: a) Rosetta promontory, b) Burullus headland, C) Damietta promontory

2.5 Conclusion

Erosion and accretion rates were determined over a 324-kilometer stretch of the Nile Delta coast for a 37-year period. DSAS software was used as an analyzing method by

casting 4050 transects perpendicular to the digitalized shorelines. The studied region witnessed erosion in 2180 transects and accretion in 1870 transects between 1985 to 2022. Three areas experienced very high erosion rates with a maximum value: Rosetta promontory (-37.2 m/y) and Damietta Promontory (-45.4 m/y), as well as Burullus headland (-11.07 m/y). These changes were mostly due to the interruption of the sediment supply via the Aswan High Dam, climate changes, and the negative impacts of coastal protection installations. The locations with maximum values of accretion rates were Alexandria coast (25.8 m/y) and Gamasa embayment (37.2 m/y), as well as some portions of Port-said coast (36.9 m/y), centered around El-Gamil inlets throughout long-term period. This study evaluated the effect of newly installed coastline protection measures on the erosion processes in this region. On the Rosetta promontory's eastern side, a new groin protection system was constructed in 2016. But the impact of these groins on the erosion process was not great. Between the inlet and outlet of GFF, 8 groins were able to lower erosion rates from -29.3 m/y in 2000- 2010 to -18.3 m/y in 2010-2022. Despite the erection of additional 8 groins on the eastern side of the outlet, erosion continues to be an issue, with an average rate of -12.3 m/y between 2010 and 2022. On the eastern side of Kitchener Drain, a group of groins was also installed in the same year, and it was noted that erosion rates which peaked at -17.6 m/y on average from 2000 to 2010, decreased by 60.2% in the period from 2010 to 2022. In 2019, a number of Y-groin was executed on the eastern side of Damietta Port to reduce the ongoing erosion in this area. These groins achieved their function and reduced erosion significantly by -2.31 m/y on average between 2010 to 2022. Five groins were erected in 2016 near the western edge of the first El-Gamil inlet, increasing accretion rates from 7.9 m/y in the years 2000–2010 to 11.05 m/y in the years 2010–2022. The estimated shoreline positions for 2030, 2050, and 2100 demonstrate that the past change patterns will be anticipated continuing at nearly similar rates in the future. If the situation does not improve and the Egyptian authorities do not step in and undertake urgent measures, zones 1, 2, and 6 will continue to accrete while zones 3, 4, 5, 7, and 8 will erode at significant rates in the future. These future estimations highlighted the areas of the shoreline that will be lost significantly due to erosion; hence, urgent necessary management solutions will be required.

To guarantee the enduring viability of coastal ecosystems in the Nile Delta, forthcoming research on shoreline alterations must transcend conventional, structure-centric treatments and adopt integrated, nature-based methodologies. Sustainable management necessitates the integration of long-term monitoring systems, climate-resilient models, and adaptive methods that include both natural processes—such as sediment movement, sea-level rise, and land subsidence—and anthropogenic factors. Coastal resilience may be increased while reducing ecological disturbance by supporting ecosystem-based solutions, such as soft engineering and wetland restoration. Moreover, combining shoreline dynamics with socioeconomic vulnerability evaluations is vital to safeguard at-risk communities and infrastructure. A more comprehensive and sustainable framework for coastal management in the Nile Delta will be further supported by involving local stakeholders and building institutional capacity via training, data exchange, and participatory planning.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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Chapter (3)

Evaluation of coastal risks to Sea level rise: Case Study of Nile Delta Coast

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ABSTRACT

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Evaluation of coastal risks to Sea level rise: Case Study of Nile Delta Coast

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Abstract

One of the most effective strategies for coastal management in Egypt is analyzing how the Nile Delta shoreline is adapted for climate change and rising sea levels and identifying the most vulnerable and hotspot sites. Thirteen geological, physical, and socioeconomic factors were identified and assessed to ascertain the level of vulnerability of the Egyptian Delta coast. The rank for each parameter was integrated using two different techniques (Gornitz's method and Analytical hierarchy process, AHP) to estimate the coastal vulnerability index, CVI. Based on the CVI values from both models, the Nile Delta shoreline is categorized into five vulnerability classes: very high, high, moderate, low, and very low, using percentage techniques. Both models produced excellent results. CVI calculations using Gornitz's method identified five vulnerable coastal zones: i) the western part of Abu-Qir Bay, ii) Rosetta Headland, iii) Abo-Khashba Bay, iv) Damietta Headland, and v) some scattered sectors along the Port Said coast. The AHP model results indicate significant vulnerability, with very high vulnerability (4.499–3.8) and high vulnerability (3.8–3.593) primarily on the western sector of Alexandria, Abu-Qir Bay, most of Abo-Khashba Bay, the eastern side of Damietta, and some sectors at the Port Said coast. Moderate (3.598–3.398), low (3.398–3.17), and very low (3.17–2.016) vulnerability areas are in specific regions such as the eastern side of Alexandria, Burullus Headland, and Gamasa Bay. The study reveals that the coast has witnessed high vulnerability to geomorphology, elevation, coastal slope, bathymetry, significant wave height, lack of artificial structures and land use; moderate

vulnerability to shoreline change, sea level change, and land subsidence; low vulnerability to tidal range, distance to urban, and wave direction. The research showed success at assessing the level of coastal threat with the potential for implementation of countermeasures by providing decision-makers with data.

Keywords: Climate change, Sea level rise SLR, Coastal vulnerability index CVI, AHP method, ArcGIS

3.1 Introduction

Coastal areas in Egypt are under pressure and threat due to natural impacts, such as wave, current, tide, storm surges, and sediment supply as well as human interventions in the form of construction of seawalls, breakwaters, groins, and jetties as well as tourism development (ElKotby et al., 2023). Furthermore, climate change (CC) effects are also threatening these areas, because of their high human densities, diversified ecosystems, ongoing urbanization, and intense industrial activities (Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021, Hemida et al., 2023). One of the most certain and alarming impacts of CC is sea-level rise (SLR), which will intensify the pressure on many coastal regions (Ehsan et al., 2019). Human activities have caused a sharp increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations in the atmosphere globally, which has led to significant losses of ice mass and the trapping of heat emitted from land in the atmosphere and ocean (IPCC, 2007). According to the very high GHG emissions scenario, the global surface temperature averaged by 2100 is extremely likely to be higher by 3.3°C to 5.7°C (IPCC, 2021). Between 1901 and 2018, the global mean sea level climbed by 0.20 m (IPCC, 2021). Hemeda (2021) reported that sea level is consistently increasing at a pace of 1.8 and 4.9 mm/year with an average of 3 mm/year on the Egyptian coast. According to the recent IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), the very high GHG emissions scenario is anticipated to cause a 0.63- 1.01 m rise in the global mean sea level by 2100 (SSP5-8.5). Even if GHG emissions were controlled shortly, deglaciation and thermal expansion would keep increasing the sea level for decades (Raey and Askary, 2020).

Coastal erosion, inundation, changes in both intensity and occurrences of storm surges, and saltwater intrusion (Basheer Ahammed and Pandey, 2019; Elsharkawy et al., 2009) are serious environmental problems related to SLR and affecting the important coastal assets, especially in low-lying and densely inhabited places (Yan et al., 2016). Several research efforts have probed into the potential effects of increasing sea levels on the

most vulnerable coastal regions, such as Egypt (Eldeberky, 2011; Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021; Refaat and Eldeberky, 2016), Malaysia (Ehsan et al., 2019; Lee Lee et al., 2023), Vietnam (Erban et al., 2014; Nguyen and Woodroffe, 2016; Thanh, 2022), China (Wang et al., 2018; Yan et al., 2016), and India (Dhiman et al., 2019; Mahapatra et al., 2015). The ramifications of SLR for 84 coastal developing countries were underlined by Dasgupta et al. (2009). Egypt was rated as level 2 on a scale of 1-10 (high to low range), with the most severe impacts from a 1-m SLR. The coastal stretch of the Nile Delta was particularly susceptible to the effect of CC and SLR, due to its low-lying land zones (El-Hattab, 2015).

Several researchers have declared various definitions of vulnerability such as (Bevacqua et al., 2018; Gornitz, 1991; Kunte et al., 2014; Oloyede et al., 2022; Silva et al., 2017). Coastal vulnerability is a spatial approach that draws attention to the people and locations that are exposed to coastal threats. In the literature, there are a number of methods to assess coastal vulnerability linked to different types of dangers (Gallina et al., 2016; Noor and Abdul Maulud, 2022; Simac et al., 2023). The coastal vulnerability index (CVI) established by Gornitz, (1991) remains the most widely used tool for quantifying and comparing the relative vulnerability of different coastline regions employing the equal weights method (Kunte et al., 2014). The analytical hierarchy process (AHP) can be also applied to assess the susceptibility of coastal areas utilizing the uneven weights technique (Saaty, 1977). Many papers, including (Akash et al., 2023; Arda et al., 2024; Mahapatra et al., 2015; Thirumurthy et al., 2022), have concurred that the AHP method improves upon traditional methods by allowing users to set weights to model parameters, making coastal area vulnerability inquiry more reliable and valuable. CVI, as an integrated index, is an analytical technique based on the composition of physical, geological, social, and economic variables that may be used to combine a variety of quantitative and qualitative data from many sources. Some authors (Emam et al., 2019; Gornitz, 1991; Hereher, 2013; Thieler and Hammar-Klose, 1999; Widura and Mardiatno, 2022) incorporated six physical, and geological variables (geomorphology, coastal slope, shoreline displacement (erosion/ accretion), tidal ranges, sea level rise, and wave heights) to calculate the CVI while others (e.g. Hossain et al., 2022) incorporated 10 variables, adding to the aforementioned, elevation, bathymetry, coastal land use, and storm surge height. Arun Kumar and Kunte (2012) developed a CVI using eight parameters to determine the most vulnerable locations.

Bagdanavičiute et al. (2015) introduced several new variables into the CVI method, namely: beach width/height, the underwater slope's inclination and presence of sand bars, and beach sediment properties. The role of artificial protection structures in CVI was carefully discussed by (Sekovski et al., 2020; Turriza et al., 2024). Also, the presence of land use within the parameters and linking it to the CVI is of great importance and was reported by (Handiani et al., 2022; Mani Murali et al., 2018; Oloyede et al., 2022).

Moreover, several of the previous studies (e.g., Hzami et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2015; Kunte et al., 2014; Mani Murali et al., 2018; Mavromatidi et al., 2018; Murali et al., 2013; Oloyede et al., 2022) depend on determination coastal vulnerability by the interaction between physical, geological, and social-economic parameters. Boruff et al. (2005) evaluated coastal vulnerability based on 39 socio-economic parameters in addition to physical parameters for the US coastal countries. El-Hattab (2015) assessed the vulnerability of the Nile Delta coastline, Egypt to projected SLR by analyzing eight physical and geological parameters with two socio-economic parameters.

The study aims to apply the CVI models for evaluating the effects of SLR on the Nile Delta coast and identify the most hazardous areas. This information is intended to help decision-makers implement effective coastal management strategies for shielding future generations from the impacts of CC. Unlike the traditional methods described in previous research, this study introduces an advanced and enhanced approach called the AHP model for assessing vulnerability in the Nile Delta, Egypt. This approach is designed to be a straightforward evaluation method for coastal areas, requiring neither extensive computer capabilities nor complex data. The coastal system's vulnerability to SLR was mapped and ranked based on 13 parameters including geological, physical, and socioeconomic elements. Finally, a comparative study was also carried out between the AHP and the traditional method, resulting in the creation of a CVI map for each approach to identify the most critical vulnerable coastal regions.

3.2 Study area

Nile Delta is one of the major river deltas globally and is situated in North Egypt (**Figure 3.1**). It extends from Port Said in the east at 32.57°E and 31.07°N to Alexandria in the west at 29.39°E and 30.89°N. Before the Aswan High Dam was constructed, it was formed during flood seasons using sediment carried up the river. It is distinguished

by three huge brackish lakes: Maruit, Burullus, and Manzala which are encircled by massive fishing farms (Iskander, 2013). Natural barriers also exist between Port Said and Alexandria in the form of coastal ridges, elevated coastal strips on the western sector of Alexandria, coastal dunes along Edku Bay, and Burullus Headland, (ElKotby et al.,2023). These barriers help to protect interior areas, especially existing low-lying lands, from flooding and storm surges. However, the majority of coastal dunes along the coast were destroyed or eliminated when the Ras El-Bar resort and vacation amenities were being established (El Sayed Frihy et al., 2010).

Nile Delta covers only 2.3% of Egypt's land area, but it is populated by almost 41% of the country's citizens (Erban et al., 2014; Hereher, 2010). The bulk of these people resides in and around the important commercial and industrial centers of Alexandria, Rosetta, Damietta, and Port Said (Eldeberky, 2011). Like other deltas around the world, the Nile Delta is prone to abrupt changes in its shorelines, involving issues with erosion (Rosette, Burullus, Damietta Headland, Ras El-bar), siltation in estuaries and lake outlets, pollution, saltwater intrusion, land subsidence, and SLR due to global CC (Elshinnawy and Almaliki; 2021; Masria et al., 2014). The Nile Delta has a long coastline of 324 kilometers, but it is vulnerable to severe climate conditions like that storm surges that attacked Alexandria on a regular basis with wave heights of more than 4 meters, causing a 1-meter rise in sea level in 2003, 2010, and 2017, (Mohamed, 2020). Unfortunately, despite the importance of the Nile Delta region economically, there is a severe lack of available information and data related to the issue of CC and SLR.

The hottest months for Nile Delta's weather are July and August when the highest average temperature is 34 °C. Temperatures in the winter vary from 9 °C at night to 19 °C during the daylight hours (Kassem et al., 2019). Due to colder temperatures and some rain, the Nile Delta region is quite fairly humid in the winter. The delta area receives only 100-200 millimeters of rain per year on average, with a significant portion of this precipitation falling during the winter (Abdel-Shafy et al., 2010).

Figure 3.1: Location of study area

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 Definition parameters and data sources

A variety of parameters were introduced to assess the degree of risk for the Nile River Delta. In this research, eleven geological and physical parameters, namely Geomorphology, Coastal elevation, Coastal slope, Bathymetry, Shoreline change, Significant wave height, Mean tidal range, Sea level change, Artificial structures, Land subsidence and Wave direction and two socio-economic parameters, namely Distance to urban, Land use land cover (LULC) were incorporated for constructing the CVI model, (Figure 3.2). Table 3.1 summarizes the sources of data as well as the time range of the same data investigated for assessing vulnerability.

Table 3.1: Details of the sources and time scale of data sets considered.

Parameters	Data source	Time scale	Resolution
Geomorphology	(Hereher, 2015), (MODIS) satellite	2012	250m
Elevation	STRM model	2014	30m
Coastal slope	STRM model, Raster calculator in ArcGIS	2014	30m
Bathymetry	Field data by Coastal Research Institute (CoRI)+ Gebco website https://download.gebco.net/	Gebco 2022	(15 arc seconds)
Shoreline change	Landsat TM, ETM, Oli USGS website https://www.usgs.gov + DSAS tool	1985-2022	30m
Sea level change	(Makary et al., 2007; El Sayed Frihy et al., 2010; Hemed, 2021) + interpolation (IDW), ArcGIS		-
Significant wave height	Wave data by Coastal Research Institute (CoRI)	Rosetta 2005 Burullus 2015 Port Said 2010	-
Tidal range	Wxtide 32 program, Masria et al., 2021 and ElKotby et al.,2023	2022	-
Land subsidence	(El Sayed Frihy et al., 2010) + interpolation (IDW), ArcGIS	-	-
Artificial structures	Google Earth Pro.	2022	30m
Wave direction	Wave data by Coastal Research Institute (CoRI) Autocad 2020+ ArcGIS	Rosetta 2005 Burullus 2015	-

		Port Said 2010	
Distance to urban	Google Earth Pro.	2022	30m
LULC	Landsat OLI and ArcGIS	2022	30m

3.3.2 Mapping Parameters and Data

3.3.2.1 Remote Sensing parameters and data

Remote sensing (RS) and geographic information system (GIS) techniques have been employed in the current analysis due to their potential to handle spatial data such as shoreline delineation, LULC, Bathymetry and elevation, more efficiently and expeditiously (Isha and Adib, 2020). The following parameters used RS and GIS techniques are briefly discussed:

Elevation and Coastal slope

To produce maps of coastal elevation and coastal slope, the STRM (Shuttle Topography Radar Model) with 30m-spatial resolution was acquired from the <https://www.usgs.gov> website file of the study area. The slope map is created for the study area using ArcGIS software. Most reports present coastal slope in percentages, which is the percentage of latitude difference to the horizontal distance between two locations perpendicular to the coastline (Hereher et al., 2020; Oloyede et al., 2022). The Raster calculator tool is employed under the "Spatial Analyst" toolbar, to create the slopes of each cell and then create a slope classification map. According to Hasan et al. (2015), CC is anticipated to cause coastal areas in Egypt to be at risk of SLR from 0.5 and 1.0 m by the end of the 21st century. Thus, it is essential to analyze the elevation map to pinpoint submergence zones under various scenarios of SLR. This analysis is conducted as follows: First, the STRM model was accurately processed by filling in all depressions and gaps, ensuring that they were allocated the appropriate elevations from their adjacent areas. A mathematical operation is conducted on the filled STRM using the Raster calculator tool to produce a binary inundation map. Finally, to evaluate the extent of the flooding, the spatial distribution of submerged areas is overlaid on satellite images.

Bathymetry

Bathymetry data was obtained through the available website (<https://download.gebco.net/>) of 15 Arc seconds, in addition to field data by Coastal Research Institute (CoRI) for vital areas such as Rosetta promontory, Burullus Headland, New Mansoura region, and Damietta promontory. A merger was made

between the data, and then the missing data were interpolated using Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) technique and converted to a shape file into ArcGIS.

Shoreline change

Shoreline alterations were estimated using Landsat images TM, ETM, OLI, and the Digital Shoreline Change Analysis (DSAS) tool over a span of 37 years. Geometric, atmospheric correction and radiometric calibration are the procedures used in the pre-processing of the chosen satellite images, utilizing ENVI 5.3 software. These images are analyzed to extract shorelines through Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) classification techniques, followed by the application of the Linear Regression Rate (LRR) method to track historical changes in shorelines from 1985 to 2022.

Artificial coastal structures

On the other hand, the coastal structures that were implemented along the study area were monitored by using Google Earth pro.. Symbology on ArcGIS software was done for each type of these installations to get artificial structures map.

Distance to urban

The distance to the urban parameter was estimated through the Google Earth pro. by tracking the normal distance between urban areas and the shoreline, which was exported as a KML layer and then converted into a shape file that can be dealt with it in the ArcGIS.

LULC

This paper utilizes the supervised classification of Landsat images OLI (2022) to generate a LULC map. Six Landsat images were mosaiced together to cover the whole region. More than 750 polygons were used as training regions during this process, which were saved as a signature file. Finally, the Maximum likelihood method was employed by appending the signature file to create a LULC map ([Appendix II, Table B-1](#)).

3.3.2.2 Other parameters and data

The geological and physical data including geomorphological, sea level change, significant wave height, tidal range, Land subsidence, wave direction, of the proposed

model, are retrieved from two primary sources depending on field data and literature research for the study area.

Geomorphology

Our analysis of the geomorphological data was based on the findings of the study that [Hereher \(2015\)](#) provided. He used a single picture from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) satellite in 2012 to derive the geomorphology features.

Significant wave height

Significant wave height or H_s represents an average of one-third of the highest waves in a record. H_s is considered as an indicator for wave energy and as a measure of coastal vulnerability, which is responsible for coastal sediment transport ([Hossain et al., 2022](#); [Kunte et al., 2014](#); [Pramanik et al., 2016](#)). The following equation estimates the relationship between wave height and wave energy:

$$E = \frac{\gamma H^2}{8} \quad \dots\dots (3.1)$$

Where; γ is the specific gravity of water, E is wave energy, and H is wave height.

The wave height data for Rosetta promontory, Burullus, and Damietta acquired from Coastal Research Institute (CoRI) give H_s of 1.65, 0.87, and 1.24 m, respectively ([Appendix II, Figs B-2, B-3](#)).

Tidal range

Tide is sea level fluctuations resulting from the gravitational influence of the Moon and Sun on the Earth as well as the Earth's rotation ([Murali et al., 2013](#)). According to **Equation (3.2)**, the tidal range represents the height difference between high-high and low-low tide:

$$\text{Tidal range} = \text{HHWL} - \text{LLWL} \quad \dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where, HHWL is high high-water level, LLWL is low low-water level.

The average tidal range in the study area varies from 0.20 m to 0.30 m based on the WX-tide program used by ([Arun Kumar, and Kunte, 2012](#); [Mani Murali et al., 2018](#)) and literature reviews of ([ElKotby et al., 2023](#); [ElKotby et al., 2024](#); [Masria et al., 2021](#)).

Sea level change

While tides generate daily fluctuations in sea level, long-term changes in sea level are observed as well. Such variations are the result of significant consequences related to CC and thermal expansion. Tidal gauge data is used as a source of sea level change information (Islam et al., 2015). Data based on (Makary et al., 2007; El Sayed Frihy et al., 2010; Hemeda, 2021) observations in locations such as Alexandria, Abu-Qir Bay, Rosetta, Burullus, and Damietta are utilized (See Appendix II, Fig. B-1). From available data, it is observed that sea level change in Alexandria, Abu-Qir Bay, Rosetta, Burullus, Damietta, and Port Said is at rates of 1.8, 3.4, 4.9, 3.0, 2.9, and 2.8 mm/year, respectively.

Land subsidence

(El Sayed Frihy et al., 2010; Refaat and Eldeberky, 2016) observed that subsidence rates at Alexandria, Abu-Qir, Rosetta, Burullus, Damietta, and Port Said were 0, 0.25, 4.0, 1.5, 1.5, and 3.98 mm/y, respectively. Mohamed (2020) revealed that because of contemporary neotectonics falling and earthquakes, Alexandria is considered stable or experiencing minor subsidence. Furthermore, the northern Nile delta's subsidence rate increases dramatically eastward because of the natural consolidation and dewatering of the dense Holocene deltaic sediments, particularly in the Port Said area.

Wave direction

In this study, the Python programming language widely used in engineering sciences was employed to create a wave rose by applying the code of WindroseAxes (Appendix II, Fig. B-4). WindroseAxes is a class in the matplotlib library for Python that allows you to create wind rose plots. The wave angle is defined as the angle between the direction of the wave, which is assumed to be northwest and the perpendicular to the shoreline. This angle was determined and measured by drawing the direction of the wave and the perpendicular line on the shoreline in the AutoCAD program.

3.3.3 CVI calculation method

3.3.3.1 Gornitz's method

The research area's shoreline is separated into segments by using data management tool in ArcGIS software according to the 13 factors impacting coastal vulnerability.

Depending on the ranking scheme shown in **Table 3.2**, a rank from one to five is given to each segment denoting very low, low, moderate, high, and very high vulnerability, respectively. The ranks selected for the five classes are the same already used in previous studies. According to the methodology, each variable is imported into ArcGIS as a "Shape File," and the vulnerability rankings for each of the 13 factors are recorded in the attribute table of each coastal segment. All shape files are combined using the "Spatial Join" option in Arc Map Software's "Overlay" module of the "Arc Tools" menu. In the current study, the entire coast was shown as a line feature in the ArcGIS. The final output map includes the properties of all investigated variables separating the whole coast into 10014 segments, each with its ID number. Then, the CVI is calculated at each segment using **Equation (3.3)**, (Gornitz, 1991). In this approach, which is most commonly used in previous studies, the weight or importance degree of each parameter was considered equal and equal to 1.

$$CVI = \sqrt{\frac{R1 * R2 * \dots * Rn}{n}} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where, R: vulnerability rank for each parameter, n: number of parameters

Figure 3.2: Methodological framework for vulnerability assessment.

Table 3.2: Vulnerability rank assigned to the different CVI parameters investigated.

Parameters	Ranks assigned of CVI's parameters					REFERENCES
	Very low (1)	Low (2)	Moderate (3)	High (4)	Very high (5)	
Geomorphology	Rocky and cliffy coast,	Coastal plain and dune with vegetation	Low cliffs	Lagoon, estuary creeks	Sandy beaches, deltas, dunes system	Silva et al. (2017)
Coastal slope %	> 1.9	1.9- 1.3	1.3- 0.9	0.9- 0.6	< 0.6	Koroglu et al. (2019)
Coastal elevation (m)	> 6 m	> 4- 6m	> 2- 4m	> 1- 2 m	< 1 m	Oloyede et al. (2022)
Bathymetry (m)	< -4	-3 to -4	-2 to -3	-1 to -2	> -1	Hoque et al. (2019)
Shoreline change m/y	> 2.0	1.0- 2.0	-1.0 - 1.0	-1.0 - -2.0	< - 2.0	Torresan et al. (2020)
Significant wave height (m)	< 0.55	0.55–0.85	0.85–1.05	1.05–1.25	> 1.25	Thieler and Hammar-Klose (1999)
Tidal range (m)	< 1 Microtidal	1: 2 Micro-tidal	2: 4 Meso-tidal	4:< 6 Meso-tidal	> 6 Macro-tidal	Mahapatra et al. (2015)
sea level change mm/y	< 1.8	1.8- 2.5	2-5- 3.0	3.0- 3.4	> 3.4	Hereher (2015)
Land subsidence (mm/y)	< 1	1	2	2- 3	> 3	El-Hattab (2015)
Artificial structure	Sea wall	-	Groins, jetty, detached breakwaters	-	No protection	Mohamed (2020)
Wave direction	10- 45°	-	0- 10°	-	0	Rangel-Buitrago and Anfuso (2015)
Distance to urban (m)	> 300	150- 300	100- 150	50- 100	< 50	Tahri et al. (2017)
Land use land cover LULC	Bare areas	-	-	Agriculture	Urban, wetland, fish farms	(Satta et al., 2016; and Rajasree and Deo, 2020)

3.3.3.2 Analytical hierarchy process ‘AHP method’

Studies on coastal vulnerability such as (Hossain et al., 2022; Nguyen and Woodroffe, 2016; Sekovski et al., 2020) are progressively using AHP, which was the multi-criteria decision-making method initially created by Saaty (1977, 1980). It gives an exhaustive understanding of challenging topics by partitioning the decision problem into a hierarchical framework.

According to ‘AHP method’, a comparison matrix is formed for all parameters that are thought to be a potential variable impacting vulnerability. Each vulnerability factor is evaluated against other factors using the relative importance intensity scale, which ranges from 1 (equal importance) to 9 (very high importance), as shown in **Table 3.3**.

After assigning values of the pairwise comparison matrix's parameters (Appendix II, Table B-2), they were normalized to get the criteria weight (Appendix II, Table B-3).

Table 3.3: The fundamental scale of Saaty, 1977.

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Each of the two parameters equally contributes to the objective
3	Moderate importance	One parameter is preferred over another.
5	strong importance	One parameter is superior to another based on experience and judgment.
7	Very strong importance	Strong support for a particular activity, including evidence of that activity's dominance in practice
9	Extreme importance	The strongest evidence feasible is used to support one behavior over another.
2,4,6,8	Middle scale values between two nearby scale values	When compromise is required
Reciprocals $1/2, 1/3,$ $1/4, \dots$	When comparing activities, I and j, if activity i has one of the aforementioned values assigned to it, then j has the reciprocal value of i.	

The consistency index (CI) and consistency ratio (CR) are calculated by the following equations to make sure from the consistency of the criteria weight.

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad \dots (3.4)$$

$$CR = CI / RI \quad \dots (3.5)$$

Where, λ_{max} is the principal Eigenvalue of the matrix (Calculated in Appendix II, Table B-4), and n is the size of the comparison matrix, RI: random index as reported by Saaty (1977, 1980) and shown in Table 3.4.

The CR should be smaller than 0.1 to provide the maximum level of consistency. If the consistency ratio was more than or equal to 0.1, then, it is necessary to reconsider your decisions.

Table 3.4: Random index for n of parameters

n	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
R	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49	1.51	1.48	1.56

CVI can be calculated by embedding the weight of all variables using the following formula:

$$CVI = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i X \quad \dots (3.6)$$

Where, W_i is the criteria weight of each variable, X is the vulnerability rank of parameters as shown in Table 3.2 and n is the number of parameters.

3.4 Results

3.4.1 Geomorphology

Geomorphological analysis has a crucial role in identifying regions where the risk is relatively high. It measures the reaction of coastal elements to wave impact and shoreline erosion (Hoque et al., 2019; Mahapatra et al., 2015). Generally, cliffy, and rocky shorelines offered maximum resistance capacity, which is less susceptible than soft and sandy coasts (Pramanik et al., 2016; Widura and Mardiatno, 2022). According to Hereher (2015), the area along Alexandria coast is considered a low cliffy coast classified with rank 3 (moderate vulnerability) while the remaining coast represents Nile delta from Abu-Qir Bay up to Port Said coast is a sandy beach with rank 5 (very high vulnerability).

3.4.2 Elevation

Elevation is another essential aspect of determining how vulnerable a shoreline is to SLR because any land under a mean sea level will face floods as sea levels rise (El-Shahat et al., 2021; Pramanik et al., 2016). Low-elevation locations are assumed to be more susceptible, and vice versa (Eldeberky, 2011; Sekovski et al., 2020).

Five categories were employed to assess the coastal vulnerability index based on elevation data: very low (> 6.0 m), low (6.0- 4.0 m), moderate (4.0- 2.0 m), high (2.0- 1.0 m), very high (< 1.0 m), as shown in **Table 3.2**. **Figures 3.3, 3.4(A)**, illustrating the results of an analysis of the STRM model, showed that if the sea level increased by 0.5 m, it will induce a flooding of more than 17.1 % of the Nile delta's entire area, but when the sea level increases by 1-meter, the area exposed to flooding will increase to reach 25.1 %. Additionally, the vulnerability mapping of elevation data revealed that the majority of Nile delta shoreline (84.62 %) has moderate to very high vulnerability.

Figure 3.3: Inundation areas under scenarios SLR of 0.5m, 1.0m

3.4.3 Coastal slope

Coastal slope shows how flat of a coastal area is and serves as an indicator for both the likelihood of shoreline erosion and the relative inundation risk (Torresan et al., 2020). A highly sloping shoreline would be less affected by SLR than a coast with a low slope, where any rise in sea level would result in flooding massive areas of land (Hoque et al., 2019; Mahapatra et al., 2015; Mohd et al., 2021; Sahana et al., 2019).

To classify every shoreline section of the Nile Delta, the slope values were extracted from the STRM model, (Figure 3.4B). The coastal slopes for all segments were rated utilizing indices from 1 to 5, from very low rank to very high-rank susceptibility. According to the results, more than 54.26 % of the Nile Delta's coastline has a slope that is categorized as a very high vulnerability, 5.93 % has a slope that is rated as a high vulnerability, and just 1.52 % has a slope that is classified as a moderate vulnerability. About 38.29 % of the shoreline appears to have a slope variation of more than 1.3 %, which is considered to be of low to very low susceptibility.

3.4.4 Bathymetry

Bathymetry plays a great role in examining the impact of SLR (Hoque et al., 2019). The incursion of seawater is greater in locations with a mild bathymetric slope (Sahana et al., 2019).

The vulnerability Ranks of nearshore Bathymetry were adopted by Hoque et al. (2019) and were classified as very high (< -4.0 m), high (-4.0- -3.0 m), moderate (-3.0- -2.0 m), low (-2.0- -1.0 m), and very low risk (> -1.0 m). Locations that are regarded highly to very highly vulnerable represented about 56 % and are distributed in many parts of Alexandria, east and west of Rosetta, Damietta promontory, Burullus Headland, and

parts of Port Said. About 12 % of the shoreline centered around Gamasa Bay was of moderate risk rating. About 32.88 % of the coastline was under low and very low-risk categories centered in the eastern side of Alexandria, Abu-Qir Bay, and western side of Burullus Headland.

Figure 3.4: Mapping of A) coastal elevation and B) coastal slope

3.4.5 Shoreline change

Shoreline is the interface between water and land. Shoreline erosion is caused by both natural forces e.g., wind, waves, current, tide (Sarhan et al., 2020) and anthropogenic activity, such as the construction of breakwaters, groins, jetties, and dams (Quang et al., 2021).

In light of coastal vulnerability, the regions whose accreting coastlines are considered less susceptible since the deposit decreases wave energy. Erodible coastlines on the other hand, are classified as being extremely susceptible due to the ensuing loss of both human and ecological resources (Murali et al., 2013).

Figure 3.5 shows the assessment of the different parts along the coast, which can be summarized as follows: four areas experienced very high erosion rates based on averaged values, namely, Rosetta promontory (-14.12 m/y), Damietta Promontory (-19.5 m/y) and Burullus Headland (-3.98 m/y) as well as the eastern side of Damietta spit (-6.3 m/y). The accreted areas with high average rates are Alexandria coast (+1.87

m/y) and Gamasa Bay (+3.59 m/y) as well as some portions of Port Said coast (+4.83 m/y) through study period.

The vulnerability ranks of shoreline change were classified by [Torresan et al. \(2020\)](#) as very high (< -2.0), high (-2.0- -1.0), moderate (-1.0- 1.0), Low (1.0- 2.0) and very low risk (> 2.0). About 28.23 % of 324 km of mapped shoreline is rated as very high and high vulnerability, while 15.92% and 55.83% are moderate and low to very low vulnerability, respectively.

Figure 3.5: Decision matrix for shoreline changes along Nile Delta

3.4.6 Significant wave height

Since the Egyptian coast is wave-dominated, the incident waves drive sediment transport resulting in morphological changes. Consequently, a growth in incident wave energy, especially when coupled with rising sea levels, can cause a variety of coastal problems including erosion and flooding (Koroglu et al., 2019; Sahana et al., 2019). The whole coastline was classified from moderate to very high vulnerability. The assigned vulnerability rank map of the Hs displayed that 42.75 % of the coastline is very high vulnerability, followed by high vulnerability (39.16 %), moderate vulnerability (18.09 %).

3.4.7 Tidal range

A group of researchers assumed that high values for tidal range indicate high vulnerability to CC (e.g., (Beluru Jana and Hegde, 2016; Hereher et al., 2020; Kunte et al., 2014; Mani Murali et al., 2018; Mavromatidi et al., 2018). According to their viewpoints, high tidal range results in swift tidal currents that erode and transport sediments. This makes us consider the whole coastline as very low vulnerability.

3.4.8 Sea level change

In the perspective of coastal sensitivity, a high rate of SLR is defined as a high-risk coastal area, (Pramanik et al., 2016). The whole coastline was classified from low to very high vulnerability. Based on sea level change mapping, it was found that around 18.39 % of the coastline is very highly vulnerable, while 13.3 % is highly vulnerable. A large percentage of 43.2 % of the coastline experienced moderate vulnerability followed by a low vulnerability of 25.11 %.

3.4.9 Land subsidence

Land Subsidence also makes coastal areas more susceptible to floods and seawater penetration. The Nile Delta has undergone local land subsidence due to the reduction in Nile inflows caused by the installation of the Aswan High Dam. The vulnerability ranks of land subsidence mapping are classified in **Table 3.2** as very low (<1.0 mm/y), moderate (1.0- 2.0 mm/y), high (2.0- 3.0 mm/y), and very high risk (> 3.0mm/y). The results revealed that about 42.2 % of the coastline is under very low risk, 27.5 % under moderate risk, and 30.3 % under high and very high vulnerability.

3.4.10 Artificial protection structures

Many coastal protection structures were constructed on the coast of the Nile Delta (**Figure 3.6**). They have been built after the construction of the High Dam in Aswan, which prevented sediments from reaching the Mediterranean Sea coast, such as Seawalls, Groins, Jetties, and detached breakwaters ([Tharwat Sarhan et al., 2022](#)). Here, according to [Mohamed \(2020\)](#), the coastal structures were classified into 3 degrees of risk: Considering Seawalls such as at Rosetta and Damietta promontory rated as very low risk while submerged breakwater in Alexandria, detached breakwater at Ras-Elbar resort, groins at the eastern side and western side of Rosetta and Damietta promontory .. etc. rated as moderate risk. Locations without any structures are rated as having very high vulnerability. Based on coastal structures mapping, 4.03 % of the shoreline has very low vulnerability, while 47.35% has moderate vulnerability as against 48.62% being very highly vulnerable. It is evident that the region needs to build some coastal infrastructure to deal with the threats of rising sea levels.

Figure 3.6: Artificial structures along Nile Delta coast at A) Rosetta promontory, B) Burullus Headland, C) Damietta promontory, and D) El-Gamil inlet

3.4.11 Wave direction

Another aspect that is thought to have an impact on the coastal system is wave direction. This factor indicates the wave direction and its relationship with shoreline orientation. **Figure 3.7** shows that N, NNW, NW, and WNW wave orientations are the most prevalent. Additionally, there are minor percentages from the NNE, NE, and ENE directions. [Rangel-Buitrago et al. \(2020\)](#) assumed that shore-perpendicular waves at an angle of 0° expose the beach to the risk of inundation and more dangerous surge storms. So, these coasts have very high vulnerability (rank 5). On the other hand, very low

vulnerability is associated with relatively large angles, such as 10-45° (rank 1). Small angles, such as 0-10°, provide medium vulnerability (rank 3). The results show 60.25 percent of the coastline to be at very low risk, 27.6 percent at moderate risk and 12.15 percent at very high risk.

Figure 3.7: Wave rose diagram for the locations: A) Rosetta Headland, B) Burullus Headland, C) Damietta Headland

3.4.12 Distance to urban

The predicted increases in storm surges and SLR may exacerbate coastal damage, especially with growing population density. Also, rapid coastal development may degrade the ecology. The danger of exposure to coastal threats increases in the urban area adjacent to the seashore and reduces as the distance from the coastline increases, according to the coastal vulnerability point. The results indicate that about 49.2 % of

coastline has very low vulnerability, with low and moderate vulnerability constituting 18.72% and 9.35%, respectively as against 22.73% for high and very high vulnerability. The Nile Delta coast is typically wide enough to handle wave and current action except for Alexandria, Abo-Qir Bay, and Port Said.

3.4.13 Land use Land cover LULC

Changes in land use significantly affect whether coastal vulnerability increases or decreases. The resulting land use map was verified by Google Earth, and the accuracy coefficients were calculated by using 265 referenced points that were distributed randomly. Overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient is determined from the error matrix and found to be 85.7 %, and 78.92 % respectively (see [Appendix II, Eqs B-1, B-2](#)), (**Table 3.5**) which is well sufficient to map LULC. In this study, LULC features as shown in **Figure 3.8** are classified into 6 categories: water body, wetland, urban land, agricultural land, fishing farm as well as barren soil. The coastal vulnerability indexes were ranked using six categories: very low (waterbody, barren land), high (agricultural land), and very high (urban lands, fishing farms, and wetlands). Finally, according to their grading categories, 7.43 % of the shoreline has a very low vulnerability, 1.3 % is highly vulnerable, and 91.33 % has a very high vulnerability.

The detailed maps of coastal vulnerability for all considered parameters are displayed in **Figure 3.9(a, b, c)**. Also, the distribution of vulnerability ranks for each parameter by percentage is described in **Figure 3.10**. The combination of 85% low elevation, 61.7% gentle coastal slope, 68% low bathymetric slope, 44.15% shoreline erosion, 75% sea level rising, 57.8% Land subsidence, 95.97% lack of effective coastal structures, 32.08% urbanization proximity to the coast, and 92.63 % land use, exposes more than half of the Nile Delta's coast to very high to moderate risk levels.

Figure 3.8: LULC classification for Nile Delta region

Table 3.5: Summary of accuracy and error of land use classification

Class name	Training cell	Overall accuracy %	Kappa Coeff. %	Producer Accuracy %	User Accuracy %	Omission Error %	commission Error %
Water body	1733834	85.7%	78.92%	68.2	100	31.8	0
Wetland	52427			88.9	69.6	11.1	30.4
Urban area	115630			93.8	83.3	6.3	16.7
Agriculture land	329071			88.7	96.2	11.3	3.8
Fish farms	49611			58.3	35	41.7	65
Barren area	15869825			79.2	82.6	20.8	17.4

Figure 3.9: a) Mapping vulnerability of Geomorphology, Elevation, Coastal slope, Bathymetry, Shoreline change, b) Mapping vulnerability of Hs, Tidal range, SLR, land subsidence, Artificial protection, c) Mapping vulnerability of Wave direction, Distance to urban, LULC

Figure 3.10: Percentage of the vulnerability of each parameter on the Nile Delta coast

3.4.14 Calculation of CVI

Ultimately, in ArcGIS, all of the ranking parameters were incorporated, and the map was created using 20th, 40th, 60th, and 80th percentile procedures. The CVI values, as determined by Gornitz's approach, varied from 8.32 to 1248.075. The CVI has a mean value of 215.74 and a standard deviation value of 171.46. Five vulnerability ranks e.g., very high (1248.075–312.02), high (312.02–197.33), moderate (197.33–144.11), low (144.11–93.03), and very low (93.03–8.32) were assigned to the CVI map, as seen in **Figure 3.11**.

The comparison matrix for the AHP technique, formed for all considered parameters based on expert opinions, is detailed in **Table 3.6**. Five coastal engineering specialists were consulted, and the criteria weight for each factor was determined using a normalized pair-wise matrix. To ensure the coherence of the comparison matrix values, the consistency index (CI) and consistency ratio (CR) were calculated, as shown in Equations (4), (5) and **Table 3.7**. The results highlighted that elevation (weight of 0.178), significant wave height (weight of 0.125), and the presence of coastal structures (weight of 0.193) are the most impactful factors for the Nile Delta region, followed by beach slope, bathymetry, shoreline change, and distance to urban. Finally, these parameters: geomorphology, sea level change, land subsidence, wave direction, LULC, and tidal range were deemed less influential from the point of view of experts.

The values of the CVI results based on AHP model ranged from 2.016 to 4.499 with a mean of 3.488 and a standard Deviation of 0.349, respectively. The CVI map (**Figure 3.12**) shows that 20.11% of the coastline has very low vulnerability (CVI values of 2.176-3.171). Additionally, 40% of the coastline is classified as low to moderate susceptibility (CVI values of 3.171-3.398 and 3.398-3.593, respectively). High and very high vulnerability areas (CVI values of 3.593-3.801 and 3.801-4.499, respectively) account for 39.9% of the entire coastline.

Correlation test for two investigated models:

The correlation test was performed to verify the similarity of the results between the two methods and produced a good correlation. The Gornitz's and AHP models have a high level of consistency, as shown by the correlation coefficient (r) for values of CVI which is about 72.5 % (**Figure 3.13**).

Figure 3.11: Coastal vulnerability mapping by using Gornitz’s model along Nile Delta coast: A) Alexandria coast, B) Rosetta, C) Burullus, D) Damietta, E) Port Said coast.

Figure 12: Coastal vulnerability mapping by using AHP model along the Nile Delta coast: A) Alexandria coast, B) Rosetta, C) Burullus, D) Damietta, E) Port Said coast.

Table 3.6: Comparison matrix and criteria weight

	Geomorphology	Elevation	Coastal slope	Bathymetry	Shore-line change	Significant wave height	Sea level change	Tidal range	Distance to urban	Wave direction	Artificial structures	Land subsidence	LULC	Criteria weight
Geomorphology	1	0.14	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.2	0.33	5	0.5	0.5	0.14	2	0.5	0.031
Elevation	7	1	3	2	5	0.5	5	8	3	5	2	5	3	0.178
Coastal slope	3	0.33	1	2	2	0.5	3	3	0.33	2	0.2	2	2	0.069
Bathymetry	3	0.5	0.5	1	2	2	2	2	0.33	2	0.2	3	2	0.075
Shore-line change	3	0.2	0.5	0.5	1	2	3	4	1	3	0.20	3	3	0.080
Significant wave height	5	2	2	0.5	0.5	1	3	5	3	3	0.5	5	3	0.125
Sea level change	3	0.2	0.33	0.5	0.33	0.33	1	2	0.33	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.33	0.030
Tidal range	0.2	0.125	0.33	0.5	0.25	0.2	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	0.17	0.5	0.5	0.020
Distance to urban	2	0.33	3	3	1	0.33	3	2	1	2	0.33	3	3	0.084
Wave direction	2	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.33	0.33	2	2	0.5	1	0.25	1	0.33	0.035
Artificial structures	7	0.5	5	5	5	2	5	6	3	4	1	5	5	0.193
Land subsidence	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.33	0.33	0.2	2	2	0.33	1	0.2	1	0.33	0.029
LULC	2	0.33	0.5	0.5	0.33	0.33	3	2	0.33	3	0.2	3	1	0.050

Table 3.7: Consistency index calculations.

Parameters	Values
λ_{max}	14.62
n	13
RI	1.56
CI	0.136
CR	0.087

Figure 3.13: Correlation test between Gornitz's and AHP model.

3.5 Discussions

This is one of the few attempts to evaluate coastal vulnerability over the low-lying Nile Delta coast using social-economic and physical factors and the first to attempt so using the AHP approach. The Nile Delta is historically vulnerable to several natural

hazards, including floods, land subsidence, coastline erosion, and SLR, putting millions of people in danger so it is highly worrying (Elshinnawy and Almaliki, 2021).

This research evaluates and pinpoints vulnerable spots in the Nile Delta more thoroughly by applying the AHP and Gornitz's models considering 11 physical, geological, and two socio-economic parameters. Gornitz's model seeks to evaluate coastal regions sensitivity to SLR straightforwardly and simply. It combines the proposed variables while standardizing their weight and relevance. The AHP model, on the other hand, is a more extensive and systematic method and serves as a tool for making decisions. It is very helpful for analyzing coastal vulnerability since it can consider expert opinion and convert qualitative data into quantitative weights (Turriza et al., 2024). Furthermore, the pair-wise comparison matrix can prioritize one variable over the other depending on its relevance and influence on the research region. Finally, the consistency test aids in analyzing the efficacy of measurements, which adds some validity to the research, compared to random weights (Murali et al., 2013). AHP model provides a more accurate view of the vulnerability of the delta and can help planners and policymakers identify the most susceptible places that need immediate attention.

The distribution of vulnerability categories through 6 zones along the Nile Delta coast, namely Alexandria, Abo-Qir, and Rosetta, Abo-Khashba, Burullus Headland, Gamasa, and Damietta, Port said, reveals that some are highly vulnerable (**Figure 3.14**). The beaches of Abu-Qir Bay, Abu Khashba Bay, and scattered parts of Port Said are all considered significantly susceptible. Alexandria, Burullus Headland, Gamasa Bay, and Damietta coast, on the other hand, are moderately hazardous locations that, due to their high population density and the presence of a sufficient number of buildings, might become vulnerable. Hattab (2015) monitored susceptible spots situated predominantly (in Abo-Qir Bay and the western sector of Alexandria), whereas zones designated as moderately vulnerable were in Alexandria, Rosetta, and Damietta.

The Alexandria coast features a low cliff shore, a gentle coastal slope, a low bathymetric slope, many urban areas close to the shoreline, and exposure to high waves. Using Gornitz's and AHP methods, it is seen that 32% and 40% of the entire coastline are at risk of very high to high vulnerability, respectively. About 15% and 28% of its shoreline, respectively, are moderately vulnerable, while a percentage of the entire length belongs to the very low (~25.75%, 18.6%) or low (27.6%, 14%)

susceptibility classes, respectively. It is also observed that the AHP model indicates a significant degree of danger in the western sector of Alexandria, which is not evident in Gornitz's model. The research results are congruent with what was found by (El-Geziry, 2020; Hereher, 2015) that 30 % of the Alexandria coast has a very high vulnerability to the SLR. With less resilience than the Alexandria shores, the soft sandy beaches of Abu Qir Bay and Rosetta Headland are more susceptible to SLR (Mohamed, 2020), harmonized with the current study's findings.

Figure 3.14 makes it evident that both approaches reached a similar conclusion about the Abu Khashba coast over 50% exposure to a very high vulnerability. This coast has a sandy beach, low-lying land, substantial land subsidence, rising sea levels, unprotected beaches, and extensive urbanization. It is also vulnerable to extreme coastal erosion. Similar findings were concluded by (Dewidar and Bayoumi, 2021; El Sayed and Khalifa, 2017).

Additionally, it is apparent that the Burullus coast has a low to moderate vulnerability risk, as shown by percentages higher than 74% and 88% for the two techniques, respectively. This beach is sandy, but it has a high-sloping beach with medium exposure to high waves, sea level rise, and land subsidence, protected by a variety of coastal structures. Gamasa and Damietta coasts have experienced very low to moderate risk for 69.22% and 60.26% of the whole coast, respectively. Looking at the shore of Port Said, we find that the two approaches reported a "very high" vulnerability risk of 24% and 20%, but the results were somewhat different in a "very low" vulnerability risk rating of 12% and 25%, respectively. Substantial erosion rates were also discovered in this region by EIKotby et al. (2023).

All of it is essential because decisions on coastal growth and preservation need thorough planning and consideration of all relevant financial, environmental, social, and political issues.

Figure 3.14: Distribution of CVI scores (%) for Egypt's Nile Delta coast for a) Gornitz's model, b) AHP model.

3.6 Conclusion:

The Nile Delta is in northern Egypt, where the Nile River empties into the Mediterranean Sea. It is a highly inhabited and agriculturally productive region prone to SLR due to its low elevation. This region is already grappling with concerns including land subsidence, urbanization, and wetlands loss, all of which can exacerbate the consequences of SLR. Thirteen parameters were considered to identify the coastal vulnerability in terms of coastal characteristics and impacts. To integrate these parameters and calculate CVI, Gornitz's and AHP techniques are employed. CVI values indicate the degree of susceptibility across the research area, varying from very low to very high risk. The results based on the AHP model reveal that on average, 128 km (around 40 %) of the coastline is located within a very high to high-vulnerability zone

concentrated in locations such as Abo-Khashba Bay (75%), Abu-Qir Bay and Rosetta Headland (48%), and western sector of Alexandria (25%) demanding more attention. In contrast, 65 km (20%) of the 324 km coastline lies in very-low vulnerability areas located in specified parts of Alexandria coast (18.5%), Burullus Headland (38.6%), Gamasa Bay (35%), some parts of Port Said (24.6%). Furthermore, carefully evaluating coastal risks employing factors such as artificial structures, distance to urban, the direction of wave propagation, LULC, and land subsidence is critical in identifying sites prone to SLR. This study emphasizes how the AHP approach, integrated with expert opinions, shows a more balanced representation of vulnerability degrees along the Nile Delta coast. This would allow planners to exercise greater caution in implementing coastal management strategies and to protect future generations from the impacts of CC.

Data availability

The authors declare that all the relevant data described in the article are included in the article itself as tables, figures, and supplementary information.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Chapter (4)

Impact evaluation of development plans in the Egyptian harbors on morphological changes using numerical simulation (case study: Damietta harbor, northeastern coast of Egypt).

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ABSTRACT

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Evaluation of development plans in the Egyptian harbors on morphological changes using numerical simulation (case study: Damietta harbor, northeastern coast of Egypt).

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Abstract

The Egyptian government is grappling with the challenge of sedimentation in Damietta Harbor (DH), leading to expensive and recurring dredging operations for safe vessel navigation. This research examined the changes in the region's coastline, both before and after the port was established between 1977 and 1995. The impact of the government's policy to halt backfilling in the navigation lane on adjacent beaches until 2023 was also assessed using remote sensing (RS) and the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) program, revealing varying yearly accretion and erosion rates. Following a shoreline movement tracking procedure, in the period from 1985 to 2023, the total areas undergoing erosion and accretion amounted to -1.36 km^2 and $+2.21 \text{ km}^2$, respectively.

To address the issue, the research team developed scenarios reflecting regional realities and conducted a numerical simulation using the Coastal Modeling System (CMS). Morphological alterations in the approach channel and pre- and post-port regions were monitored to assess the scenarios. The study also explored how deepening the navigation channel affected the annual sediment volume. Results showed that Scenario 5, involving breakwaters extension and the new western breakwater (NWBW), effectively controlled sediment. However, sedimentation increased with the deepening of the navigation channel. Scenario 7, with a 19 m deepening, exhibited slightly higher sediment volume by 21.75% but stood out for its capacity to handle large vessels. Additionally, the sedimentation in the

navigation channel experienced a notable 72.1% decrease in Scenario 8, which portrays the anticipated final state of DH compared to the benchmark case.

The study noted morphological changes from planned coastal constructions on the eastern side, including detached breakwaters (DBW) and Y-groins (Y-gs). Despite significant development costs, these structures were deemed insufficient to stabilize the shoreline. In summary, the research highlights the complexity of addressing sedimentation in DH, emphasizing the need for nuanced approaches in coastal management, and considering the consequences of deepening navigation channels.

Keywords:

Damietta harbor, Shoreline change, Sedimentation problem, CMS model, Morphology changes

4.1 Introduction

DH in the Mediterranean region is a key port for international trade but contends with operational challenges due to sedimentation, resulting in reduced water depth and constraints on docking vessel sizes. As a central hub for import and export activities, it is crucial to address this issue to uphold the harbor's efficiency, enable the accommodation of larger vessels, and maintain its pivotal role in facilitating international trade in the region.

To maintain a suitable depth, periodic dredging involves removing accumulated sediments resulting from erosion in a water body. Studies indicated that DH annually dredged volumes ranging from 0.35 million to 2 million m³ (Abo Zed, 2007; Frihy et al., 2002). The cost of maintenance dredging has escalated, rising from 0.23 Euro/m³ (1.9 LE/m³) in 1988 to 1.10 Euro/m³ (9.25 LE/m³) in 2001 (Abo Zed, 2007). These high costs, combined with substantial sedimentation, impact the harbor's economy, as evidenced by an estimated expenditure of nearly 77 million LE in 2015 for dredging 1.7 million m³ of sediment (Khalifa et al., 2017). Despite being a costly process requiring specialized equipment, dredging raises environmental concerns due to the release of sediment, contaminants, and pollutants into the water during operations (Masria et al., 2021). In response to siltation challenges, the Egyptian government has initiated measures, including investments in dredging equipment and regular operations to clear sediment from the harbor's channels. Despite these efforts, siltation remains a significant and persistent challenge for DH.

Numerous studies have proposed various scenarios and utilized numerical simulations to model DH's morphology and sediment transport rates, aiming to address the challenges

posed by siltation at the harbor entrance. [Gad et al., 2013](#) employed three numerical modeling techniques, including the NMLONG (1D depth averaged finite difference wave model), RMA2 (2D depth averaged finite element hydrodynamic model), and SED2D (2D depth-averaged finite element sediment transport model), to develop effective strategies such as extending breakwaters or constructing submerged dikes along the eastern bank. [Khalifa, 2017](#) used Delft 3D modeling to assess scenarios like extending breakwaters and implementing sediment traps. [Masria et al., 2022](#) explored six scenarios using the CMS model, including breakwaters extension and groins building along the eastern side of DH. Certainly, various studies have proposed the use of numerical models to address challenges in ports and tidal inlets along the Nile Delta coast of Egypt, as well as in other ports worldwide. For instance, ([Masria et al., 2021](#); [Sharaan et al., 2018](#)) investigated and proposed solutions for issues specific to the Burullus fishing port. [Nassar et al., 2019](#) suggested and analyzed different scenarios for the artificial western inlet at Bardawil Lagoon. [Elnabwy et al., 2024](#) employed the CMS model and field observations to examine the sedimentation challenges for the developed fishing harbor of Ezbet Elborg, Egypt. Additionally, ([Bosa et al., 2021](#); [Li et al., 2011](#); [Yüksek, 1995](#); [Zikra et al., 2021](#)) emphasize the efficacy of numerical modeling for addressing port-related challenges around the world.

Since 1970, the Damietta shoreline has suffered greatly from dreadful erosion due to being one of the significant locations affected by dynamic changes. A major contributing factor to this problem is human intervention, specifically the construction of the High Dam in Aswan, which traps sediments and prohibits them from feeding the Damietta shoreline. Before establishing the High Dam in Aswan, the shoreline advanced and protruded for 2-3 km due to the 0.6–1.8 million m³ of sediment that flowed annually from the Damietta branch into the Mediterranean Sea ([Ismail et al., 2019](#)). After the completion of the High Dam, the Mediterranean Sea's sediment flux became disregarded, allowing waves and currents to deteriorate the coastline.

The construction of Western Breakwater (WBW) and Eastern Breakwaters (EBW) in DH aimed to mitigate sedimentation but inadvertently affected neighboring beaches and the shoreline. ([Abo Zed, 2007](#); [El-Asmar and White, 2002](#)) noted accretion ranged from 2 to 4.2 km upstream of the WBW and erosion from 5 to 6.2 km beyond the EBW, respectively. However, [ElKotby et al., 2023](#) observed that between 2010 to 2022, the shoreline eroded about -4.12 m/yr eastward and expanded +3.4 m/yr westward of the harbor. The study by

Ibrahim et al., 2024 involved conducting a net longshore sediment transport (NLST) simulation using the MIKE21 modelling to analyze the pre- and post-construction phases of DH for the data from 1940 to 2020.

The DSAS is an automatic statistical algorithm, utilized to digitize the shoreline, track coastal activities, measure the paces of accretion and erosion, and identify the eroded or accreted areas. The accuracy of DSAS mostly depends on Satellite measurements and delineated shorelines. However, it may have trouble correctly capturing intricate coastal processes. The pattern of shoreline alterations during the past 20 years has been calculated by several authors worldwide, e.g. (Akhter et al., 2024; Harikrishna et al., 2024; Kilar, 2023; Quang et al., 2021). In Egypt, the shoreline shifts were analyzed historically using DSAS technique by numerous researchers e.g. (Ali and El-Magd, 2016; Awad and El-Sayed, 2021; Elsherif et al., 2020; El-Zeiny et al., 2016; Mansour et al., 2024; Mirdan et al., 2023; Tharwat Sarhan et al., 2022).

The study initially seeks to update the trend of shoreline alterations by leveraging RS techniques and the DSAS program, from 1977 to 2023. It evaluates the effectiveness of the protective structures. The Damietta Governorate ambitiously plans to develop DH to address sedimentation issues, increase its capacity, and improve profitability in line with the Egyptian government's 2030 vision. To simulate the reality that the Egyptian government would intend, different scenarios were proposed and evaluated in this research using the CMS model, which can only be used for similar ports that have identical geometrical and environmental conditions, with a specific focus on addressing sedimentation issues in DH. The effects of these scenarios on the surrounding beaches are also scrutinized, encompassing the amenities that have already been installed or are scheduled to be built shortly in the region east of the DH.

4.2. Study area

DH, (coordinate: 31°28'14.8"N 31°45'37.8"E), is a key seaport in the Nile Delta region of Egypt, strategically located about 9.7 km west of the Damietta Nile branch on the Mediterranean Sea coast, **Fig. 4.1**. Recognized for its vital role in global trade, DH serves as a crucial hub for Egypt's import and export activities. Ongoing development efforts aim to enhance its capacities.

Coastal structures have been deployed to safeguard DH and its environs against coastal erosion, wave impacts, and sedimentation. These structures play a crucial role in

maintaining navigational channels, ensuring the secure movement of ships entering or exiting the harbor. Additionally, their purpose extends to shielding the eastern side of the port from substantial erosion. To address sedimentation concerns in DH, two breakwaters, the WBW and EBW, were initially designed, aiming to minimize sedimentation rates. The WBW, running parallel to the navigational channel at a length of 1,500 m and reaching a depth of 7 m, and the EBW, nearly perpendicular with a span of 500 m and reaching a depth of 3 m, were implemented (Sharaan and Negm, 2017). However, it was observed that the existing lengths of these breakwaters were insufficient to effectively combat sediment movement at the port entrance and the initial navigational channel.

Recent developments since 2021 have involved significant modifications to these structures. The EBW has undergone an extension, now parallel to the channel and stretching 1420 m with a depth of 12 m. Additionally, the WBW on the western side will be extended by 1225 m to a depth of 12 m. The NWBW, spanning 5400 m, is now being introduced with the first phase of its installation having been completed to augment the port's capacity and accommodate a greater number of vessels.

The navigational canal, excavated between 1982 and 1984, currently maintains a water depth of 15 m and extends 20 km offshore (Frihy et al., 2002). The width of the canal varies from 200 m at the port entrance to 300 m away from the breakwaters (Gad et al., 2013). Efforts are underway to deepen the canal further, aiming for a depth of 19 m to accommodate Mother ships (El-Asmar and Taha, 2022).

The prevailing northwest winds and resultant longshore current contribute to sediment transport from west to east, compounded by the port's location in a sink area where wave and current impact is minimal, leading to sediment accumulation. The WBW traps the majority of these sediments, causing severe erosion along the eastern beaches. To address this, measures have been taken, including the construction of eight DBWs between 1991 and 2002, each 200 m long with 200 m spacing, to protect the Ras El Bar beach resort (El-Gamal et al., 2020). The government aims to add two more DBW west existing one to ensure coastline stability as part of the region's future development plan.

Additionally, in 2019, four Y- gs were erected just east of the port, with three groins measuring 170 m and the fourth 120 m, spaced 400 m apart, to combat ongoing erosion. These measures collectively aim to safeguard affected beaches and mitigate erosion resulting from sediment transport (El-Asmar and Taha, 2022; ElKotby et al., 2023).

Fig. 4.1. Study area location

4.3. Materials and methods:

4.3.1. Remote sensing study

4.3.1.1 Dataset and Processing

The analysis of coastline locations at and around DH utilized satellite images spanning 46 years. Digital images, including Landsat Multispectral Scanner (MSS), Thematic Mapper (TM), Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+), and Operational Land Imager (OLI), acquired from 1977 to 2023 intervals, were employed in the current investigation. These images, sourced from the USGS Global Visualization website (<http://www.earthexplorer.usgs.gov>), provided a spatial resolution of 30 m (see **Table 4.1**).

To guarantee the reliability of RS outcomes, the selected images must contain no more than 10% cloud cover. Geometric correction is then applied to rectify discrepancies between actual location coordinates and the raw image data on the ground or target image. Subsequently, these data undergo projection to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system, specifically in the World Geodetic System (WGS 84) zone 36. Additionally, radiometric calibration is conducted, involving sensor calibration and atmospheric correction, utilizing ENVI v.5.3 software.

Table 4.1. Information about the satellite images utilized in this research.

Acquired date	Sensor type	Resolution (m)
30/05/1977	Landsat2 MSS	60
02/06/1980	Landsat2 MSS	60
03/06/1985	Landsat5 TM	30
17/06/1995	Landsat5 TM	30
01/05/2000	Landsat5 TM	30
18/06/2005	Landsat7 ETM	30
08/06/2016	Landsat8 OLI	30
08/06/2020	Landsat8 OLI	30
03/05/2023	Landsat8 OLI	30

4.3.1.2 Shoreline extraction and analysis

Shoreline extraction was conducted through Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) classification techniques in ENVI v.5.3 software. NDWI was determined using **Eq. 4.1**, which needed adjustment for every used Landsat image due to the different wave spectra.

$$NDWI = \frac{Green - NIR}{Green + NIR} \quad Eq (4.1)$$

Here, NIR is the Near-Infrared wave band, and Green is the green wave band. The NDWI images were classified as follows: values larger than "0" denoted surfaces of water, and values equal to or less than "0" denoted non-water surfaces (El Kafrawy et al., 2017; Zoysa et al., 2023). The resulting data was exported as a shapefile to ArcGIS v.10.7 software, where it underwent conversion from feature to polyline (refer to **Fig. 4.2**). For the analysis of shoreline changes, the DSAS, an Esri ArcGIS add-on, was employed to compute shoreline change rate data across multiple coastlines with various dates, as outlined by El-Asmar and Taha, 2022. Each set of shorelines covered a coastal length of approximately 20 km, intersected by 2000 transects spaced at 10 m intervals. DSAS measured shoreline changes at each transect using three different methods (Mirdan et al., 2023). The spatial changes in the study area's coastline were assessed using the End Point Rate (EPR) model for intermediate periods (1977–1980, 1985–1995, 2005–2016, 2020–2023) and for the overall long-term period spanning from 1985 to 2023.

4.3.2. Morpho-dynamics study

4.3.2.1 Field Observation Data

Initiating a CMS modeling project involves the crucial step of compiling and organizing data, where various essential data points such as the study domain's geometry, bathymetry, shoreline position, layout of coastal structures, wave characteristics, water elevation, and

sediment properties play a vital role. The field data, encompassing bathymetric, wave, and tide information, were sourced from the Coastal Research Institute (CoRI) for both the navigation channel and its surrounding area. Notably, the bathymetric survey conducted for this study took place in 2016 and 2017, while wave data was collected at a water depth of 12 m in the navigation channel using a wave gauge identified as S4DW.

Fig. 4.2(e) and the left panel of **Fig. 4.3** provide visual representations of the wave rose and bathymetry. Damietta coast experienced seasonal wave environment. Strong storm waves coming in from the NW- NNW in the winter (October to March of 2010) move sediment eastward as resulting long-shore current with velocities of up to 0.9 m/s (El-Asmar et al., 2016). Long waves during the spring and summer are predominantly from the NNW- WNW sector, exerting a significant influence on the NW direction, while lesser contributions come from the NE, NNE (13.5%), and SW (3.85%). These can cause the generation of an eastward-flowing long-shore current with velocities between 0.1 and 1.2 m/s (Elnabwy et al., 2024). Notably, the waves reach a maximum height of 3.73 m, with an average height of 0.74 m. Waves less than 1 m occur 68% of the year and waves more than 2 m occur 0.04% of the time (Ibrahim et al., 2024). The average significant wave period is 4.31 seconds, with a maximum period of 6.6 seconds. The peak wave period fluctuates between 6 and 12.3 seconds, as illustrated in the right panel of **Fig. 4.3**.

The coastal region of the Nile Delta exhibits a characteristic micro-tidal semi-diurnal tidal regime, featuring a tidal range of 25 to 30 cm, as reported by Masria et al., 2021. Tide gauge data for Damietta beach, specifically covering the year 2015, provides insight into water levels. In the DH area, there is a gradual decrease in the mean grain size from the beach towards the sea. The mean grain size for beach sand falls within the range of 0.14 mm to 0.58 mm, with a comprehensive average of 0.25 mm (Khalifa et al., 2017).

Fig. 4.2. Shoreline extraction and human interventions along Damietta coast: a) DH in 2016 and 2023, b) Y-gs east of DH in 2016 and 2023, c) DBW along Ras-Elbar resort, d) Jetties at Damietta promontory, e) Wave rose at DH entrance.

Fig. 4.3. Bathymetry and Meteorological data

4.3.2.2 Hydrodynamic Model Description

Model description

This study employed numerical simulation through the 2D dynamic model, the CMS, developed by the US Army Corps of Engineers Coastal and Hydraulics Laboratory. About 260 runs were tested at the numerical simulation lab, at hydraulic department, Mansoura university. CMS simulates hydrodynamics and sediment transport in coastal seas. The model is depth-averaged and does not account for the vertical profile of current velocities and suspended sediment. The CMS model comprises two integral modules: CMS-Flow and CMS-Wave. CMS-Flow is capable of simulating water and sediment movement in 2D and 3D, accounting for factors such as tides, wind, and river inflow. It solves the 2D depth-integrated continuity and momentum equations using a finite-volume method (Nassar et al., 2019). In contrast, CMS-Wave replicates wave behavior in coastal regions, encompassing phenomena like refraction, reflection, and wave breaking (Masria et al., 2022). It solves the steady-state wave-action balance equation on a non-uniform Cartesian grid (Nassar et al., 2019). These two models can be used separately or in tandem via a steering module. When coupled, CMS-Wave provides certain variables to CMS-Flow, such as wave height and direction, wave-breaking dissipation, and radiation stress gradients. CMS-Wave uses the updated bathymetry, water levels, and currents from CMS-Flow (Nassar et al., 2018). This coupling facilitates the simulation of significant processes such as shoreline changes, erosion, and storm-induced flooding. The simulation is executed through the SMS software by specifying the CMS-Flow simulation period and running CMS-Wave at regular intervals. The CMS model assumes that sediments are non-cohesive and have constant density and porosity. A detailed explanation of how to run the CMS model can be accessed at Masria et al., 2022.

The CMS provides three different models for sediment transport: (1) Equilibrium total load, (2) Equilibrium bed load plus advection-diffusion for suspended load, and (3) Non-Equilibrium total load. The non-equilibrium sediment transport model was applied in this study. In this model, the sediment transport is current-related. The 2DH transport equation for the current-related total load was mentioned by Nassar et al., 2021. The transport formulae developed by Lund-CIRP, Van Rijn, and Watanabe are employed to compute the near-bed sediment concentration capacity. The Rijn, 1984 transports equations are utilized with the recalibrated coefficients of van Rijn, 2007 as shown:

$$q_b = 0.015 \rho_s U h \left(\frac{U_e - U_{cr}}{\sqrt{(s-1)gd_{50}}} \right)^{1.5} \left(\frac{d_{50}}{h} \right)^{1.2} \quad \text{Eq. 4.2}$$

$$q_s = 0.012 \rho_s U d_{50} \left(\frac{U_e - U_{cr}}{\sqrt{(s-1)gd_{50}}} \right)^{2.4} D_*^{-0.6} \quad \text{Eq. 4.3}$$

Where; q_b : bed load transport rate in m^2/sec ; q_s : current-related suspended load transport in m^2/sec ; U_{cr} : the critical depth-averaged velocity for initiation of motion; U_e is the effective depth-averaged velocity calculated as $U_e = U + 0.4U_w$ in which U_w : the peak orbital velocity based on the significant wave height; h : the total water depth; D_* : dimensionless grain size; g : gravitational constant; d_{50} : the median grain size

Model setup:

Non-uniform Cartesian grids enable local refinement through a gradual variation in grid spacing and are applicable to both CMS-Flow and CMS-Wave. Utilizing two concurrent computational grids of identical size, one for the CMS-Flow model and one for the CMS-Wave model, facilitated an extensive simulation of the DH system, encompassing the approach channel, nearby beaches, and breakwaters within the system's grids.

The CMS-Flow grid extended 4.0 km offshore, covering 2.5 km west and 6 km east of DH (refer to **Fig. 4.4(a)**). Employing a fine grid spacing of 20 m within the approach channel allowed for precise simulation of the area's morphological processes and sediment transport. To enhance computational efficiency, the grid dimension was gradually increased to 150 m offshore. CMS-Flow simulation of the flow field was driven by the tide data measured along the open boundaries in 2015. Regarding waves, the modeling effort incorporated wave records from 2010, considered representative of the study. The CMS-Wave model adopted the half-plane model, illustrated in **Fig. 4.4(b)**, to address wave dynamics in the simulation.

Fig. 4.4. Model grids with boundary condition for DH, (a) CMS-Flow grid; (b) CMS-Wave grid; A) Hard bottom cells at the DH entrance in CMS-Flow; B) Rubble mound cells at the DH entrance in CMS-Wave.

Model calibration

During the calibration process, adjustments may be necessary for a set of model parameters, model geometry, and bathymetry. Initial test runs can be carried out to assist users in establishing an appropriate model setup, considering factors such as grid resolution, domain extent, boundary condition types, and time steps for various cases.

The calibration process considered crucial parameters such as hydrodynamics time step (600, 450, 300 sec), sediment transport formulae (Lund-CIRP, Watanabe, Van-Rijn), bedload scaling factor (0.5, 1, 2), suspended load scaling factor (0.5, 1, 2), bedload adaption length (5, 10, 20), and various Manning coefficients (0.01, 0.025, 0.04). Utilizing the bathymetric survey data from 2016, the numerical model was calibrated, and predictions for bottom evolution in 2017 were generated. Sensitivity analysis and model calibration were carried out using several profiles on the eastern side of DH, as depicted in **Fig. 4.5(a)**. Cross sections for elevation depth were extracted from the bathymetry survey of 2017 using 3D analyst option in ArcGIS 10.7, illustrating profiles graph with labels. The corresponding bathymetric maps in 2016 and after simulation in 2017 (using the VanRijn formula) are presented in **Fig. 4.5 (b, c)**. A comparative analysis was performed at DH profiles 1, 2, and 3 in 2016 to showcase the disparities between measured and simulated profiles in 2017. The R^2 and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) were computed for each profile, indicating that the model is highly qualified to predict coastal morpho-dynamic processes, (as demonstrated in **Fig. 4.6 and 4.7**), also ([Appendix III, Figs C-1: C-13](#)), with a Manning coefficient of 0.01, d_{50} of 0.2mm, a 450-sec time step, a scaling factor of 2.0, and an adaptation length of 20 m, utilizing the VanRijn formula. When sediment conditions are close to the critical shear stress of motion, the Van Rijn formula tends to underestimate the amount of sediment transport. Additionally, based on research by ([Camenen and Larroudé, 2003](#); [Cialone et al., 1991](#)), it often underestimates the movement of sediment near the shore and tends to overestimate the transport in the case of very fine sediments.

Fig. 4.5. Explained a) Profiles location east DH, b) Bathymetry map 2016, c) Morphology change after simulation for 2017 using VanRijn formula.

Fig. 4.6. Estimated values of NRMSE and R2 between the measured and calculated depth in 2017 for (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; and (c) Profile 3 for different manning coefficient n (sediment formula VanRijn, time step = 450 s, scaling factor = 2.0 and adaptation length = 20 m).

Fig. 4.7. Estimated values of NRMSE and R2 between the measured and calculated depth in 2017 for (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; and (c) Profile 3 for different sediment formula (Manning coefficient $n = 0.01$, time step = 450 s, Scaling factor = 2.0 and adaptation length = 20 m).

Proposed scenarios.

This study evaluated the strategies and initiatives devised by the Egyptian government concerning the EBW, WBW, and NWBW to mitigate the persistent siltation issue in the navigation channel. Potential solutions, outlined in **Fig. 4.8**, were explored. The first scenario proposed an extension of the EBW by 1420 m, aligned parallel to the navigation channel. The second scenario recommended the extension of the WBW as the primary breakwater, measuring 1225 m in length, following the same direction. The third scenario combined elements from the first and second scenarios. The fourth scenario focused on the NWBW, with a length of 5400 m. The fifth scenario was a combination of the first, second, and fourth scenarios. In contrast, the sixth scenario advocated for a deeper navigation channel, reaching a depth of 19 m. The seventh scenario emerged by combining

elements from the fifth and sixth scenarios. In scenario 8 or the actual case, the same measures will be taken as in scenario 7 but to accommodate more ships in the port, 670 m of the existing WBW will be demolished, forming a new basin between it and the NWBW, with a depth of 17 m.

Fig. 4.8. Proposed scenarios in CMS modeling.

4.4. Results and discussion

4.4.1 Shoreline analysis results

The findings of the present study of the Damietta coast are compiled in **Table 4.2** and are juxtaposed with previous research's results. Before the construction of the port in the late 1970s, the Damietta coast experienced significant erosion and accretion, with rates of -12.25 m/y and +4.82 m/y, respectively. After the establishment of the port and the WBW and EBW, the region west of the WBW exhibited a consistent pattern of accretion at varying rates in the period from 1985 to 2016. The average annual accretion rates were +13.60 m/y, +10.8 m/y, +10.11 m/y, and +5.51 m/y during the intermittent periods of 1985–1995, 1995–2000, 2000–2005, and 2005–2016, respectively.

During the building of the NWBW from 2021 to 2023, accretion was observed on the western side at an average rate of +17.22 m/y. Substantial coastal growth to the west of NWBW, presented an opportunity for the Egyptian government to develop this area by establishing a new tourist village that would benefit the Egyptian community. In contrast, **Fig. 4.9(a)** illustrates a mixed pattern of erosion and accretion between the NWBW and WBW, with average rates of -35.6 m/y and +56.55 m/y, respectively.

Between 1985 and 1995, the shoreline along the EBW experienced a substantial deterioration with an average retreat of -19.37 m/y. This erosion displayed notable continuity, persisting with subsequent average rates of -7.34 m/y, -7.6 m/y, and -3.65 m/y in subsequent periods. Following the extension of the EBW, the eastern region exhibited a combination of accretion and erosion during the 2020–2023 period, with an average accretion rate of +25.58 m/y and concurrent erosion at an average rate of -15.6 m/y.

In 2019, four Y-gs were constructed to address erosion concerns in the eastern part of the port. The analysis indicates that this area experienced erosion at an average rate of -2.7 m/y from 2005 to 2016 **Fig. 4.9(b)**. However, in the period from 2020 to 2023 (**Fig. 4.9(c)**), the erosion rate has slightly decreased to an average of -2.51 m/y. Moreover, in this recent period, accretion has been observed at an average rate of +5.43 m/y. The results of this study demonstrate that these groins have not been able to stop shoreline erosion.

Over the period from 1985 to 2023, the total areas undergoing erosion and accretion amounted to -1.36 km² and +2.21 km², respectively (see **Fig. 4.9(d)**). Examining annual erosion rates, we observe -0.11 km² (1977–1985), -0.40 km² (1985–2005), and -1.179 km² (2005–2023). Conversely, annual accretion rates varied, with the highest at +1.65 km² during 1985- 2005, followed by +1.29 km² (1977–1985) and +0.77 km² (2005–2023).

Fig. 4.9. Shoreline changes showing accretion and erosion patterns along DH coast: a) Shoreline changes between 2020- 2023, b) Shoreline changes between 2005- 2016, c) EPR rates along Damietta coast in the period of 2020-2023, d) Overall accretion and erosion areas from 1985- 2023.

Table 4.2. Results from the present study along the Damietta coast compared with the pervious works.

Works	Periods	DH				4 Y- gs		Extension of EBW	NWBW of port	
		Before const. m/yr		After const. Mean m/yr		Before Const. m/yr	After const. Mean m/yr	After const. Mean m/yr	Zone before NWBW m/yr	Zone between NWBW and WBW m/yr
		East	West	East	West					
The current study	1977-1980	-12.3	+4.82							
	1985-1995			-19.37	+13.6					
	1995-2000			-7.34	+10.8					

	2000-2005		-7.6	+10.11									
	2005-2016		-3.65	+5.51	-2.7	+1.4							
	2020-2023						-2.51	+5.43	-15.6	+25.58	+17.22	-35.6	+56.55
ElKotby et al., 2023	1985-2000				-17.4								
	2000-2010		-5.64	+10.7	-5.13								
	2010-2022		-4.12	+3.40			-2.31						
El-Asmar and Taha, 2022	1984-1987		+10.1	+13									
	1987-2015		-4.13	+12.4									
	2014-2022						-2405, -2626, -3076 m ² /yr.	+391, +432, +1253, +1765 m ² /yr					
Abou Samra and Ali, 2021	1984-2018			+15.2									
El-Gamal et al., 2020	1985-2015		-17.0										
Esmail et al., 2019	1990-1999		-9.0	+15.1									
	1999-2003		-4.50	+8.0									
	2003-2015		-1.75	+8.0									
Esmail et al., 2018	1990-1999		-10.0	+14.0									
	1999-2003		-10.0	+14.0									
	2003-2015		-3.0	+14.0									
El-Asmar et al., 2016	1984-1998		-7.43										
	1998-2003		-10.9										
	2003-2015		-3.11										
El-Asmar et al., 2014	1987-1991		-14.4										
	1991-2003		-9.5										
	2003-2006		-15.25										
	1984-2011		-9.95										
Dewidar and Frihy, 2010	1995-2005		-5.0	+10.0									

4.4.2 Numerical simulation results

4.4.2.1 The influence of designed scenarios on DH's navigation channel

The study assessed the impact of proposed solutions in DH, to mitigate the complex issue of sedimentation at the entrance. Utilizing hydrodynamics data from 2016 as the analytical foundation, the simulation yielded color-filled scalar maps illustrating morphological alterations at DH inlets over one year (see **Fig. 4.10**). The findings indicated sediment accumulation in the same locations, albeit in varying amounts across almost all scenarios. To delve deeper, four pivotal profiles, including one longitudinal section and three cross sections, were selected, and scrutinized along the navigable inlet (**Fig. 4.11**). The outcomes revealed all profiles exhibited alterations in the original cross-section due to the proposed scenarios, displaying a similar pattern.

The accumulation of sediments within the navigation channel experienced a minor increase in volume under the first scenario. This outcome stemmed from the prevailing long-shore current in the region, responsible for sediment transport originating from the northwest. Consequently, the extension of EBW led to a substantial entrapment of sediment, resulting in the channel's fill-up, as depicted in (**Fig. 4.11**- scenario 1). In the

second scenario, a significant rise in sedimentation within the navigation lane was observed compared to the initial solution. Despite expectations that this extension would curtail sedimentation by trapping sediment flowing along the shoreline from west to east, the formation of an eddy zone around the WBW tip resulted in the transport of sediment to the navigation channel (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 2). It is noted that the extension of the WBW in this way could lead to its collapse. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to make an inclination of the extension to maintain its stability. Results also indicated that modifying the WBW and EBW yielded barely worse change. The third scenario exhibited unfavorable results, allowing the largest amount of sediment to reach the navigation channel (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 3). Scenario 4 emerged as the most favorable among the presented options, significantly reducing sedimentation (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 4). This could be due to substantial sediment deposition upstream of NWBW extending behind the closure depth, where no sediment transports.

In scenario 5, the predicted amount of accumulated sediment was smaller than in scenario 4. The least amount of deposited silt at the port entrance was recorded in this scenario, making it the optimal choice (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 5). The volume of filled sediments in the navigation path rose significantly when it was deepened to 19 m (scenario 6). This was predicted since increasing the depth of the navigation lane reduces the speed of the currents that convey the sediments, causing them to settle and decreasing the proper depth for ships to navigate (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 6). The seventh situation is the same as the fifth scenario, except the waterway is now 19 m deep. Although sedimentation rates were somewhat higher in this scenario, the deeper waterway enables the handling of larger ships (**Fig. 4.11-** scenario 7). In scenario 8, the amount of accumulated sediment in the navigation path dramatically decreased (**Fig. 4.11-** Scenario 8).

Fig. 4.10. Explained a) Profile locations, and Morphology changes after one-year simulation for b) Benchmark case, c) Scenario 1, d) Scenario 2, e) Scenario 3, f) Scenario 4, g) Scenario 5, h) Scenario 6, j) Scenario 7, k) Scenario 8.

Fig. 4.11: Bed elevation inside DH inlet for three cross sections (a) Profile 1; (b) Profile 2; (c) Profile 3, and one longitudinal section (d) Profile 4.

The yearly estimated sedimentation volume in scenario 1 slightly rose from $17.12 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3$ in the benchmark scenario without intervention to $17.25 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3$ (see **Fig. 4.12**). Compared to the benchmark case, the yearly sediment volume in scenarios 2, and 3 increased notably by 16.18 %, 27.45 % respectively. Notably, scenarios 1, 2, and 3 did not exhibit a discernible role in effectively mitigating deposition at the harbor entrance. The yearly sediment volume decreased significantly in scenarios 4 and 5. It grew once again in scenario 6 to become about $20.11 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$. When the waterway was deepened, the seventh scenario's rate of increase was 21.75 % higher than that of scenario 5. In the ultimate case, the volume dramatically dropped once more, reaching $4.77 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$.

Fig. 4.12. A comparison of sediment volumes (m^3/y) in the navigation channel based on Benchmark and the designed scenarios.

In earlier studies, [Khalifa, 2017](#) investigated various scenarios to address the sedimentation issue at DH. He suggested creating a sediment trap, installing a current deflector wall, and extending the WBW. Using a sediment trap with the extension of the WBW resulted in an 84% reduction in sedimentation rate. However, it was noted that the sediment trap shifted the sedimentation area from the navigation channel to a specific area, necessitating ongoing dredging operations. [Masria et al., 2022](#) also pointed out several solutions including an extension of the WBW, a sediment trap on the western side, or the erection of groins surrounding the port. Lengthening the WBW was found to have little effect on sedimentation, and employing two groins on the port's western and eastern sides was predicted to reduce sedimentation by approximately 37.6%. Through our analysis using scenario 8, we were able to reduce the sediment volume by 72.1%, as indicated in **Table 4.3**.

Table 4.3. Results from current study for sediment volume in the navigation channel of DH for different scenarios compared to Benchmark case.

Scenarios	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	5 with 4Ygs	5 with 4Ygs and DBW	7 with 4Ygs	7 with 4Ygs and DBW
% Reduction in sediment volume	-0.75%	-16.17%	-27.4%	63.4%	70.7%	-17.5%	64.4%	72.1%	71.1%	71.7%	65.7%	65.4%

4.4.2.2 The influence of designed scenarios on adjacent beaches

Two profiles were presented in (Appendix III, Fig. C-14) on the western side of the port, strategically chosen to illustrate alterations along the shoreline, one taken before and one after the introduction of NWBW. The outcomes concluded that the impact of planned developments without NWBW implementation was marginal, emphasizing that NWBW is poised to induce a substantial change in the shoreline morphology.

Three profiles along the eastern side of the harbor are monitored as shown in (Appendix III, Fig. C-15). Across all proposed scenarios, profile 7 consistently displayed an accretion pattern. These observations can be attributed to the classification of the area behind the EBW as a shadow zone, where sediment transport is expected to significantly slow down, resulting in accretion. Conversely, profile 8 clearly illustrated coastal erosion. For Profile 9, all scenarios indicated a discernible increase in erosion, with Scenario 3 showing the most significant erosion rate.

4.4.2.3 The influence of deepening navigation channel on sedimentation problem

Maintaining the requisite depth in the navigation channel involves periodic dredging as a straightforward solution. This approach entails the removal of sediment accumulation within the waterway. Initially estimated by designers to be approximately 1.18 million m³ per year at the port's inception, the average annual dredging volume exceeded projections, reaching 2.0 million m³ annually (Ezzeldin et al., 2019). An annual expense of over 30 million LE goes into dredging and maintaining Damietta Port's navigational channel (Frihy et al., 2015). Here, this study explores the impact of deepening the navigation channel on sediment accumulation.

Five navigation depths were considered, ranging from 15m for the current depth to 19 m (future plan). The softer soil layers that emerged from deepening the navigation path necessitated a decrease in the Manning coefficients, (n) and average grain size diameter, d₅₀. For every depth, the morphological alterations were highlighted in Fig. 4.13(a: f). Every coastal engineering project must take into account the wide variations in nearshore wave characteristics, as reported by Shaltout and Tonbol, 2011. The distribution of wave energy in Fig. 4.13(g) indicated that rates are as low as predicted behind the DBW, on the western side of DH, and within the port's entrance.

Additionally, the yearly sediment volumes deposited in the navigation lane were computed (see **Fig. 4.14(A)**). Five profiles were acquired within the critical zone exhibiting the highest sediment concentration, as illustrated in **Fig. 4.14(b: f)**. The results indicate a proportional increase in sediment volume with the rise in navigational depth, primarily concentrated at the port entrance zone. At the current navigation depth of 15 m, the measured yearly sediment quantity was $4.30 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3$. Elevating the depth to 16 m, 17m, and 18m increased sediment volume by 12.83 %, 26.27%, and 33.42%, respectively compared to the existing situation. With the Egyptian government aiming for a depth of 19 m to accommodate larger ships and enhance waterway capacity and efficiency for trade and transportation, the annual sediment volumes increased by 41.96 %, reaching $6.10 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3$.

Fig. 4.13. Explained a) Profile location, Morphology changes for b) Current state 15 m deepening, c) 16 m deepening, d) 17 m deepening, e) 18 m deepening, f) Future-plan of 19 m deepening, g) Wave height distribution.

Fig. 4.14. Explained A) Sediment volume accumulation for each navigation depth m^3/y , b), c), d), e), f) Bed elevation in port entrance for five cross-section profiles of different navigation depth.

4.4.2.4 The influence of planned coastal structures at the eastern side of harbor.

This research offers valuable insights into the effects of DH development on its adjacent shorelines. Substantial and evident erosion rates were observed along the eastern shoreline of DH in the aftermath of simulating each scenario linked to the development plan. In a bid to capture sediments and fortify the beach, the Egyptian government contemplated the construction of four Y- g's in 2019, each measuring 170 m in length and spaced 400 m apart. East of these groins, there are plans to construct two new (DBW), each 250 m long and 230 m apart (see [Appendix III, Fig. C-16](#)). The crucial question is whether these structures will effectively fulfill their intended roles in halting erosion in this region. Additionally, it raises the query of whether the deepening of the navigation channel will

impact the morphology of the shoreline. **Fig. 4.15** depicted the proposed solutions in two navigation depths of 15 m and 19 m while morphology changes resulting from numerical simulation over one-year were displayed in **Fig. 4.16**.

Fig. 4.16(a, b) illustrates the erosion pattern on the western side of the four Y-gs, with an intervening accretion state observed between these proposed groins. However, east of the four Y-gs, an erosion pattern reemerged. It also appears that the effectiveness of the designed four Y-gs is not directly influenced by the depth of the navigation channel. After adding the new DBW, **Fig. 4.16(c, d)** depicted an accretion pattern in the shadow zone of the DBW. **Fig. 4.16(e)** explains the decrease in wave energy at Y-gs and behind DBW.

These simulation results are presented in ([Appendix III, Fig. C-17](#)), outlining the differences between the scenario with no action and the four studied cases of the coastal structures across four prescribed cross-sections. The findings lead to the conclusion that, despite their substantial construction costs, the structures designed for installation in this area did not fully achieve their intended purposes but could be useful if combined with a suitable nourishment system. According to **Table 3**, the erection of the 4Y-gs and new DBW have minimal impact on the sedimentation volume in DH.

Fig. 4.15. Proposed scenarios at the eastern side of port.

Fig. 4.16. Morphology changes for a) 4 Y gs only east of harbor at 15 m deepening, b) 4 Y gs only at 19 m deepening, c) 4 Y gs + DBW at 15 m deepening, d) 4 Y gs + DBW at 19 m deepening, e) Wave distribution at planned coastal structures.

2.5 Conclusion

The significant depth of the navigational channel and the high cost associated with sediment removal are pivotal factors contributing to the sedimentation challenge at DH, impacting the required mooring depth for vessels. Since 2019, the Egyptian government has been implementing a study plan to make improvements to the port to tackle the sedimentation problem. But the nearby beaches were also visibly impacted by this development. Initially, the changes in the shoreline resulting from the improvements implemented in DH, namely the extension of the EBW in addition to the NBBW, were investigated using RS and DSAS. Between 2020 and 2023, there was a dominating rate of accretion in the area west of the NBBW (+17.22 m/y), whereas there were two distinct rates of erosion and accretion in the area between the NBBW and the port (-35.6 m/y and +56.55 m/y, respectively). An advance of the coastline emerged when the EBW was extended, at an average pace of +25.58 m/y. The Egyptian government implemented 4 Y-

gs in 2019 to address the severe issue of beach erosion east of the port, however, these facilities were insufficient to stop the erosion. Next, using a CMS, the team designed a set of scenarios that closely mimicked reality and ran a simulation to display the morphological changes associated with each scenario. The simulations show that scenario 8 outperformed the other scenarios and contributed an annual sediment volume of 72.1 % less than the benchmark case into the entrance area. After discussing the impact of deepening the navigation channel on the volume of deposited sediments, it turned out that the volume of sedimentation increased with channel depth. The authors also observed a minor improvement in the predicted beachline with the building of four Y-gs and two new DBW, but erosion still occurs, demonstrating the inefficiency of these facilities. The overview of the morpho-dynamic mechanisms in DH provided by the current study will help stakeholders and coastal management address the harbor's issues more effectively. It is recommended that the Egyptian government perform cost analysis and economic studies concerning scenario 8 and compare them with the dredging expenses. Tracking long-term siltation rates inside the harbor is also essential for gaining a more profound understanding of sediment movement dynamics. Additionally, to mitigate excessive erosion on the eastern side of DH, the Egyptian government should incorporate both hard and soft protection approaches.

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Chapter (5)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CHAPTER (5)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMCONCLUSION

5.1 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Major alterations to the shoreline of the Nile Delta are being driven by both natural and human-induced processes. These shifts have been exacerbated by human actions like as agriculture, urbanization, and dam building, which have raised the rates of corrosion and deposition. The rates of eroding and accretion were measured over 37 years over a 324-kilometer section of the coastline of the Nile Delta. The Linear Regression Rate (LRR) model was put to use to figure out shoreline changes after 4,050 transects were cast perpendicular to the digital shorelines using "DSAS" software as the analytical tool.

The conclusion for this analysis is drawn in to

- 1- The following locations had notably high rates of erosion: Burullus headland (-11.07 m/y), Damietta headland (-45.4 m/y), and Rosetta headland (-37.2 m/y).
- 2- During the long-term phase, the Gamasa embayment (+37.2 m/y), the Alexandria coast (+25.8 m/y), and portions of the Port Said coast (+36.9 m/y), especially in the vicinity of the El-Gamil inlets displayed the greatest accretion rates.
- 3- The 2016 installation of a new groin protection system had no effect on erosion on the Rosetta headland's eastern side. Eight groins between the GFF's intake and exit reduced levels of erosion from -29.3 m/y (2000–2010) to -18.3 m/y (2010–2022). Even after the installation of eight more groins on the outlet's eastern side, erosion continued to occur between 2010 and 2022 at an average rate of -12.3 m/y.
5. To minimize continued erosion, Y-shaped groins were built on the eastern side of the Damietta Port in 2019. This helped to marginally lower the rate, which was -2.31 m/y on average between 2010 and 2022.

6. In 2016, five groins were built close to the first El-Gamil inlet's western side, raising the accretion rates from 7.9 m/y (2000–2010) to 11.05 m/y (2010–2022).

7. Shoreline positions projected for 2030, 2050, and 2100 show that past patterns of change are probably going to continue at comparable rates in the years to come.

Climate change and sea level rise are also predicted to have a greater impact on the shoreline of the Nile Delta in the years to come. One of the most important tasks for effective coastal conservation in Egypt is examining how the shoreline of the Nile River Delta has changed in response to climate change and sea level rise, as well as determining the most vulnerable and hotspot locations. Thirteen geological, physical, and social factors were assessed to decide the level of vulnerability of the Egyptian Delta shoreline. Using two different approaches—the "analytical hierarchy process (AHP)" and the "Gornitz's" approach—the rank for each parameter was integrated to generate the coastal vulnerability index, or "CVI."

The conclusion for these findings is figured in to

1- The "CVI " values obtained using "Gornitz's" technique ranged from 8.32 to 1248.075, whereas the "AHP" method yielded values ranging from 2.176 to 4.499.

2- The western portion of Abu-Qir Bay, Rosetta Headland, Abo-Khashba Bay, Damietta Headland, and other sectors along the Port Said coast were identified as five extremely hazardous coastal locations by "CVI" calculations using "Gornitz's" technique.

3- The results of the "AHP" model show a high degree of vulnerability, with very high vulnerability (4.499–3.8) and high vulnerability (3.8–3.593) concentrated within regions like the eastern side of Damietta, the western sector of Alexandria, Abu-Qir Bay, the majority of Abo-Khashba Bay, and some sectors of the Port Said coast. The eastern edge of Alexandria, Burullus Headland, and Gamasa Bay are among the areas with moderate (3.598–3.398), low (3.398–3.17), and very low (3.17–2.016) susceptibility.

4- Elevation, significant wave height, and the existence of coastal facilities were the variables with the greatest weights in the vulnerability examination, as determined by the "AHP" approach.

5- More than half of the coast of the Nile Delta is exposed to very high to moderate risk levels due to a combination of factors such as 85% low lying land, 61.7% mild coastal slope, 68% lower bathymetric slope, 44.15% eroded shoreline, 75% sea level rise, 57.8% land subsidence, 95.97% lack of effective coastal projects, 32.08% proximity of urbanization to the coast, and 92.63% land use.

The considerable depth of the navigating channel and the expensive cost of silt removal affect the required docking depth for vessels. These are significant factors that add to the problem of sedimentation. Siltation is a major issue at Damietta Port, which has an adverse influence on the efficiency and operation of the port. The Egyptian government began implementing a well-thought-out plan to modernize the port in 2019 to alleviate the sedimentation problem. But the nearby beaches were also significantly impacted by this expansion. Using a coastal modeling system "CMS", the researchers developed a number of realistic scenarios. They then utilized a one-year simulation to illustrate the morphological changes associated with each scenario.

The conclusion for this simulation is plugged in to

1- At comparison to the Benchmark case at the entry region, Scenario 8 reduced the yearly sediment amount by 72.1%, according to the simulations, exceeding all other scenarios.

2. It was discovered that the sedimentation quantity rose with increasing channel depth after assessing the effect of deepening the navigation channel on the accumulation of sediment. West of the port, considerable accretion was also seen, especially following the NWBW's installation.

3. Although the installation of four Y-groins and two new detached breakwaters (DBW) resulted in a little improvement in the anticipated beachline, erosion persists, underscoring the ineffectiveness of these expensive structures.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS:

The following recommendations are required to more completely describe for proposed models:

1- Looking at alternate coastline protection strategies that could end up being more economical and ecologically friendly.

2- Creating a comprehensive coast management strategy to address the risks discovered in designated areas. This strategy should include measures like replenishing beaches, land use planning, coastline preservation, and community involvement to boost resilience to coastal hazards including erosion, floods, and sea level rise.

3- Applying of vulnerability assessment using machine learning techniques where they allow for a more advanced and accurate analysis of coastal risks. This approach helps in automating the assessment process and improving decision-making by providing more reliable predictions of areas at risk, based on historical data and real-time environmental factors.

4- Evaluating coastal structure designs before construction by utilizing simulation models. Before construction begins, designers can make the required adjustments to their plans in order to identify any shortcomings or potential areas for improvement. In the end, this can lead to a more robust and cost-effective final product by lowering the risks and uncertainties associated with coastal building.

5- Doing economic research and cost analysis related to scenario 8 and contrasting it with the dredging costs.

6- Tracking long-term siltation rates inside the harbor is also essential for gaining a more profound understanding of sediment movement dynamics.

Appendix I for the first research

To cover total study area in single scene image, various Landsat images for all selected dates have been mosaicked by using ENVI v.5.3 software.

Because of the missing data problem in the scan line corrector SLC-off Landsat-7 ETM+ image, the segmentation process was backed by a simple Landsat gap-fill extension added to ENVI software to compensate for the missing data. This procedure was carried out by filling gabs in one scene with data from another one.

Fig. A-1) Landsat images (TM, ETM, OLI) for overall study area

The observations for EPR and LRR models revealed minimal differences for the intermediate periods 1985-2000, 2000-2010, and 2010-2022.

Fig. A-2) Shoreline changes rates LRR and EPR along study area for all studied periods.

Fig. A.3 Shoreline changes along zone 1 through intermitted periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.4 Shoreline changes along zone 2 through intermitted periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.5 Shoreline changes along zone 3 through intermitted periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.6 Shoreline changes along zone 4 through intermittent periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.7 Shoreline changes along zone 5 through intermittent periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.8 Shoreline changes along zone 6 through intermittent periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.9 Shoreline changes along zone 7 through intermitted periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Fig. A.10 Shoreline changes along zone 8 through intermitted periods a)1985-2000, b)2000-2010, c) 2010-2022. d) 1985-2022

Appendix II for the second research

- **Data used in evaluating vulnerability for Nile Delta coast.**

Fig. B-1) Annually data observed for sea level rise at A) Alexandria station (PSMSL Website), B) Burullus (Akary et al., 2007), and C) Port-said station (PSMSL Website).

Fig. B-2) Distribution of wave direction at Damietta coast

Fig. B-3) Distribution of wave height at Damietta coast

```

from windrose import WindroseAxes

df=pd.read_csv('ElBrullus.csv')
print(df)
##df['Hs_x']=df['Hs']*np.sin(df['DIR']*pi/180.0)
##df['Hs_y']=df['Hs']*np.cos(df['DIR']*pi/180.0)
fig, ax=plt.subplots(figsize=(8,8))
##x0, x1=ax.get_xlim()
##y0, y1=ax.get_ylim()
##ax.set_aspect('equal')
##df.plot(kind='scatter', x='Hs_x', y='Hs_y', alpha=0.35, ax=ax)
##plt.show()
df.dropna()
print(df.dtypes)
ax=WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(df['Wind direction (from ?N)'], df['Hs'], normed=True, opening= 0.6, edgecolor='white')
ax.set_legend()
plt.show()

ax=WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.box(df['Wind direction (from ?N)'], df['Hs'] , normed=True, bins=np.arange(0.01,8,1))
ax.set_legend()
plt.show()

ax=WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.contourf(df['Wind direction (from ?N)'], df['Hs'] , normed=True, bins=np.arange(0.01,8,1), cmap=cm.hot, lw=3)
ax.set_legend()
plt.show()

```

Fig. B-4) Coding for wave rose drawing using python language.

- **For Setting Land Use Land Cover map**

Accuracy assessment:

Accuracy assessment can be defined as a comparison of a map produced from remotely sensed data with another map from some other source. Used to assess the land cover land use mapping.

Table B-1) Summary of Accuracy and error of land use classification by using google Earth.

	Waterbody	Fish-farm	Urban area	Agriculture land	Wetland	Sand	Total	commission Accuracy %	User Accuracy
Waterbody	15	0	0	0	0	0	15	0.0	100.0
Fish-farm	1	7	1	9	1	1	20	65.0	35.0
Urban area	1	1	45	4	1	2	54	16.7	83.3
Agriculture land	1	1	1	125	0	2	130	3.8	96.2
Wetland	4	3	0	0	16	0	23	30.4	69.6
Sand	0	0	1	3	0	19	23	17.4	82.6
Total	22	12	48	141	18	24	265		
producer Accuracy %	68.2	58.3	93.8	88.7	88.9	79.2			
omission Accuracy %	31.8	41.7	6.3	11.3	11.1	20.8			

- Overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient is determined from the error matrix and Eqs. B-1, B-2 as shown:

Overall Accuracy = [total no. of correctly classified pixels/ total no. of referenced pixel] *100%,Eq. B-1

$$= (15+7+45+125+16+19)/265 *100% = 85.66%$$

- **User Accuracy = no. of correctly classified pixels in each category/ total no. of classified pixel in that category (row total)] *100%**

Waterbody=15/15*100%=100%

Fish-farm=7/20*100=35%

Urban area=45/54*100= 83.3%

Agriculture land=96.2%

Wetland=69.6%

Sand=82.6%

- **Producer Accuracy = no. of correctly classified pixels in each category/ total no. of classified pixel in that category (column total)] *100%**

Waterbody=15/22=68.2%

Fish-farm=7/12*100=58.3%

Urban area=45/48*100= 93.8%

Agriculture land=88.7%

Wetland=88.9%

Sand=79.2%

Kappa coefficient = $[(Ts * Tcs) - \sum row\ total - \sum column\ total]/[Ts^2 - \sum column\ total - row\ total]$ Eq. B-2

= $[(265*227) - (15*22+20*12+54*48+130*141+23*18+23*24)] / [(265^2) - (15*22+20*12+54*48+130*141+23*18+23*24)] = 37697/ 47767 = 78.92%$

Where, Ts: total no. of referenced pixel, TCS: total no. of correctly classified pixels

- **Analytical hierarchy process steps**

1- Pairwise Comparison matrix

Table B-2) Comparison matrix in AHP method

	Geomorphology	Elevation	Coastal slope	Bathymetry	Shore-line change	Significant wave height	Sea level change	Tidal range	Distance to urban	Wave direction	Artificial structures	Land subsidence	LULC
Geomorphology	1												
Elevation	7	1											
Coastal slope	3	0.33	1										
Bathymetry	3	0.5	0.5	1									
Shore-line change	3	0.2	0.5	0.5	1								
Significant wave height	5	2	2	0.5	0.5	1							
Sea level change	3	0.2	0.33	0.5	0.33	0.33	1						
Tidal range	0.2	0.125	0.33	0.5	0.25	0.2	0.5	1					

Distance to urban	2	0.33	3	3	1	0.33	3	2	1				
Wave direction	2	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.33	0.33	2	2	0.5	1			
Artificial structures	7	0.5	5	5	5	2	5	6	3	4	1		
Land subsidence	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.33	0.33	0.2	2	2	0.33	1	0.2	1	
LULC	2	0.33	0.5	0.5	0.33	0.33	3	2	0.33	3	0.2	3	1
sum	38.7	6.1	17.5	16.66	18.4	9.92	32.83	44	14.15	27.5	5.59	34	23.99

2- Normalized matrix to estimate criteria weight

Table B-3) Normalized matrix and criteria weight

	Geomorphology	Elevation	Coastal slope	Bathymetry	Shore-line change	Significant wave height	Sea level change	Tidal range	Beach width	Wave direction	Artificial structures	Land subsidence	LULC	Sum	Criteria weight)
Geomorphology	0.026	0.023	0.019	0.020	0.018	0.020	0.010	0.114	0.035	0.018	0.025	0.059	0.021	0.408	0.031
Elevation	0.181	0.165	0.172	0.120	0.272	0.050	0.152	0.182	0.212	0.182	0.358	0.147	0.125	2.318	0.178
Coastal slope	0.078	0.055	0.057	0.120	0.109	0.050	0.091	0.068	0.023	0.073	0.036	0.059	0.083	0.902	0.069
Bathymetry	0.078	0.083	0.029	0.060	0.109	0.202	0.061	0.045	0.023	0.073	0.036	0.088	0.083	0.969	0.075
Shore-line change	0.078	0.033	0.029	0.030	0.054	0.202	0.091	0.091	0.071	0.109	0.036	0.088	0.125	1.036	0.080
Significant wave height	0.129	0.330	0.114	0.030	0.027	0.101	0.091	0.114	0.212	0.109	0.089	0.147	0.125	1.620	0.125
Sea level change	0.078	0.033	0.019	0.030	0.018	0.033	0.030	0.045	0.023	0.018	0.036	0.015	0.014	0.392	0.030
Tidal range	0.005	0.021	0.019	0.030	0.014	0.020	0.015	0.023	0.035	0.018	0.030	0.015	0.021	0.266	0.020
Beach width	0.052	0.055	0.172	0.180	0.054	0.033	0.091	0.045	0.071	0.073	0.059	0.088	0.125	1.098	0.084
Wave direction	0.052	0.033	0.029	0.030	0.018	0.033	0.061	0.045	0.035	0.036	0.045	0.029	0.014	0.460	0.035
Artificial structures	0.181	0.083	0.286	0.300	0.272	0.202	0.152	0.136	0.212	0.145	0.179	0.147	0.208	2.503	0.193
Land subsidence	0.013	0.033	0.029	0.020	0.018	0.020	0.061	0.045	0.023	0.036	0.036	0.029	0.014	0.377	0.029
LULC	0.052	0.055	0.029	0.030	0.018	0.033	0.091	0.045	0.023	0.109	0.036	0.088	0.042	0.651	0.050

3- Computing consistency index

To check consistency of comparison matrix.

Table B-4) Matrix to calculate λ_{\max}

	Geomorphology	Elevation	Coastal slope	Bathymetry	Shore-line change	Significant wave height	Sea level change	Tidal range	Beach width	Wave direction	Artificial structures	Land subsidence	LULC	weighted sum	weighted sum/criteria
Geomorphology	0.031	0.025	0.023	0.025	0.026	0.025	0.010	0.102	0.042	0.018	0.027	0.058	0.025	0.437	13.944
Elevation	0.220	0.178	0.208	0.149	0.399	0.062	0.151	0.164	0.253	0.177	0.385	0.145	0.150	2.641	14.816
Coastal slope	0.094	0.059	0.069	0.149	0.159	0.062	0.091	0.061	0.028	0.071	0.039	0.058	0.100	1.040	14.995
Bathymetry	0.094	0.089	0.035	0.075	0.159	0.249	0.060	0.041	0.028	0.071	0.039	0.087	0.100	1.127	15.119
Shoreline change	0.094	0.036	0.035	0.037	0.080	0.249	0.091	0.082	0.084	0.106	0.039	0.087	0.150	1.169	14.671
Significant wave height	0.157	0.357	0.139	0.037	0.040	0.125	0.091	0.102	0.253	0.106	0.096	0.145	0.150	1.798	14.432
Sea level change	0.094	0.036	0.023	0.037	0.026	0.041	0.030	0.041	0.028	0.018	0.039	0.015	0.017	0.444	14.698
Tidal range	0.006	0.022	0.023	0.037	0.020	0.025	0.015	0.020	0.042	0.018	0.033	0.015	0.025	0.301	14.733
Beach width	0.063	0.059	0.208	0.224	0.080	0.041	0.091	0.041	0.084	0.071	0.064	0.087	0.150	1.262	14.939
Wave direction	0.063	0.036	0.035	0.037	0.026	0.041	0.060	0.041	0.042	0.035	0.048	0.029	0.017	0.510	14.408
Artificial structures	0.220	0.089	0.347	0.373	0.399	0.249	0.151	0.123	0.253	0.142	0.193	0.145	0.250	2.933	15.229
Land subsidence	0.016	0.036	0.035	0.025	0.026	0.025	0.060	0.041	0.028	0.035	0.039	0.029	0.017	0.410	14.137
LULC	0.063	0.059	0.035	0.037	0.026	0.041	0.091	0.041	0.028	0.106	0.039	0.087	0.050	0.702	14.023
sum	1.214	1.079	1.213	1.242	1.467	1.236	0.991	0.900	1.195	0.974	1.076	0.987	1.201		
														λ_{\max}	14.626

Appendix III for the Third research

- Calibration process in numerical modelling (CMS model):**
 Utilizing the bathymetric survey data from 2016, adjusting model parameters(manning coefficient n (0.04, 0.025, 0.01), bed or suspended scaling factor S (0.5, 1, 2), bed adaption length L_b (5, 10, 20), sediment formulas (LundCirp, VanRijn, Watanabe), time step (600, 450, 300)) and predicting for bottom evolution in 2017 to match with measured bed elevation at 3 profiles located at the eastern side of Damietta harbor.

Fig C-1) Comparison between manning coefficient at $T = 450s$, bed and suspended scaling factor $S = 2$, bed adaption length $L_b = 20$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 1

Fig C-2) Comparison between bed adaption length L_b at bed and suspended scaling factor $S = 20$, $T = 450s$, $n = 0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 1

Fig C-3) Comparison between bed and suspended scaling factor S at bed adaption length $L_b = 20$, $T = 450s$, $n = 0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 1

Fig C-4) Comparison between sediment formula at bed and suspended scaling factor $S=2$, bed adaption length $L_b=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$ for profile 1

Fig C-5) Comparison between manning coefficient at $T=450s$, bed and suspended scaling factor $S=2$, bed adaption length $L_b=20$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 2

Fig C-6) Comparison between bed adaption length L_b at bed and suspended scaling factor $S=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 2

Fig C-7) Comparison between bed and suspended scaling factor S at bed adaption length $L_b=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for profile 2

Fig C-8) Comparison between **sediment formula** at bed and suspended scaling factor $S=2$, bed adaption length $L_b=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$ for **profile 2**

Fig C-9) Comparison between **manning coefficient** at $T=450s$, bed and suspended scaling factor $S=2$, bed adaption length $L_b=20$, sediment formula VanRijn for **profile 3**

Fig C-10) Comparison between **bed adaption length L_b** at bed and suspended scaling factor $S=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for **profile 3**

Fig C-11) Comparison between **bed and suspended scaling factor S** at bed adaption length $L_b=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$, sediment formula VanRijn for **profile 3**

Fig C-12) Comparison between sediment formula at bed and suspended scaling factor $S=2$, bed adaption length $L_b=20$, $T=450s$, $n=0.01$ for profile 3

Continued calibration process:

Fig C-13): Bed elevation at the different model parameters for profile 1 and profile 2, profile 3

- Sediment accumulated in navigation channel with different scenarios and % Reduction.

Table C-1) Quantification results of the annual sediment volumes at the entrance for all scenarios and the corresponding percentages of sedimentation reduction in DH.

Scenarios	Sediment volumes at the entrance			Reduction %
	$V_{in} (m^3/y)$	$V_{out} (m^3/y)$	$V_{net} = V_{in} - V_{out} (m^3/y)$	
Benchmark	+1713406	-1485	+1711921	-
Scenario 1	+1726068	-1261	+1724807	- 0.75%
Scenario 2	+1989267	-397	+1988870	- 16.18%
Scenario 3	+2181959	-198	+2181761	- 27.45%
Scenario 4	+630065	-4526	+625538	63.46%
Scenario 5	+502088	-1071	+501017	70.73%
Scenario 6	+1336115	-1184.61	+1334931	22.02%
Scenario 7	+612158	-1816	+610342	64.35%
Scenario 8	+478074	-985	+477089	72.1%

- Results of numerical modelling for bed evolution around Damietta harbor

Fig. C-14 Bed elevation at the western side of DH for (a) profile 5; (b) profile 6.

Fig. C-15) Bed elevation at the eastern side of DH before planned coastal protection for (a) profile 7; (b) profile 8, (c) profile 9.

Fig. C-16) Location of new planned DBW.

Fig. C-17) Bed elevation at the eastern side of the DH due to planned coastal structures for a) profile 1, b) profile 2, c) profile 3, d) profile 4.

الملخص العربي،

تطبيق الاستشعار عن بعد والنمذجة المورفولوجية في التحكم بمشاكل المنطقة الساحلية.

مقدمة:

يعد التآكل الساحلي أحد أبرز التحديات البيئية التي تواجه السواحل العالمية، حيث يؤثر بشكل مباشر على البنية التحتية، الأنشطة الاقتصادية، والأنظمة البيئية الساحلية. وتعود هذه الظاهرة إلى مجموعة من العوامل الطبيعية والبشرية، والتي تشمل ارتفاع مستوى سطح البحر، التغيرات المناخية، التيارات البحرية، الأمواج العاتية، والتدخلات البشرية مثل إنشاء السدود والموانئ التي تؤثر على حركة الرواسب الساحلية وتعزز معدلات التآكل.

في دلتا النيل، وهي من أكثر المناطق كثافة سكانية وازدهارًا في مصر، تشكل التغيرات الساحلية المتسارعة تهديدًا بيئيًا واقتصاديًا كبيرًا. فقد شهدت المنطقة خلال العقود الماضية تحولات ملحوظة في خط الساحل، نتيجة اضطرابات في حركة الرواسب، والأنشطة البشرية، لا سيما إنشاء السدود على امتداد نهر النيل. كان للسد العالي في أسوان تأثير جوهري في تقليل التدفق الطبيعي للرواسب إلى الدلتا، والتي كانت تلعب دورًا حيويًا في تجديد المناطق الساحلية والحد من التآكل. ونتيجة لهذا التغير، تعرضت العديد من المناطق الساحلية، خاصة على امتداد فرعي دمياط ورشيد، إلى تآكل متسارع، مما يشكل خطرًا على المجتمعات المحلية، البنية التحتية، والأراضي الزراعية المحيطة.

لدراسة هذه الظاهرة، تم تطبيق نظام تحليل خط الشاطئ الرقمي (DSAS) مع نظم المعلومات الجغرافية (GIS) في منطقة الدلتا، والذي يعتمد على تحليل الصور الفضائية والبيانات الزمنية لتقييم معدلات التآكل والتغيرات الساحلية. وقد كشفت النتائج عن معدلات تآكل مرتفعة في ثلاث مناطق رئيسية، حيث بلغ معدل التآكل السنوي في منطقة رشيد 37.2 مترًا، وفي منطقة البرلس 11.07 مترًا، بينما سجلت منطقة دمياط أعلى معدل تآكل بلغ 45.4 مترًا سنويًا.

يؤدي التغير المناخي إلى تفاقم معدلات تآكل خط الساحل في دلتا النيل من خلال ارتفاع مستوى سطح البحر وزيادة حدة العواصف البحرية. ومن هنا، تصبح تقييمات المخاطر الساحلية أمرًا ضروريًا لضمان استدامة الدلتا على المدى الطويل. تساهم هذه التقييمات في تحديد المناطق الأكثر عرضة للخطر من خلال تحليل مجموعة من العوامل الجيولوجية والفيزيائية والاجتماعية والاقتصادية مثل: الجيومورفولوجية، مناسيب الأراضي، الميل الساحلي، قياسات الأعماق البحرية، تغير خط الساحل، ارتفاع الموجة، نطاق المد والجزر، تغير مستوى سطح البحر، الهبوط الأرضي، اتجاه الموجة، المنشآت الحماية الساحلية، استخدام الأراضي، والمسافة إلى المناطق الحضرية. تتيح هذه التحليلات بيانات دقيقة لصانعي القرار لمساعدتهم في وضع إجراءات استباقية للتكيف مع هذه التحديات.

تم تقدير مؤشر خطورة الساحل (CVI) من خلال دمج درجات المخاطر للعوامل المختلفة باستخدام نهجين: نهج Gornitz وعملية التسلسل الهرمي التحليلي (AHP). يعتمد نهج Gornitz على توحيد أوزان العوامل المختلفة لتقييم مخاطر المناطق الساحلية أمام ارتفاع مستوى سطح البحر (SLR). أما نموذج AHP، فيوفر تحليلاً أكثر شمولية ومنهجية لاتخاذ القرارات، حيث يجمع بين آراء الخبراء وتحويل البيانات النوعية إلى قيم كمية، مما يتيح ترتيب العوامل حسب تأثيرها على المخاطر الساحلية. أيضا يتيح AHP تقييماً أكثر دقة لمخاطر السواحل، مما يساعد في تحديد المناطق ذات الأولوية لاتخاذ التدابير اللازمة.

كشفت النتائج المستندة إلى نموذج AHP أن حوالي 128 كيلومتراً (40% من خط الساحل) تقع ضمن منطقة عالية إلى عالية جداً من حيث الخطورة، وتتركز في مواقع مثل:

- خليج أبو خشبة (75%)
- خليج أبو قير ورأس رشيد (48%)
- القطاع الغربي من الإسكندرية (25%)

تساهم النمذجة العددية، مثل نظام نمذجة السواحل (CMS)، في تحليل كيفية نقل الرواسب، وتطور خط الساحل، وتقييم تأثير المنشآت الساحلية، خاصة في المواقع الحيوية مثل ميناء دمياط. يوفر هذا النموذج رؤى دقيقة حول تأثير التغييرات المستقبلية على الميناء والسواحل المجاورة من خلال محاكاة سيناريوهات مختلفة لخطط التنمية الحكومية.

تم التحقق من ثمانية سيناريوهات في هذه الدراسة، شملت: تعميق قناة الملاحة، إنشاء حاجز أمواج جديد في المنطقة غرب الميناء، تمديد الحواجز الشرقية والغربية.

أظهرت النتائج تحليل كميات الرواسب في قناة الملاحة بميناء دمياط، ومدى تأثيرها على الشواطئ المجاورة. وقد تبين أن السيناريو الثامن، الذي يمثل التخطيط المستقبلي للميناء، كان الأكثر كفاءة، حيث ساهم في تقليل الترسبات السنوية بنسبة 72.1% مقارنة بالحالة المرجعية في منطقة المدخل.

من خلال دمج النمذجة العددية مع تقييمات درجة الخطورة الساحلية، يمكن لصناع القرار وضع سياسات فعالة لإدارة السواحل، مما يضمن حماية دلتا النيل على المدى الطويل من التحديات الناتجة عن تغير المناخ والأنشطة البشرية.

[محتويات الدراسة:](#)

[تتكون الرسالة من خمسة أبواب ملحق موزعة على النحو التالي:](#)

[الفصل الأول: المقدمة](#)

يقدم مقدمة عامة للدراسة مع مراجعة بسيطة وتحديد الهدف من البحث.

الفصل الثاني: "تقييم تأثير التدخلات البشرية على تغيرات خط الشاطئ على طول دلتا النيل، مصر"

يعرض تحليلاً لتغيرات خط الشاطئ في منطقة دلتا النيل باستخدام أداة DSAS في الفترة من 1985 إلى 2022.

الفصل الثالث: "تقييم المخاطر الساحلية نتيجة ارتفاع مستوى سطح البحر: دراسة حالة لساحل دلتا النيل"

يقدم تقييمًا شاملاً للخطر على طول خط شاطئ دلتا النيل باستخدام طريقتين: طريقة Gornitz وطريقة AHP وعمل مقارنة بين الطريقتين.

الفصل الرابع: "تقييم تأثير خطط التطوير في الموانئ المصرية على التغيرات المورفولوجية باستخدام المحاكاة العددية (دراسة حالة: ميناء دمياط، الساحل الشمالي الشرقي لمصر)"

يقدم تقديرات لحجم الترسبات في ميناء دمياط بعد تنفيذ خطط التطوير للميناء باستخدام النموذج العددي CMS.

الفصل الخامس: الخلاصات والتوصيات

يعرض ملخصًا للرسالة والخلاصات والتوصيات للأبحاث المستقبلية.

ملحق 1 يحتوي على نتائج خاصة بالبحث الأول

ملحق 2 يحتوي على بيانات استخدمت في عملية التقييم، خطوات عمل خريطة استخدام الأراضي وخطوات تطبيق طريقة AHP.

ملحق 3 يحتوي على نتائج عملية المعايرة للنموذج الرقمي ونتائج أخرى لشكل مورفولوجية القاع عند الجانب الغربي والشرقي من ميناء دمياط.

من خلال تحليل ومناقشة نتائج الدراسة يمكن أن نوصي ب:

1- دراسة استراتيجيات بديلة لحماية الساحل قد تكون أكثر اقتصادية وصديقة للبيئة، مما يساهم في تعزيز استدامة النظم الساحلية وتقليل التأثيرات السلبية للمشروعات الهندسية التقليدية.

2- استخدام خوارزميات التعلم العميق (Deep Learning) والشبكات العصبية الاصطناعية (ANNs) لتحليل التغيرات في خط الشاطئ والتنبؤ بالمخاطر الساحلية.

3- تطوير استراتيجية شاملة لإدارة المناطق الساحلية لمعالجة المخاطر المكتشفة في المناطق المحددة. ينبغي أن تتضمن هذه الاستراتيجية إجراءات مثل تغذية الشواطئ، تخطيط استخدام الأراضي، الحفاظ على الخط الساحلي، وتعزيز مشاركة المجتمع المحلي، وذلك لتعزيز القدرة على التكيف مع المخاطر الساحلية مثل التآكل، الفيضانات، وارتفاع مستوى سطح البحر.

4- تطبيق تقييم الضعف الساحلي باستخدام تقنيات الذكاء الاصطناعي والتعلم الآلي (machine learning and Artificial intelligence)، حيث يتيح هذا النهج تحليلاً أكثر دقة وتطوراً للمخاطر الساحلية. كما يساعد في أتمتة

- عملية التقييم وتحسين عملية صنع القرار من خلال توفير تنبؤات أكثر موثوقية بشأن المناطق المعرضة للخطر، وذلك بالاعتماد على البيانات التاريخية والعوامل البيئية في الوقت الفعلي.
- 5- إجراء دراسة اقتصادية وتحليل تكاليف السيناريو 8، ومقارنته بتكاليف أعمال التجريف لتحديد الجدوى الاقتصادية والفعالية المالية لكل خيار.
- 6- مراقبة معدلات الترسيب طويلة الأجل داخل الميناء تُعد أمرًا ضروريًا لفهم أكثر عمقًا لديناميكيات حركة الرواسب، مما يساعد في تحسين استراتيجيات الصيانة وإدارة العمليات الساحلية بكفاءة أعلى.
- 7- استكشاف تقنيات Optimization (e.g., Genetic Algorithms, Multi-Objective Optimization) لتصميم سيناريوهات فعالة لإدارة الرواسب، تهدف إلى تقليل تكاليف التجريف والتأثيرات البيئية.
- 8- دمج سيناريوهات تغير المناخ (مثل توقعات الهيئة الحكومية الدولية المعنية بتغير المناخ IPCC) في النموذج العددي للتنبؤ بتكوينات خط الشاطئ المستقبلية.

إقرار

تقر الباحثة \ مي رمضان عبد الحلیم الكتبی بالالتزام بقوانين جامعة المنصورة وأنظمتها وتعليماتها وقراراتها السارية المفعول المتعلقة بإعداد رسائل دكتوراة الفلسفة في العلوم الهندسية عندما قامت بإعداد رسالة الدكتوراة بعنوان:

"Applying Remote Sensing And Morphological Modeling In Controlling Coastal Zone Problems"

كجزء من متطلبات الحصول على درجة الدكتوراة الفلسفة في العلوم الهندسية في الهندسة (قسم الري والهيدروليكا) والإقرار بجدائة موضوع الدراسة البحثية وانه لم يسبق دراسة الموضوع والعنوان البحثي بصورته النهائية الكاملة او نشره سابقا في أي رسائل، او كتب، او اطروحات، او أبحاث، او أي منشورات بحثية ذلك بما ينسجم مع الأمانة العلمية المتعارف عليها في كتابة الرسائل او الاطروحات العلمية.

تحت اشراف

أ.م.د ثروت عيد سرحان

أ.د. محمود الجمل

وتم نشر ثلاثة أبحاث في مجلات محكمة ومتخصصة وهم:

1 - ElKotby, M.R., Sarhan, T.A. and El-Gamal, M., 2023. Assessment of human interventions presence and their impact on shoreline changes along Nile delta, Egypt. *Oceanologia*, 65(4),

595-611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2023.06.008>

2-" ElKotby, M.R., Sarhan, T.A., El-Gamal, M. and Masria, A., 2024. Evaluation of coastal risks to Sea level rise: Case Study of Nile Delta Coast. *Reg. Stud. Mar. Sci.*,

p.103791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2024.103791>

3- ElKotby, M.R., Sarhan, T.A., El-Gamal, M. and Masria, A., 2024. Impact evaluation of development plans in the Egyptian harbors on morphological changes using numerical simulation (case study: Damietta harbor, northeastern coast of Egypt). *Remote Sens. Appl.: Soc. Environ.*, p.101301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2024.101301>

وان الأبحاث المنشورة مستخرجة من الرسالة المذكورة وان أسماء جميع السادة المشرفين موجود ع الأبحاث وان الباحثة مي رمضان عبد الحلیم هي الباحث الأول ع جميع الأبحاث.

المقر

مي رمضان عبد الحلیم

أعضاء لجنة المناقشة والحكم،

عنوان الرسالة: تطبيق الاستشعار عن بعد والنمذجة المورفولوجية في التحكم بمشاكل المنطقة الساحلية.

اسم الباحث: م/ مي رمضان عبد الحليم الكتبي

الدرجة العلمية: دكتورة الفلسفة في العلوم الهندسية في الهندسة (هندسة ري والهيدروليكا)

لجنة الإشراف

التوقيع	الوظيفة	الاسم
.....	أستاذ المنشآت المائية المتفرغ بقسم هندسة الري والهيدروليكا كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة	أ.د. محمود محمد عبد العزيز الجمل
.....	أستاذ مساعد متفرغ بهندسة الري والهيدروليكا كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة	أ.د. ثروت عيد سرحان

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.....	أستاذ الهيدروليكا - نائب مدير معهد بحوث النيل المركز القومي لبحوث المياه	أ.د. أحمد مصطفى أحمد موسي
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وكيل الكلية للدراسات العليا والبحوث

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أ.م.د. ريهام محسن عز الدين

المشرفون،،،

- عنوان الرسالة:** تطبيق الاستشعار عن بعد والنمذجة المورفولوجية في التحكم بمشاكل المنطقة الساحلية.
- اسم الباحث:** م/مي رمضان عبد الحليم الكتبي
- الدرجة العلمية:** دكتوراة الفلسفة في العلوم الهندسية في الهندسة (هندسة ري و الهيدروليكا)

لجنة الإشراف

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جامعة المنصورة
كلية الهندسة
قسم هندسة الري والهيدروليكا

**تطبيق الاستشعار عن بعد والنمذجة المورفولوجية في التحكم بمشاكل
المنطقة الساحلية.**

رسالة مقدمة من

المهندسة / مي رمضان عبد الحليم

**مدرس مساعد بقسم هندسة الري والهيدروليكا بكلية الهندسة -
جامعة المنصورة**

**كجزء من المتطلبات للحصول على درجة دكتوراة الفلسفة في العلوم الهندسية
"هندسة ري وهيدروليكا"**

تحت إشراف

الأستاذ الدكتور / محمود الجمل

**أستاذ المنشآت المائية المتفرغ بقسم هندسة الري والهيدروليكا
كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة**

الأستاذ الدكتور / ثروت عيد سرحان

**أستاذ مساعد متفرغ بقسم هندسة الري والهيدروليكا
كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة**

كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة

2025